

micaado

migrant integration cockpits & dashboards

Deliverable D7.9

Logbook and concept convergence kit for developing an ICT solution to migrant integration

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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

The MICADO project is an interdisciplinary project involving research institutions, public authorities, SMEs and technology developers. The aim is to facilitate public services and integration-relevant information (in aspects related to housing, health, education, labour, and participation) to migrants through digital means, in the form of the MICADO Cockpits and Dashboards.

This deliverable consists of two parts: Logbook for Development (Part I) and Convergence Handbook (Part II). Both of these documents were aimed at bridging the gaps between the research part of the project and the development phase. Together, they formed a Concept Convergence Kit that allowed for convergence between all partners and pilot cities on the essential requirements for development of the MICADO digital solution.

Based on the co-creation, co-design and interviewing process conducted by MICADO researchers in 2019 in MICADO's 4 pilot cities (Bologna, Antwerp, Hamburg and Madrid), the gathered insights from different local stakeholders – public authorities (PAs), migrants and civil society organizations (CSOs) – were compiled into a **Logbook for Development**. The Logbook gathered and systematized in a comprehensive way the collected data on migrant population in the pilot cities; demands of PAs, migrants and CSOs; existing Apps and digital tools usage, assigning them an order of priority (critical, important, desirable). Project partners compiled migrants “user personas” to characterize certain profiles of the migrant population, present in the pilot cities, and described their arrival process, needs and requirements through “user stories”. The latter were also compiled for PAs and CSOs. Frequently Asked Questions by migrants were gathered as well. Finally, a series of limitations and difficulties were identified while gathering both qualitative and quantitative information to be considered also during the development phase of the MICADO Dashboard and Cockpits solution: e.g. data integration and protection, filtering of information, user engagement, terminology, etc.

To provide a more manageable resource for the first convergence workshop carried out in early 2020, the Logbook was transformed into the **Convergence Handbook**, a document with attractive layout, easy-to-work-with within a relatively short time by a variety of stakeholders (the MICADO project partners) with different levels of technical, scientific and public administration understanding. During the convergence phase, common needs of the different cities needed to be identified and turned into technical features and first requirements for development of the MICADO solution. In this sense, most of the tables, user personas, user stories and technical solutions were turned into a visually appealing and easy-to-use handbook with dedicated work templates for small discussion sessions during the convergence workshop. The handbook included colour coded needs for easy recognition, visual elements and limited text descriptions. The needs were cut into “cards”, discussed in small interdisciplinary groups. After identifying the most important and common needs between the four cities, the technical developers provided their opinion on the technical feasibility, the public authorities on the data availability to implement the needed features and thus a final allocation was done on the work template. The final allocation was the base for developing the MICADO minimal viable product.

Taken together, this deliverable **describes the innovative ways of bridging the research and development phases used in the MICADO project**. As such, it could be useful for other projects related to migrant integration and, more broadly, to those that develop digital solutions aimed at improving public services using co-creation processes.

PART I - LOGBOOK FOR DEVELOPMENT

The Logbook for Development **compiles the results of the co-creative sessions and data/solutions mapping** developed earlier in the project into a source book for later IT development. It gathers in a systematic way the **demands of different stakeholders** (migrants, public authorities and CSOs) harvested in a total of **28 workshops and several interviews** carried out by each partnering city between June and September 2019 to specify **local demands and needs in regard to migrant integration**.

These demands were collected through a **co-creative process** in which **137 migrants, asylum-seekers and refugees** (half of them women) and **65 representatives of civil society organizations (CSOs) and public authorities** were consulted. Additionally, through this process, feedback on the **existing digital solutions and to identify potential features to include in the MICADO-solution** was gathered.¹

The Logbook for Development brings all these insights together as a **first step of the convergence process among the 4 pilot cities – Hamburg, Antwerp, Bologna, and Madrid**. Explicit attention is given to spotting the **differences and similarities among cities and actors involved in the five delineated MICADO-domains** - education, employment, health, housing and participation - the project aims to tackle and include in the digital solution.

The structure of this document is the following: in the first place, using data from the national statistical institutes, Eurostat, and, OECD, a **description of the local migrant populations** is presented in section 2 to shed light on the sociodemographic composition of MICADO's target groups. Secondly, an overview of the **demands of the stakeholders involved and the usage of existing apps** is offered in section 3. Third, **User Personas, User Stories and FAQs** are gathered in sections 4, 5, and 6 to inform and facilitate the development of the MICADO tool. Subsequently, the **difficulties identified while gathering both qualitative and quantitative data in WP1 and WP2** are briefly assessed in section 7, pinpointing the possible hindrances that the project might encounter in the development phase. Section 8 concludes.

¹ A extensive and detailed report on the demands and existing solutions can be found in *Deliverable 2.1 "Overview of existing solutions incl. data and Demand Analysis for MICADO key services."*

1. Structure of local migrant populations

A necessary first step for the development of the MICADO solution is to describe the structure of local migrant populations. Knowledge of the number and composition of migrant populations in the four pilot cities will allow the developers to better profile the digital solution targeting the potential users. We gathered **descriptive data on foreign citizens living in the four cities/regions, both migrants and refugees/asylum seekers, by their origin, gender, age, and legal status of residence**. Some data on the situation of migrants in the **local labour market** are also offered, as it is one of the most significant challenges newcomers face in the integration process.

The **availability of comparable data** varies depending on the level of aggregation. In short, while there is plenty of data on migration at the country-level and many indicators available at the regional-level, access to local/city-level data is limited.² In what follows, we try to fill in the shortcomings of the initial MICADO research phase, which focused on the national level, and present **the most recent subnational data (2018/2019) on Autonomous Community of Madrid (region), Hamburg (city and region), Metropolitan City of Bologna (Province), and Antwerp (Province)**. Of course, indicators would change if we were to restrain the analysis to the city-level. We chose these levels of aggregation for each city/region due to data accessibility and comparability. Moreover, we can assume that potential users of MICADO will also live outside of the city limits (be it province in case of Bologna and Antwerp or region in the case of Madrid). However, in the few cases in which comparable data was available, we completed the picture with data at the municipality level for the sake of comparison).

Table 1 gathers basic information on the population of each city/region and the **share of the population with foreign nationality**.³ **Hamburg stands out as the city/region with the biggest share of the foreign population (16.5%), followed by Madrid (13.2%), Bologna (12.0%), and Antwerp (11.8%).**

Table 2 gathers the same information, this time at municipal level, showing that **the share of population with foreign nationality is the highest in the City of Antwerp (21.4% – almost doubling the number for the Province of Antwerp)**, followed by the city of Hamburg (16.5% – same data as in table 1, as there is no difference between the NUTS-2 level and the

² Deliverable D1.2 “Migration Challenges for MICADO” already highlighted the lack of data, official statistics and sometimes transparency at the regional and local levels and presented a vast collection of secondary and statistical data mostly at the national level. See Section 5 of Deliverable D1.2 “Migration Challenges for MICADO” for more information on the issue of availability of data at the local level.

³ There are different ways of measuring the number of migrants in a given region. We opted for official national statistics of residents with foreign nationality over those that count residents born in a foreign country or residents with migration background. With all the trade-offs involved, we believe that this indicator is well suited for the purposes of developing the MICADO solution. This kind of data includes only migrants registered in the official census, most of them with some kind of residence permit. Thus, we can assume that including those that reside without an official permit and those undocumented, would increase in most cases the ‘real’ share of the population with foreign nationality. Data from Madrid and Hamburg offer some insight into the magnitude of such an increase. There are 880,918 foreigners with a residence permit in the Community of Madrid. However, as it is possible to register in the census without a residence permit, we know that there are additional 67,906 foreigners who live in Madrid without official permission: 7.1% of the total foreign population (Observatorio de la Inmigración, 2019). In Hamburg, 3% of registered foreigners do not have a residence permit, toleration or permission to stay (they are already included in the total of 305,621 in Table 1).

municipality), Bologna (15.5%, compared to 12% in the province) and Madrid (14.1% compared to 13.2% in the Community of Madrid).

Table 1. Share of population with foreign nationality, regions, 2019

City/Region	Population	Population with foreign nationality	Percentage of foreign population
Community of Madrid	6,661,949	880,918	13.2
Hamburg	1,847,253	305,621	16.5
Bologna (Metropolitan City)	1,014,728	121,462	12.0
Province of Antwerp	1,847,486	217,454	11.8

Source: Instituto Nacional de Estadística, INE; Statistische Bundesamt, Statistisches Amt für Hamburg und Schleswig-Holstein, ISTAT; and Directorate General Statistics - Statistics Belgium, STATBEL. Notes: Latest available data for 2019 as of 31.10.2019.

Table 2. Share of population with foreign nationality, municipalities, 2019

Municipality	Population	Population with foreign nationality	Percentage of foreign population
Madrid	3,275,195	462,343	14.1
Hamburg	1,847,253	305,621	16.5
Bologna	391,984	60,698	15.5
Antwerp	527,461	112,859	21.4

Source: Padrón Municipal de Habitantes, Ayuntamiento de Madrid; City of Antwerp, Districts – en loketwerking; <http://inumeridibolognametropolitana.it/cittadini-stranieri-bologna>; Statistisches Amt für Hamburg und Schleswig-Holstein.

The top five nationalities of the foreign population are presented in Table 3. Nationals from **Romania and Morocco** stand out as the most frequent nationalities of foreigners both in the Community of Madrid and the Metropolitan City of Bologna, with important presence also in Flanders, ranked 3rd and 4th (in this case, the lowest level of aggregation for which there is comparable data is the Flanders region). In Hamburg, the dominant nationality is **Turkish** followed by **Polish**, which also takes second place in Flanders (after the neighbouring **Netherlands**). In the Community of Madrid, the list is completed by **China** (3rd), **Colombia** and **Venezuela**, confirming the high share of Latin American immigrants in the region. In Hamburg, 6.6% of migrants come from **Afghanistan**, 5% from **Syria**, with **Russia** in the 5th place. In the Metropolitan City of Bologna, **Pakistan, Albania, and Ukraine** complete the ranking. In total, the migrant population is the most heterogeneous with regard to nationality in Hamburg with only 37.3% of all migrants declaring one of the top five nationalities, and most homogeneous in Bologna with the top five nationalities gathering a 51.5% share of all foreigners in the metropolitan region.

Table 3. Top five nationalities of the foreign population

Madrid (Community)			Hamburg			Bologna (Metropolitan City)			Antwerp (Flanders Region)		
Nationality	N	%	Nationality	N	%	Nationality	N	%	Nationality	N	%
Romania	160,126	18.2	Turkey	45,245	14.6	Romania	26,753	22.0	Netherlands	141,806	23.8
Morocco	79,105	9.0	Poland	24,545	7.9	Morocco	12,915	10.6	Poland	42,885	7.2
China	62,018	7.0	Afghanistan	20,555	6.6	Pakistan	8,055	6.6	Romania	39,047	6.6
Colombia	47,524	5.4	Syria	15,390	5.0	Albania	7,977	6.6	Morocco	28,968	4.9
Venezuela	42,165	4.8	Russia	9,980	3.2	Ukraine	6,883	5.7	Italy	24,818	4.2
Total top 5	390,938	44.4		115,715	37.3		62,583	51.5		277,524	46.6

Source: Instituto Nacional de Estadística, INE; Statistische Bundesamt, DESTATIS; Istituto Nazionale di Statistica, ISTAT; Directorate General Statistics - Statistics Belgium, STATBEL; and National Bank of Belgium (2019).

Table 4 displays the shares of the **total number of foreigners by their nationality** with more detail for Europe and MENA (the Middle East and North Africa). Given that Table 3 offered data only for the Flanders region, we opted for including both the level of Province and the City of Antwerp. The first takeaway is that high percentages of migrants living in the four cities/regions come from other EU member state. Also, there is divergence among the cities, as the **share of EU migrants** is 27.9% in the Metropolitan City of Bologna, while it increases to 60.1% for the Province of Antwerp (in the City of Antwerp it is slightly lower – 49.8%). In the Metropolitan City of Bologna and the Community of Madrid, most of EU migrants come from **Central and Eastern Europe (CEE)**. In Hamburg, about half of the foreigners with a member state nationality come from CEE. In the city and Province of Antwerp, they come mostly from West and North of the EU15. Migrants from **non-EU European countries** are present mostly in Hamburg and the Metropolitan City of Bologna (27.8% and 21.2%, respectively). Incomers from the **MENA** region account for about 10-17% of all immigrants in all cities/regions. In the Community of Madrid and the Metropolitan City of Bologna, City of Antwerp these are mostly Moroccans, while in Hamburg a considerable proportion comes from Syria. About one out of four migrants in Hamburg and the Province of Antwerp declare having other (not European nor MENA) nationality. In the Metropolitan City of Bologna, 35.4% do not have European or MENA nationalities, while in the Community of Madrid more than half of the migrants come from outside of Europe and MENA.

Table 4. Foreign population by nationality over the total of immigrants, 2019 (in %)

Nationality	City/Region				
	Community of Madrid	Hamburg	Metropolitan city of Bologna	Province of Antwerp	City of Antwerp
EU	33.0	33.2	27.9	60.1	49.8
West and North EU15	6.6	6.6	1.8	34.7	23.1
South EU15	3.9	9.6	0.9	8.8	10.4
EU12/EU13 (East) ⁴	22.5	17.1	25.3	16.5	16.3
EUROPE NON-EU	4.2	27.8	21.2	3.8	4.3
Turkey	0.1	14.6	0.4	-	3.8
Ukraine	2.7	1.3	5.7	-	0.5
Russia	0.5	3.2	0.7	-	1.1
Albania	0.1	0.5	6.6	-	0.3
Moldova	0.3	0.1	5.4	-	-
Serbia	0.1	2.3	0.9	-	0.6
Macedonia	-	2.2	0.4	-	0.5
Bosnia-Herzegovina	-	1.3	0.2	-	0.4
Kosovo	-	0.8	0.4	-	0.5
Georgia	0.2	0.2	0.3	-	0.2
MENA	10.0	12.0	15.5	10.4	17.0
Morocco	9.0	0.3	10.6	-	10.4
Syria	0.2	5.0	0.1	-	2.6
Iran	0.2	2.7	0.7	-	0.5
Tunisia	0.1	0.4	2.7	-	0.2
Egypt	0.1	0.8	0.9	-	0.2
Iraq	0.1	1.7	0.1	-	2.7
Algeria	0.2	0.2	0.2	-	0.2
Lebanon	0.1	0.2	0.1	-	0.1
OTHER	52.8	27.0	35.4	25.7	28.9
TOTAL	100	100	100	100	100

Source Instituto Nacional de Estadística, INE; Statistische Bundesamt, DESTATIS; Istituto Nazionale di Statistica, ISTAT; and Statistiek Vlaanderen City of Antwerp, Districts - en loketwerking. Notes: Latest available data for 2019 as of 31.10.2019, except for Hamburg (31.12.2018); Shares lower than 0.1 were omitted from the table.

⁴ EU12/EU13 category entails all Central and Eastern European countries that became members of the EU in 2004 and after.

Table 5 displays in more detail the data on **migrants with nationalities other than European or MENA**. In the Metropolitan City of Bologna, one out of four of all immigrants come from **Asia** (mostly Pakistan, China, and The Philippines). In Hamburg, 15.7% are of Asian nationality, with a high share of immigrants from Afghanistan. In the City of Antwerp, it is 16.3% from Asia with the largest share from Afghanistan and India. In the Community of Madrid, 35.9% of incomers are from **South and Central America**, a distinctive characteristic of the local migrant population due to the shared language. Colombian is the most common nationality, with established inflow also from Ecuador, and a more recent one from Venezuela. In Hamburg, the Metropolitan City of Bologna, and the City of Antwerp the shares of residents from Latin American countries are small (under 4%). Finally, migrants from **Sub-Saharan Africa** account only for 3.3% in Madrid, 5.7% in Hamburg, 6.3% Metropolitan City of Bologna and 7.3% in the City of Antwerp.

Table 5. Foreign population from other countries than Europe and MENA over the total of immigrants, 2019 (in %)

Nationality	City/Region			
	Community of Madrid	Hamburg	Metropolitan city of Bologna	City of Antwerp
Asia	11.2	15.7	25.1	16.6
China	7.0	2.0	5.2	1.6
The Philippines	1.7	0.3	5.1	0.3
Pakistan	0.4	0.4	6.6	0.7
Afghanistan	0.0	6.6	0.1	3.7
Bangladesh	0.8	0.1	4.8	0.2
India	0.3	1.5	1.2	2.1
Sri Lanka	0.0	0.1	1.6	0.6
Japan	0.2	0.6	0.2	0.2
Vietnam	0.1	0.8		0.1
Thailand	0.0	0.5	0.1	0.3
South Korea	0.2	0.5		0.1
South and Central America	35.9	2.4	3.5	2.0
Colombia	5.4	0.3	0.2	0.1
Peru	3.8	0.2	1.2	0.1
Venezuela	4.8	0.1	0.1	0.1
Ecuador	4.2	0.3	0.3	0.2
Dominican Republic	2.9	0.1	0.3	0.1
Paraguay	3.0			
Honduras	2.9	0.1		
Brazil	1.8	0.7	0.6	0.4
Bolivia	2.3			
Cuba	1.1	0.1	0.5	0.1
Argentina	1.2	0.1	0.1	
Nicaragua	0.8			
El Salvador	0.7			
Chile	0.5	0.2	0.1	0.2
Sub-Saharan Africa	3.3	5.7	6.3	7.3
Nigeria	1.0	0.4	1.6	0.9
Ghana	0.1	2.0	0.5	1.0
Eritrea		0.9	0.4	0.6
Senegal	0.4	0.1	0.8	0.3
Cameroon	0.2	0.1	0.8	0.4
Equatorial Guinea	0.6			
Mali	0.2		0.2	
Ivory Coast	0.1	0.1	0.4	0.1
Guinea	0.1	0.2	0.1	
Cape Verde	0.1		0.1	0.1
Gambia		0.2	0.3	0.1
Ethiopia		0.1	0.2	0.1
Somalia		0.3	0.1	1.1
Democratic Rep. of the Congo			0.1	
Rep. Congo			0.1	0.7

Guinea-Bissau	0.1	0.1		
Angola	0.1		0.1	0.4
Rest	2.3	3.2	0.4	3.1
TOTAL OTHER	52.8	27.0	35.4	28.9

Source Instituto Nacional de Estadística, INE; Statistische Bundesamt, DESTATIS; Istituto Nazionale di Statistica, ISTAT; and Statistiek Vlaanderen. City of Antwerp, Districts - en loketwerking Notes: Latest available data for 2019 as of 31.10.2019, except for Hamburg (31.12.2018); Shares lower than 0.1 were omitted from the table.

Migrants in all cities/regions considered are relatively **young** (see Figure 1). Less than 5% of the population with foreign nationality in the Community of Madrid and the Metropolitan City of Bologna is over 65 years old. The share of the oldest is higher in Antwerp (7.4%) and Hamburg (10.1%). Over 20% of the foreign population in the Province of Antwerp and the Metropolitan City of Bologna is under 18 years old, followed by Madrid (18.2%) and Hamburg (12.3%). On average, the **Metropolitan City of Bologna and the Province of Antwerp have the youngest migrant populations and Hamburg the oldest one.**

Figure 1. Population with foreign nationality by age, 2019 (in %)

Source: Instituto Nacional de Estadística, INE; Statistische Bundesamt, DESTATIS; Istituto Nazionale di Statistica, ISTAT; Directorate General Statistics - Statistics Belgium, STATBEL. Notes: Latest available data for 2019 as of 31.10.2019, except for Hamburg (31.12.2018).

With regard to **gender** differences, the **Metropolitan City of Bologna and the Community of Madrid stand out as more feminized** migrant populations (53.9% and 52.9%, respectively, see Table 6). In **Hamburg and the Province of Antwerp, males** are predominant among foreigners. Taking into consideration both the age and gender, the biggest differences are to be found among those aged **35-64 in the Metropolitan City of Bologna (females 26.8% and males 19.6%)** and those aged 18-34 in the Madrid region and Hamburg (4.4 percentage points [from now on pp] higher share of females in the Community of Madrid and, inversely 3 pp lower one in the Hanseatic city).

Table 6. Population with foreign nationality by age and gender, 2019 (in %)

Age	Gender	City/Region			
		Community of Madrid	Hamburg	Metropolitan City of Bologna	Province of Antwerp
0-17	Male	9.3	6.4	11.5	11,6
	Female	8.9	5.8	10.0	10,9
18-34	Male	13.8	17.5	13.7	14,6
	Female	17.2	14.5	14.0	15,1
35-64	Male	22.5	24.2	19.6	21,7
	Female	24.4	21.4	26.8	18,6
65+	Male	1.5	5.0	1.3	3,9
	Female	2.4	5.1	3.2	3,5
All	Male	47.1	53.1	46.1	51,8
	Female	52.9	46.9	53.9	48,2
Total		100	100	100	100

Source: Instituto Nacional de Estadística, INE; Statistische Bundesamt, DESTATIS; Istituto Nazionale di Statistica, ISTAT; Directorate General Statistics - Statistics Belgium, STATBEL. Notes: Latest available data for 2019 as of 31.10.2019, except for Hamburg (31.12.2018); In Madrid, the age categories are slightly different (0-19; 20-34; 35-64, 65+).

Table 7 gathers detailed information on the foreign population by **legal status of residence permit and by nationality** (grouped in regions) in the four selected cities/regions in absolute numbers.

Table 7. Foreign population by residence permit and nationality (region) 2018/2019

	EU	EFTA	Europe Non-EU	Africa	North America	South and Central America	Asia	Australia	n/a	Total	
LEGAL STATUS (RESIDENCE PERMIT)											
Community of Madrid	FREE MOVEMENT UNDER EU LAW	423,395	2,306	3,379	11,568	6,049	73,990	6,248	220	81	527,236
	TEMPORARY RESIDENCE	-	-	3,691	8,658	3,658	32,954	15,494	131	90	64,676
	Not allowed to work permit	-	-	541	1,496	953	3,811	2,257	18	42	9,118
	Family reunification	-	-	659	2,989	859	4,733	4,844	43	15	14,142
	Work permit	-	-	1,788	3,005	1,769	18,359	7,230	70	21	32,242
	Exceptional circumstances	-	-	703	1,168	77	6,051	1,163	0	12	9,174
	LONG TERM RESIDENCE			20,830	84,596	3,270	111,102	70,913	77	310	291,098
	TOTAL	423,395	2,306	27,900	104,822	12,977	218,046	92,655	428	481	883,010
Hamburg	FREE MOVEMENT UNDER EU LAW	102,815		2,270	665	110	675	655	25	-	107,215
	EXEMPTED OF NECESSARY RESIDENCE DOCUMENT, DISPLACED	-		105	15	45	10	15	0	-	190
	LONG TERM RESIDENCE	-		55,920	5,830	1,625	2,460	14,365	240	-	80,440
	TEMPORARY RESIDENCE	5		18,990	11,440	2,940	3,790	46,730	655	-	84,550
	Temporary Residence for Persons in Vocational Training [Befr,Aufenthaltsr,z,Zweck d,Ausbild,, AufenthG]	-		1,260	770	805	1,095	4,985	140	-	9,055
	Temporary Residence for Persons in Employment, [Befr,Aufenthaltsr,z,Zweck d,Erwerbst,,AufenthG]	-		2,425	610	1,125	800	4,465	305	-	9,730
	Temporary Residence for Persons in Employment [Befr, AE,aus	-		2,960	4,455	10	120	25,680	5	-	33,230

	völkerr,,human,,pol,Gründ en,AufenthG]										
	Temporary Residence for Persons in Employment [Befr,Aufenthaltserlaubn,a,fam, Gründen, AufenthG]	-	9,565	5,220	715	1,510	10,375	135	-	27,520	
	Resident status with special right of residence	-	2,785	380	290	260	1,225	70	-	5,010	
	APPLICATION FOR A RESIDENCE PERMIT	-	2,945	2,170	305	665	7,405	70	-	13,560	
	TOLERATED	5	1,925	1,350	5	60	1,860	0	-	5,205	
	RESIDENCE PERMIT [AUFENTHALTSGESTAT TUNG]	-	1,000	650	0	40	5,420	0	-	7,110	
	WITHOUT RESIDENCE PERMIT, TOLERATION OR PERMISSION	285	2,470	1,505	285	505	4,235	75	-	9,360	
	TOTAL	103,110	85,625	23,625	5,315	8,205	80,685	1,065	-	307,630	
MC Bologna	WORK PERMIT TEMPORARY RESIDENCE	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	31,517	
	WORK PERMIT LONG TERM RESIDENCE	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	50,091	
	TOTAL	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	81,608	
Antwerp	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	
	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	
	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	
	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	

Source: Observatorio Permanente de la Inmigración (2019), Ministerio de Trabajo, Migraciones y Seguridad Social (2018); Statistische Bundesamt, DESTATIS Table [12521-0026](#); Istituto Nazionale di Statistica, ISTAT.

Table 8 displays the same information in a clearer way: in percentages, with **legal status grouped to (i) free movement under EU law, (ii) temporary residence permit, (iii) long term residence permit.**

Table 8. Foreign population by residence permit and nationality (region) 2018/2019 (in % of total foreigners)

		EU	EFTA	Europe Non-EU	Africa	North America	South and Central America	Asia	Australia	n/a	Total
Community of Madrid	LEGAL STATUS (RESIDENCE PERMIT)										
	FREE MOVEMENT UNDER EU LAW	47.9	0.3	0.4	1.3	0.7	8.4	0.7	0.0	0.0	59.7
	TEMPORARY RESIDENCE	-	-	0.4	1.0	0.4	3.7	1.8	0.0	0.0	7.3
	LONG TERM RESIDENCE	-	-	2.4	9.6	0.4	12.6	8.0	0.0	0.0	33.0
	TOTAL	47.9	0.3	3.2	11.9	1.5	24.7	10.5	0.0	0.1	100.0
Hamburg	FREE MOVEMENT UNDER EU LAW	33.4		0.7	0.2	0.0	0.2	0.2	0.0	-	34.9
	TEMPORARY RESIDENCE	0.0		6.2	3.7	1.0	1.2	15.2	0.2	-	27.5
	LONG TERM RESIDENCE			18.2	1.9	0.5	0.8	4.7	0.1	-	26.1
	OTHER	0.1		2.7	1.8	0.2	0.4	6.2	0.0	-	11.5
	TOTAL	33.5		27.8	7.7	1.7	2.7	26.2	0.3	-	100.0
MC Bologna	WORK PERMIT TEMPORARY RESIDENCE	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	38.6
	WORK PERMIT LONG TERM RESIDENCE	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	61.4
	TOTAL	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	100.0

Source: Observatorio Permanente de la Inmigración (2019), Ministerio de Trabajo, Migraciones y Seguridad Social (2018); Statistische Bundesamt, DESTATIS Table [12521-0026](#); Istituto Nazionale di Statistica, ISTAT.

Unfortunately, detailed data is available only for Community of Madrid and Hamburg. Nearly 60% of legal residents with foreign nationality in the **Madrid** region entered the country under the free movement EU law and **48% have the nationality of another member state**. Only about 1/3 of the 24.7% share of the foreign population with Latin American nationality entered under free movement law, but nearly half of them are long-term legal residents in the central region of Spain. Altogether, **only 7.3% of foreign residents in the Community of Madrid have a temporary residence permit**, while one out of three has a long-term permit.

In **Hamburg**, a total of 34.9% of foreign residents entered the country under the free movement EU law, while **26.1% has a long-term residence permit**. From the remaining 39%, about two out of three immigrants have a temporary residence permit and the rest are either tolerated, waiting for the decision on residence permit or are in another precarious legal situation. Thus, **almost 40% of the foreign nationality population in Hamburg has an unstable legal residence status, compared to only 14.4% in Madrid** (adding those with temporary and no legal residence permit).

There is fewer data available about the Metropolitan City of Bologna. What is certain is that around **two out of three foreign residents in the Metropolitan City of Bologna have a work permit** and most of these permits (61.4%) are long-term ones.

Refugees and asylum seekers are of particular interest for the development of MICADO. While it is true that networks dedicated to the integration of this group into the societies of receiving countries seem to adopt a holistic approach, and thus one might claim that this collective is well taken care of in many cases, it is true that it is also one of the most vulnerable groups among the foreign population, with particular difficulties and challenges to overcome in the integration process. The number of asylum applications during **2018** was relatively small (compared to the total number of foreigners): **1,380 applications in the Province of Bologna, 4,139 in Hamburg, and 20,731 in the Community of Madrid** (see Table 9).

Table 9. Number of asylum applications and inflow of refugees/asylum seekers, 2018 and 2019

	Madrid (Community)	Hamburg	Bologna (Province)	Antwerp
Asylum applications from 1 January 2019 to 31 October 2019	-	3,023	2,341	-
2018 inflow of Refugees/Asylum Seekers	20,731	4,139	1,380	-

Source: Oficina de Asilo y Refugio (2019); Bundesamt für Migration und Flüchtlinge (2019; 2018); Istituto Nazionale di Statistica, ISTAT (data from the Ministry of Home Affairs - Permessi di soggiorno dei cittadini stranieri).

As Table 10 shows, most asylum seekers in **2018 in the Community of Madrid came from Latin American** countries: Venezuela, Colombia, El Salvador, Honduras. Also, a significant number of Palestinians applied for asylum in this region of Spain. In **Hamburg**, most of the asylum seekers come from **Afghanistan, Syria, and Iraq**. In the **Province of Bologna**, there is more diversity of backgrounds of those seeking protection; they mostly come from **Nigeria, Pakistan, Ukraine, Bangladesh, and Morocco**. In the City of Antwerp, the largest group of asylum seekers are from Turkey, followed by Syria, Palestine, Iraq, and Afghanistan.

Table 10. Top five nationalities of asylum seekers in 2018

	Madrid (Community)	Hamburg	Bologna (Province)	Antwerp (City)
Venezuela	8,107	Afghanistan 1,418	Nigeria 225	Turkey 104
Colombia	3,652	Syria 875	Pakistan 150	Syria 79
Palestine	1,251	Iraq 427	Ukraine 123	Palestine 64
El Salvador	1,210	-	Bangladesh 108	Iraq 38
Honduras	1,081	-	Morocco 86	Afghanistan 35

Source: Oficina de Asilo y Refugio (2019); Deutscher Bundestag (2019); Istituto Nazionale di Statistica, ISTAT (data from the Ministry of Home Affairs - Permessi di soggiorno dei cittadini stranieri), City of Antwerp, Districts - en loketwerking.

Until now, we have shown the most recent data on the structure of local foreign populations in the four selected cities/regions. However, these populations are very **dynamic** and their composition changes greatly in time. To account for that change, Figure 2 plots the annual inflows to the **Province of Bologna** of **non-EU citizens**, disaggregated by the residence permit. The Bologna Province welcomes around 6,000 newcomers per year, although these numbers have peaked to over 8,000 in 2011, nearly 10,000 in 2009, and over 14,000 in the record-high 2010. Two important tendencies should be noted. Firstly, the number of work residence permits, after an initial increase (up to 2010), decreased to almost cease to exist in the last four years. At the same time, the number of asylums granted and applied for has increased consistently. All in all, **until 2010 most of the residence permits issued were work permits**, but, **recently, family residence permits are the most common** with an increase also in **asylum applications**.

Figure 2. Annual inflows of non-EU citizens by the residence permit, Bologna Province 2007-2018

Source: Istituto Nazionale di Statistica, ISTAT (Ministry of Home Affairs - Permessi di soggiorno dei cittadini stranieri).

Employment is a key element of migrant integration process. The last part of this section sheds light on the **labour situation of the local foreign populations**. Table 11 shows the unemployment rates among nationals and foreigners by gender. Note that this data does not allow for disaggregation below the regional (NUTS-2) level. The last three columns on the right display the difference in percentage points between the foreign population and the national one. **Unemployment is consistently higher among those with foreign citizenship. Foreign females face higher unemployment risk in the Province of Antwerp, Hamburg,**

and Emilia-Romagna. Interestingly, only in the Community of Madrid, where the overall unemployment rates are the highest (14.4% for nationals and 21.9% for foreigners), foreign males are significantly more exposed to unemployment than male Spaniards. Although unemployment in the Community of Madrid is higher among women, **the difference between foreign females' unemployment rate (23.6%) and the Spanish females one (18.2%) is lower than between Spanish and foreign males.**

Table 11. Unemployment rates by gender and citizenship, 2018 (in %)

	National			Foreign			Difference (Foreign - National)		
	Total	Male	Female	Total	Male	Female	Total	Male	Female
European Union	6.5	6.4	7.5	11.6	10.7	12.7	5.1	4.3	5.2
Belgium	5.2	5.4	6.2	12.3	13.3	10.9	7.1	7.9	4.7
Prov. Antwerp	3.9	4.3	5.0	9.4	7.6	12.4	5.5	3.3	7.4
Germany	2.9	3.2	2.9	7.5	8.1	6.6	4.6	4.9	3.7
Hamburg	3.0	3.5	3.6	9.7	9.5	10.0	6.7	6.0	6.4
Spain	14.4	12.9	18.2	21.9	20.3	23.6	7.5	7.4	5.4
Community of Madrid	11.1	10.3	13.2	18.8	19.2	18.4	7.7	8.9	5.2
Italy	10.4	9.7	12.0	14.1	12.0	16.6	3.7	2.3	4.6
Emilia-Romagna	5.0	4.0	6.8	12.6	9.8	15.7	7.6	5.8	8.9

Source: Eurostat [lfst_r_lfur2gan], last update 23.10.2019. Notes: Unemployment rates among those aged 15-64.

However, changing the focus to **employment rates** gives quite a different picture. Table 12 gathers employment rates among nationals and foreigners by gender following the same pattern as Table 11. **Employment rates are higher for both foreign males and females in all countries/regions but Italy**, the only country in which foreigners are less likely to be employed than the nationals. **The biggest gaps are to be found in Hamburg** and, especially for females, in the Province of Antwerp and Emilia-Romagna.

Table 12. Employment rates¹ by gender and citizenship, 2018 (in %)

	National			Foreign			Difference (Foreign - National)		
	Total	Male	Female	Total	Male	Female	Total	Male	Female
European Union	63.9	73.2	54.9	69.0	73.9	64.1	5.1	0.7	9.2
Belgium	57.8	65.4	50.2	65.4	68.6	62.1	7.6	3.2	11.9
Prov. Antwerp	61.3	71.9	48.8	68.5	72.2	64.7	7.2	0.3	15.9
Germany	64.8	72.9	55.4	77.8	80.9	74.7	13.0	8.0	19.3
Hamburg	63.3	70.2	55.4	79.5	82.2	77.0	16.2	12.0	21.6
Spain	59.4	67.2	52.5	62.8	68.0	57.5	3.4	0.8	5.0
Community of Madrid	67.1	71.4	63.4	67.9	72.5	63.5	0.8	1.1	0.1
Italy	61.2	73.8	50.2	58.2	67.0	49.4	-3.0	-6.8	-0.8
Emilia-Romagna	63.1	76.5	52.2	70.7	76.6	64.6	7.6	0.1	12.4

Source: Eurostat [lfst_r_lfe2emprtn], last update 23.10.2019. Notes: ¹Among those aged 15-64.

Table 13 details the employment rates of the low-educated (lower secondary education or less) by gender and citizenship. In general terms, **employment rates of the low-educated are higher among foreigners, and especially among males.** Foreign males' employment rates are significantly higher, compared to the nationals' ones, in the Province of Antwerp (14.8 pp) and Hamburg (12.1 pp). In the Community of Madrid, this difference is of only 3.7 pp. Low-

educated female foreigners are more likely to be employed in this region (15.6 pp difference), but, contrarily, they have fewer chances to be employed in the Province of Antwerp. This is one of the most striking divergences among the cities: **low-educated foreign females' employment rate is almost three times higher in the Community of Madrid than in the Province of Antwerp (59.6% and 22.9%, respectively).**

Table 13. Employment rates of the low-educated¹ by gender and citizenship, 2018 (in percentages)

	National			Foreign			Difference (Foreign - National)		
	Total	Male	Female	Total	Male	Female	Total	Male	Female
European Union	45.4	53.0	37.3	51.9	63.3	40.3	6.5	10.3	3.0
Belgium	35.2	40.3	29.5	37.4	47.4	26.4	2.2	7.1	-3.1
Prov. Antwerp	38.6	43.5	33.5	42.1	58.3	22.9	3.5	14.8	-10.6
Germany	46.8	50.0	43.7	51.9	61.7	41.3	5.1	11.7	-2.4
Hamburg	46.6	50.7	42.3	56.0	62.8	48.7	9.4	12.1	6.4
Spain	51.1	59.6	40.9	52.5	60.8	44.0	1.4	1.2	3.1
Community of Madrid	52.5	59.9	44.0	61.6	63.6	59.6	9.1	3.7	15.6
Italy	41.8	54.1	28.1	56.6	70.3	42.0	14.8	16.2	13.9
Emilia-Romagna	54.3	63.3	43.1	56.0	70.9	41.6	1.7	7.6	-1.5

Source: Eurostat [lfst_r_lfe2empn], last update 23.10.2019. Notes: ¹Less than primary, primary and lower secondary education (ISCED levels 0-2), aged 15-64.

Tables 14 and 15 show in more detail the labour market situation of foreigners (in this case the foreign-born against the native-born), specified by age (youth), by the level of skill (low/medium/high), and by the residence duration (new vs. settled). The latest comparable regional data was gathered by OECD in 2015 (OECD, 2018). To begin with, the **share of low-educated foreign citizens varies among the regions: Madrid has the lowest share (31.6%) and Emilia-Romagna the highest (43.9%),** with Hamburg (36.6%) and the Province of Antwerp (40.6%) in between (see Table 14). **Foreign youth has systematically lower employment rate compared to their native-born peers.** The gap between the employment rates of foreign-born and native-born youth (15-34 years old) is widest in Antwerp (25 pp) and narrowest in Madrid (12.4 pp). Similarly, **foreign youth is more exposed to suffering unemployment, with the highest rate in the Madrid region (30.1%).**

Table 14. Foreign-born labour market for youth, labour market by skills level, and overqualification, 2015 (in %)

Indicator	Place of birth	Region				
		Province of Antwerp	Hamburg	Emilia-Romagna	Community of Madrid	
Share of Low Educated	Foreign-Born	40.6	36.6	43.9	31.6	
Labour Market for Youth, 15-34 years old	Youth Employment rate	Foreign-Born	60.5	69.0	55.8	61.2
		Native-Born	85.5	87.3	74.5	73.6
		Difference	-25	-18.3	-18.7	-12.4
Youth Unemployment rate	Foreign-Born	15.6	-	22.7	30.1	
	Native-Born	7.2	4.8	13.2	20.7	
	Difference	8.4	-	9.5	9.4	
Labour Market by Level of Skill	Share of Employed in Low Skill Jobs	Foreign-Born	27.7	19.7	27.4	29.2
		Native-Born	8.2	3.3	6.0	6.0
		Difference	19.5	16.4	21.4	23.2
Share of Employed in Medium Skill Jobs	Foreign-Born	43.7	47.7	60.7	46.2	
	Native-Born	41.0	38.1	51.2	41.7	
	Difference	2.7	9.6	9.5	4.5	

Share of Employed in High Skill Jobs	Foreign-Born	28.6	32.6	11.8	24.5	
	Native-Born	50.8	58.6	42.8	52.3	
	<i>Difference</i>	<i>-22.2</i>	<i>-26</i>	<i>-31</i>	<i>-27.8</i>	
Overqualified Employed	Share of Employed in Low/Medium Skilled, High Educ.	Foreign-Born	13.1	9.3	9.4	15.2
		Native-Born	7.6	4.8	3.5	13.0
		<i>Difference</i>	<i>5.5</i>	<i>4.4</i>	<i>5.8</i>	<i>2.1</i>

Source: OECD (2018).

The shares of employed in low skill jobs are higher among the foreigners than the natives. With high skill jobs, it is the other way around. For instance, 29.2% of foreigners in the Community of Madrid are employed in low skill jobs and 24.5% in high skill ones (6% and 52.3% for natives, respectively). **In Emilia-Romagna, only 11.8% of foreigners are employed in high skills jobs.** In Hamburg, this percentage is relatively high (32.6%), still short, however, of the 58.6% of natives employed in high skills jobs.

Another labour market inequity the foreigners face is overqualification. **From 9.3% of foreigners in Hamburg to 15.2% in the Community in Madrid are overqualified for their jobs** and these rates are from 2.1 pp (Madrid) to 5.8 pp (Emilia-Romagna) higher for the non-natives.

Table 15. Residence duration by labour market status, by education, and duration of unemployment, 2015 (in %)

Indicator	Place of birth	Region				
		Province of Antwerp	Hamburg	Emilia-Romagna	Community of Madrid	
Residence duration by labour market status	Share of New (<10 years) Employed	Foreign-Born	57.6	-	54.5	67
	Share of New (<10 years) Unemployed	Foreign-Born	11.9	-	15.5	20.2
	Share of New (<10 years) Inactive	Foreign-Born	30.5	-	30.0	12.8
	Total		100	-	100	100
	Share of Settled (>10 years) Employed	Foreign-Born	59.4	-	69.4	63.9
	Share of Settled (>10 years) Unemployed	Foreign-Born	9.2	-	10.7	23.1
	Share of Settled (>10 years) Inactive	Foreign-Born	31.4	-	20.0	13
	Total		100	-	100	100
	Residence duration by education	Share of New (<10 years) Low Educ.	Foreign-Born	41.5	-	44.8
Share of New (<10 years) Medium Educ.		Foreign-Born	32.7	-	40.3	39.2
Share of New (<10 years) High Educ.		Foreign-Born	25.8	-	14.9	37.5
Total			100	-	100	100
Share of Settled (>10 years) Low Educ.		Foreign-Born	39.9	-	42.8	31.3
Share of Settled (>10 years) Medium Educ.		Foreign-Born	35.3	-	44.2	31.8
Share of Settled (>10 years) High Educ.		Foreign-Born	24.8	-	13.1	36.9
Total		100	-	100	100	
Duration of unemployment	Share of Unemployed for less than 1 year	Foreign-Born	57.6	36.9	52.8	46.8
		Native-Born	62.3	52.6	51.6	47.3
	Share of Unemployed for more than 1 year	Foreign-Born	42.4	63.1	47.2	53.2
		Native-Born	37.7	47.4	48.4	52.7

Source: OECD (2018).

Employment rates are lower among foreign-born newcomers (under 10 years), compared to settled foreigners in the Province of Antwerp and Emilia-Romagna, where this difference is more pronounced (54.5% against 69.4%, see Table 15). Somewhat surprisingly, in the Community of Madrid newcomers are more active in the labour market: they are more likely to be employed and less likely to be unemployed than settled migrants. **In Emilia-Romagna, 30% of newcomers are inactive** (meaning not employed nor unemployed actively seeking for a job). **In the Province of Antwerp, the inactivity rate is above 30% both among the newcomers and the settled migrants.**

Newcomers to the Community of Madrid are by far better educated compared to those who came fairly recently to the other three regions. Only 23.2% of newcomers to Madrid have low levels of education, while in the Province of Antwerp and Emilia-Romagna this share is over 40%. The share of highly educated new immigrants in the Community of Madrid triples the one from Emilia-Romagna (37.5% compared to 14.9%). Similarly, **among the settled migrants there are more highly educated ones in the Madrid region and fewer in Emilia-Romagna.**

Finally, regarding the duration of unemployment among the foreigners the **share of those without employment for more than a year is highest in Hamburg (63.1%) and lowest (42.4%) in the Province of Antwerp.** In Emilia-Romagna and the Community of Madrid, the differences between natives and foreigners in the duration of unemployment are insignificant, while **in the Province of Antwerp and Hamburg the exposure to long-term unemployment is higher for the migrant population.**

All in all, migrant populations in the four regions are **diverse and dynamic**. In this section we tried to grasp the basic descriptive data on migrants/refugees in Hamburg, Bologna Metropolitan City (and Emilia-Romagna), the Community of Madrid, and the Province of Antwerp, to provide the basic background on the regional migrant populations for the development of the MICADO solution. What follows are the **key takeaways** from this section.

KEY TAKEAWAYS FROM THE DESCRIPTION OF LOCAL MIGRANT POPULATIONS

- Hamburg stands out as the city/region with the biggest share of foreign population (16.5%), followed by the Community of Madrid (13.2%), the Metropolitan City of Bologna (12.0%), and the Province of Antwerp (11.8%). However, at the municipality level, Antwerp is the city with the highest share with 21.4% of its inhabitants having foreign nationality. Together with data on nationalities and other structural differences, this divergence confirms the need for reliable and comparable disaggregated (local, regional) data to tackle the issue of integration;
- High percentages of immigrants living in the four regions come from a member state of the EU: the share of EU migrants is 27.9% in the Metropolitan City of Bologna, while in the Province of Antwerp it increases to 60.1%;
- Migrants with non-EU European nationality are present mostly in Hamburg and the Metropolitan City of Bologna (27.8% and 21.2%, respectively). In the Community of Madrid, 35.9% of incomers are from South and Central America, a distinctive characteristic of the local migrant population due to the shared language;
- Migrants in all regions considered are relatively young. The Metropolitan City of Bologna and the Province of Antwerp have the youngest migrant populations and Hamburg the oldest one;
- The Metropolitan City of Bologna and the Community of Madrid have more feminized migrant populations (53.9% and 52.9%, respectively). In the Metropolitan City of Bologna, the biggest gender gap in favour of women is among those aged 35-64 (26.8% of females versus 19.6% males);
- Only 7.3% of foreign residents in the Community of Madrid have a temporary residence permit (in Hamburg, 27.5%). Almost 40% of foreign nationality population in Hamburg has an unstable legal residence status, compared to only 14.4% in Madrid;
- The number of asylum applications during 2018 was: 1,380 in the Metropolitan City of Bologna, 4,139 in Hamburg, and 20,731 in the Community of Madrid;
- Unemployment is consistently higher among those with foreign citizenship. Foreign females face higher unemployment risk in the Province of Antwerp, Hamburg, and Emilia-Romagna;
- Employment rates are higher among the foreigners, and especially among males and the low-educated. Low-educated foreign females' employment rate is almost three times lower in the Province of Antwerp compared to the Community of Madrid (22.9% and 59.6%, respectively);
- The foreign youth displays systematically lower employment rates. The shares of employed in low skill jobs are higher among foreigners than natives;
- Employment rates are lower among foreign-born newcomers, excluding the Community of Madrid, where both newcomers and settled immigrants are better educated;
- The share of those without employment for more than a year is highest in Hamburg (63.1%) and lowest (42.4%) in the Province of Antwerp, but in both cities, the exposure to long-term unemployment is higher for the migrant population.

2. Results of co-creation, co-design workshops, and interviews

2.1. Basic needs and demands of migrants, public authorities and CSOs

One of the major concerns of MICADO was to be able to grasp the real demands of the migrants/refugees before developing the digital solution. These demands are of course heterogeneous, as they depend on both the local idiosyncrasies and on the individual sociodemographic characteristics of the future user of MICADO. For instance, **migrants with certain nationalities face specific administrative and legal restraints** as a consequence of treaties between their countries of origin and their country of residence. Thus, certain ethnic communities might be more interested in legal and administrative information to regularize their status, whereas other communities will be more interested in accessing the labour market and demand information on vocational training, language courses, etc. The demands are also dependent on the **level of knowledge of the local language, on the education level of the migrant, on his or her age and gender.**

This said, without doubt, **the main barrier to integration and the one that hinders to a great degree the access to services related to all MICADO domains is the legal status of the migrant.** Dependent on the **type of residence permit** (long-term vs. temporary; work vs. study; individual vs. family; etc.) the newcomer will be entitled to different services and thus he or she will search for **different types of information.** According to a different legal status, migrants might have different needs for information or find themselves in different stages of the integration trajectory, e.g. someone who is not yet registered might not have access to health insurance. Legal status is determined to a great degree by the **nationality** of the migrant, e.g. newcomers under the free movement law of EU from other member states would be the least discriminated in that matter, as they have full access to temporary or long-term residence permits which entitle them to the same health/labour/housing/education services as the natives. There is also a clear **distinction between migrants and refugees/asylum seekers**, with the latter in many cases being provided with more comprehensive attention by the local services. **Providing correct information, according to the legal status of the user, is one of the main challenges in developing the MICADO solution.**

Moreover, an additional challenge for MICADO related to the legal status of the migrant is its dynamic nature. **The legal status of migrants changes constantly**, something clearly affecting the integration process and the access to services provided by institutions and, therefore, the information migrants might search for in the application. **Profiling information is one of the key demands of the migrants.** However, given the existence of prompt changes in the legal status, there is a clear trade-off to profiling information, as **over-profiling it by legal status might lead to restriction of access to information and discrimination.** This issue will be addressed in more detail in section 7.

In the following subsections, we gather and systematize **the demands of migrants/refugees (Table 16), Public Authorities (Table 17), and CSOs (Table 18).** Most of them are requests shared by migrants from more than one city involved. Some issues were raised only in one of the workshops, nevertheless, they might prove useful for migrant integration also in a broader

context. These demands were extracted from the country reports on the results of the co-creation and co-design workshops, and the interviews with the authorities and stakeholders. They are displayed according to the four main MICADO domains (Health, Housing, Labour, and Education), plus Participation, and the transversal ones. In each domain, we classified the demands by their **level of importance**, following the concerns raised during the workshops and interviews: from issues of critical importance, through the important ones, to the ones desirable to include in the MICADO tool. A detailed description of the demands can be found in Deliverable 2.1 “Overview of existing solutions incl. data and Demand Analysis for MICADO key services.”

Subsequently, section 2.2 offers an overview of the results of the MICADO co-creation workshops and interviews with regards to app use, advantages and issues of existing digital solutions from the migrant (2.2.1) and stakeholder perspective (2.2.2) to inform and facilitate the development of the MICADO tool.

2.1.1. Migrants/Refugees

Table 16. Demands of the migrants/refugees

DEMANDS OF THE MIGRANTS / REFUGEES DATA EXTRACTED FROM COUNTRY REPORTS			Critical
			Important
			Desirable
#	Demand	Raised by	City
TRANSVERSAL			
1	Information should be provided in the simplest possible way. Conceptual and visual maps, avoiding long and excessively “legal” texts	Migrants/Refugees	Madrid, Hamburg, Antwerp, Bologna
2	A glossary for each thematic area (terms/concepts)	Migrants/Refugees	Madrid, Antwerp
3	Data should be constantly updated	Migrants/Refugees	Madrid, Hamburg, Antwerp, Bologna
4	Information on where to find free legal advice/counselling	Migrants/Refugees	Madrid, Antwerp
5	Information should be provided in several languages	Migrants/Refugees	Madrid, Hamburg, Antwerp, Bologna
6	Information about the administrative procedures for the variation of legal status and the renewal of residence permits	Migrants/Refugees	Madrid, Hamburg, Antwerp, Bologna
7	Information on the deadlines of the administrative procedures	Migrants/Refugees	Madrid
8	Online translation service/chat box	Migrants/Refugees	Madrid, Hamburg
9	The App could adapt the information to the legal status of the user	Local stakeholders	Madrid
10	Accessibility for (digital) illiterate and blind users	Migrants/Refugees	Antwerp, Bologna
11	The information on the level of government involved should be clearly visible	Migrants/Refugees Local stakeholders	Madrid, Antwerp
12	Filter information by district (proximity)	Migrants/Refugees	Madrid
13	An interactive map with local services such as doctors, NGOs, language courses, etc. featuring filters by domains	Migrants/Refugees	Madrid, Hamburg, Antwerp
14	Include a feature for cultural mediation/translator request	Migrants/Refugees	Antwerp, Bologna
15	Online groups/chats by country of origin and interest	Migrants/Refugees	Madrid, Hamburg
16	Alerts about false information/scams	Local stakeholders	Madrid

17	The App could adapt the information presented to the language skills of the user	Local stakeholders	Madrid
18	Make it available offline	Migrants/Refugees	Antwerp
19	Include a feedback system if information is incorrect	Migrants/Refugees	Antwerp
20	Provide a 'search' function, also available in speech	Migrants/Refugees	Antwerp
21	Provide the option for 'bookmarking' or 'read later'	Migrants/Refugees	Antwerp
HEALTH			
1	Formal requirements and the procedure to be able to obtain the health card (ES), insurance (DE, BE)	Migrants/Refugees	Madrid, Hamburg, Antwerp
2	Information about the difference between emergency health facilities and services and ordinary health and prevention facilities and services (when to go where)	Migrants/Refugees Local stakeholders	Madrid, Antwerp, Bologna
3	Information on NGOs/Official institutions/Medical associations that provide medical (and psychological) support services to immigrants	Migrants/Refugees	Madrid, Hamburg
4	Information on coverage of state-subsidized prescribed medicines for low-income families / information on eligibility for free treatment and about ways to obtain an exemption from payments	Local stakeholders	Madrid, Bologna
5	Advise on how to self-insure for self-employed migrants	Migrants/Refugees	Hamburg
6	Information on which treatment or medication is paid for by the insurance and what needs to be paid by oneself	Migrants/Refugees	Hamburg
7	Information necessary for choosing an insurance	Migrants/Refugees	Antwerp
8	"Doctor finder": a map-based overview of physicians offering (free) walk-in appointments (sorted by GENDER and LANGUAGE)	Migrants/Refugees Local stakeholders	Antwerp, Hamburg
9	Telephone service for translation in hospitals and a list of doctors speaking migrant's languages	Local stakeholders	Hamburg
10	Information on night pharmacies	Migrants/Refugees	Hamburg
11	More knowledge on the history, culture and society of the host community regarding sexuality and health, example: www.zanzu.de/en/	Migrants/Refugees	Hamburg
HOUSING			
1	Information on rights and obligations as tenants. Sample of a contract with a simple explanation	Migrants/Refugees, Local stakeholders	Madrid, Hamburg, Antwerp
2	Information on alternative housing/ways to find a flat: cooperatives, social housing, student housing, bonds by friends	Local stakeholders	Hamburg
3	Information about the requirements to qualify for e.g. social housing and government benefits such as rental subsidies	Migrants/Refugees	Antwerp
4	Information on NGOs accompanying migrants in the process of finding housing	Local stakeholders	Hamburg
5	Provide simple 'tips and tricks' that advice newcomers to e.g. don't pay the deposit in cash, to never pay before having visited the house	Local stakeholders	Antwerp
6	Information on ways in which the social services can provide certificates to facilitate the administrative procedure of census registration	Local stakeholders	Madrid
7	Include an interactive map, showing available houses for rent/sale in a filtered area	Migrants/Refugees	Antwerp, Madrid
8	Include information on what documents to provide	Migrants/Refugees	Antwerp
9	Include the possibility to book an interpreter to accompany newcomers when visiting a house	Migrants/Refugees	Antwerp
LABOR			
1	Information on how to obtain the Social Security Number	Migrants/Refugees	Madrid

2	Information on rights and obligations as employees. Sample of a job contract with simple explanation / Accessible summary of rights	Migrants/ Refugees	Madrid
3	Access to information about the public employment offices	Migrants/ Refugees	Madrid
4	Tool matching job offers to user profiles	Migrants/ Refugees	Antwerp
5	Information on vocational training and on the individual competences and how they match with career fields, especially at the beginning of the process	Migrants/ Refugees	Hamburg
6	Information regarding the most demanded employment sectors in the region, in order to guide their own formation	Migrants/ Refugees	Madrid
7	Existence of CV templates and glossaries of terms to be able to develop a CV according to the local labour market	Migrants/ Refugees	Madrid
8	Information on programs and resources available for all citizens to encourage entrepreneurship and self-employment	Local stakeholders	Madrid
9	Information on labour market, who offers counselling, on how to qualify and when to take up preparatory internships	Migrants/ Refugees	Hamburg
10	MICADO could combine job offers with training that is complementary to these jobs	Migrants/ Refugees	Bologna
11	Provide information on voluntary work	Migrants/ Refugees	Antwerp
EDUCATION			
1	Information on the process, the necessary documents, and waiting times for homologation of academic degrees / also on intermediary services if there are any	Migrants/ Refugees	Madrid, Hamburg, Bologna
2	A detailed explanation of the school system - public/private; scholarships, etc.	Migrants/ Refugees	Madrid
3	Information on free professional training and certificates offered by the Public Employment Services	Migrants/ Refugees	Madrid
4	Information on free local language classes / map-based overview on all volunteer organizations offering alternatives to certified classes	Migrants/ Refugees	Antwerp, Hamburg
5	Calendar with deadlines for administrative procedures	Migrants/ Refugees	Madrid
6	Scholarship database giving an overview for funding opportunities for migrants and refugees	Migrants/ Refugees	Hamburg
7	Specific information about education possibilities with unsecure residence permit	Migrants/ Refugees	Hamburg
8	Make out-of-school organizations more known, e.g. organizations that provide homework assistance but also leisure activities such as e.g. football that allow local language practicing outside of a class context	Local stakeholders	Antwerp
PARTICIPATION			
1	Announcement board for users to promote events /Collect requests and offers	Migrants/ Refugees	Madrid, Hamburg
2	Include a tool that enables migrants to reach each other and engage with the local community	Migrants/ Refugees	Antwerp, Hamburg, Bologna
3	Access to announcements of volunteer activities	Migrants/ Refugees	Madrid
4	Information about cultural activities, especially those free of charge	Migrants/ Refugees	Madrid
5	Information on how to find sport clubs/leisure activities and become member of clubs	Migrants/ Refugees	Antwerp

Source: Own elaboration based on working documents from WP2.

In general terms, the ideal digital solution for migrant integration should be **attractive, easy-to-use** and be **the central go-to tool** that provides **up-to-date, comprehensive and clear information in different languages, with visual support**. Migrant participants stress the importance of **accessibility and comprehensible aspects** for the application so that it can support migrants in their daily activities and allow them to interact independently with people of importance in the integration process.

While many ideal feature suggestions can be made, **the digital tool cannot be seen as an all-encompassing solution nor a replacement for the integration services**. Therefore, an ideal digital solution should be embedded in an (ideal) community service for the integration of newcomers. For instance, participants in Antwerp were quite satisfied with integration services. However, the degree to which the newcomers use these services is dependent on their migration history. People migrating for work or studies are not obliged to follow integration courses, thus have less contact with these services. Sometimes they receive useful information through the university or their employer, but they argue that an app providing information could facilitate their search for concrete information. Similarly, in Madrid, participants expressed the importance of knowing about NGOs' services and especially free counselling services about their rights and about where to go to solve specific problems.

2.1.2. Public Authorities and CSOs

Table 17. Demands of the Public Authorities

DEMANDS OF THE PUBLIC AUTHORITIES		Critical
DATA EXTRACTED FROM COUNTRY REPORTS		Important
		Desirable
#	Demand	City
TRANSVERSAL		
1	Develop a digital databank of all organizations, projects or available data regarding integration. An overview of all existing resources, counselling offers, locations and information, and likewise more general networking of all available actors	Hamburg, Antwerp, Bologna
2	Provide a web-based version of the app, as members of public authorities are not provided with smartphones	Hamburg
3	Map the existing resources for migrants/projects by geographical location and by themes (e.g. language courses [education], vocational training [employment], legal counselling [legal]) to identify which are the predominant intervention areas and which areas seem to receive less attention from public authorities	Madrid
4	Data exploitation and visualization (data on global expenditure, users' profiles (gender, nationality, geographical location). Ability to map projects geographically crossing them with data on the migrant population	Madrid
5	Include a feedback system, not only for process evaluation of the app itself but also for a broader evaluation of user experiences, e.g. if a user finds a job vacancy through the MICADO-solution, was he/she able to apply for and get the job in the end? This would generate insight into integration hindrances and successes. / Comments & Complaints section - both for gathering information and for quality control	Antwerp, Hamburg
6	MICADO could keep an overview of tasks and structures in the form of a knowledge repository, to be able to upscale and support a new crisis management system	Hamburg
7	Digitalize existing knowledge, such as handbooks and educational material on regulations and standards within the MICADO-domains, as well as other cultural and social topics	Hamburg
8	Access to information on targeted programs of other levels of government to improve policy planning	Madrid

Source: Own elaboration based on working documents from WP2.

Table 18. Demands of the CSOs

DEMANDS OF THE CSOs		Critical
DATA EXTRACTED FROM COUNTRY REPORTS		Important
		Desirable
#	Demand	City
TRANSVERSAL		
1	Pooling and overview on all existing resources, counselling offers, locations and information, to provide individual assistance to newcomers and, when necessary, refer them to organizations accordingly	Hamburg, Madrid, Antwerp
2	Data sharing: the possibility to share overlapping and relevant information could be useful both for the organizations as well as for the newcomers who won't be required to constantly provide the same information	Hamburg, Madrid, Antwerp
3	Networking and Collaboration: MICADO-tool should facilitate the exchange and the cooperation of different actors.	Hamburg, Antwerp
4	Display of systemic information (some of it needs to be digitalized) about the knowledge and counselling offered by volunteers	Hamburg
5	Knowledge repository and a source to look for regulations and rules	Hamburg
6	Pool all available offers (jobs, education) in order to increase the awareness about them	Hamburg
7	Copy-paste function in the App's content	Hamburg
8	Information on items most searched for or report which information is lacking	Antwerp
9	The app should gather user feedback	Antwerp, Hamburg
10	A video interpreter system for counselling (by e.g. the medical teams and the social management). E.g. SVAD - existing software in Hamburg	Hamburg
11	Access to a database of language mediators	Hamburg
HEALTH		
1	Develop a system that allows for a general overview of what is available in terms of (mental) health care provision, and that is accessible both for newcomers as well as for organizations	Hamburg, Antwerp
2	Telephone service for translation in hospitals and a list of doctors speaking migrant's languages	Hamburg

Source: Own elaboration based on working documents from WP2.

Overall, the information gathered through the workshops and interviews with public authorities and the CSOs is less comprehensive than the one collected from migrants/refugees. Many issues raised by the local CSOs concerned what they thought migrants needed or demanded rather than what the MICADO tool might offer the CSOs themselves. This is one of the gaps in knowledge to be addressed in the future development process.

Nevertheless, the idea of the ideal MICADO-tool for migrants expressed by the interviewees (i.e. local authorities and CSOs) is in line with those expressed in the workshops: they see **an attractive, easy-to-use tool with up-to-date, comprehensive and clear information in different languages, with visual support** as the end result.

Discussing the local CSOs' and authorities' side of the MICADO tool, the interviewees posited **the necessity of sharing data between organizations**. This would facilitate the follow-up of newcomers at the individual level, as well as analysing integration tendencies on a bigger scale. In addition, these analyses would be useful for their own internal purposes or to predict which actions to undertake in the future. CSOs are in favour of simplifying data exchange between organizations as this would facilitate their work but warn about the **difficulty of integrating these data systems** because of data and privacy regulations.

The ideal application is seen as **building a bridge between the information-seeking migrant and information-providing integration service which can facilitate interaction between both as well as facilitate necessary steps to undertake during the integration trajectory of a migrant**. Interviewees advise that **the display of information and offers should always be up to date**. Users will stop using the digital tool if they experience that the information provided is outdated and not applicable anymore. Therefore, **technical intersections need to be considered that allow a regular update of data**.

The information provided should be relevant and not a duplication of information that can be found elsewhere. The websites of public authorities are oftentimes unclear in formatting and structure, text-heavy, and contacts are not easily found. New applications should pay attention to **clear structures and easy-to-find contact points**. In Bologna, stakeholders stressed the fact that the application should be used to improve the knowledge and ability to navigate the complex bureaucratic structure of public administration. The display of offers and information should therefore, as it has been emphasized for instance by several interviewees in Hamburg, not follow the systemic structure of the authorities, thus reinforcing the silo structure of the public domain. Instead, answers/suggestions within the MICADO solution should develop out of the topics and thus display a differentiated and intersectional picture. This way, intersecting and overlapping topics would be found **based on the demand, not based on the source** of information.

2.2. Existing apps and digital tools usage

This section offers an overview of the results of the MICADO co-creation workshops and interviews with regards to **app use, advantages and issues of existing digital solutions in order to inform and facilitate the development of the MICADO tool**. The bases of this document are the country reports (summarizing the results of the workshops and interviews according to a template designed by the partners of the University of Antwerp) provided by the social science MICADO-partners of Antwerp, Bologna, Hamburg and Madrid.

2.2.1. Digital literacy of the incomers

The digital literacy of the workshop participants was very diverse. **In Bologna, limited use of smartphones** was mentioned: the devices were only used to make phone calls – sometimes using the internet-, to send messages, watch videos and check Facebook, and sometimes to check Twitter, or read the newspaper online. No one had ever downloaded an application for integration services. Participants preferred to always talk to someone face-to-face when it comes to e.g. ask for information or making appointments. **In Antwerp, a clear distinction between the two workshop groups was noticed**: those with a higher educational background, who often migrated because of work or studies, generally had high digital literacy and often used digital tools to look for information. On the other hand, asylum-seeking migrants and refugees who reported a lower educational background relied more on informal networks or official organizations to be informed, similar to the participants in Bologna. They would use their smartphone rather for social media such as Facebook. **In Hamburg and Madrid, all**

participants in the second phase workshops were reported to be digitally literate. In Hamburg, participants were between 31 and 38 years old, highly educated and had a good understanding of how to use applications. In Madrid, many of the participants used digital media as a tool to communicate with people in their countries of origin.

It is important to stress that we might need to **reconsider what is defined as digital literacy**, as use of digital tools is often related to the language of the tool: e.g. highly digitally literate persons who only speak Arabic might make extensive use of tools written in Arabic script, but report low digital tool use concerning websites or apps that are only offered in other languages, while those who (also) speak English, French or another European language, might be more prone to use such websites/apps. Another influential factor might be **age**, as in Hamburg, all participants were between 31 and 38 years old and were reported as digitally literate, while in Bologna participants who were between 50 and 60 years old reported not to be used to new technologies.

Local stakeholders in Bologna and Antwerp pointed out that the barriers to access online services persist. A lower threshold should be created using multiple languages, a speech component, but also by helping those without digital skills or access to these tools.

2.2.2. Newcomers' digital tools usage

In the table below, the apps mentioned in the country reports of the MICADO-partners are listed. **This list is by no means comprehensive but merely a compilation.** In Bologna, no information was available as the participants stated to not use apps considering these domains. No digital tools specific for newcomers were mentioned in Hamburg and Madrid, **the apps or websites cited are often in line with those used by the native population.** In Antwerp, this was also the case; the 'Welkom in Antwerpen' -app, specifically designed for newcomers, was only known by a few participants and not actively used because of language issues (the app is only available in Dutch).

	Antwerp	Bologna	Hamburg	Madrid
General	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Google as a start, for every topic • Google Translate • Meetup (app with groups on different topics/activities), groups mentioned: 'Expats in Antwerp' and 'Antwerp Expats' • It's me (digital ID app) • Stad van Antwerpen/ A-profile • Welkom in Antwerpen • Facebook (for events in Antwerp) 	-		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Cercade • Next Door (Both apps share information regarding events)
Education	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • University websites • VDAB 	-	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Tandem • Uдеми • Duolingo • YouTube-channels 	
Employment	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • VDAB • LinkedIn 	-	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • LinkedIn • HoneyPot 	

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Werk.be • Stepstart • Hays • Unique recruitment • Stepstone • Indeed • Monster • Vacature.com • Facebook for advertisement of job days etc 			
Health	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • HZIV-website (health insurance website) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Google Translate 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Google Translate 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • App to manage medical appointments provided by Madrid Public Health System
Housing	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Immoweb • Facebook: cohousing pages, specific groups/communities with informal housing offers, marketplace, ... • Tweedehands.be (online second-hand marketplace which also has an immo-offer) • Immoscoop • Century 21 • VP partners 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Immobiliare .it • Idealista 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • AirBnB • Wg-gesucht.de • Immowelt.de • Immobilienscout24.de 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Idealista • Fotocasa • Milanuncios

Advantages of existing digital tools

In Antwerp, participants mentioned advantages of websites or apps such as **attractiveness**, **provision of clear and up-to-date, information** and with **at least a version in English, but preferably in multiple languages**. Some participants were in favour of websites that were **'active'** and reminded them to fill in their profile or helped their search, such as suggestions made by LinkedIn. Websites or applications that facilitate connecting with likeminded people or people within a similar situation were appreciated, such as Facebook groups or the app Meetup. A website mentioned by participants both in Antwerp and Hamburg and considered very useful is **Google Translate**, which is often used by participants to communicate when there is no common language. In Madrid, participants pointed out that **a filter system** to search for information, especially in apps for housing, is useful. Similar to the Antwerp results, up-to-date information was also highly appreciated. Furthermore, they valued apps supporting their job searches because they are **easy to use** and give **convenient results**, i.e. jobs aimed at traditional sectors where migrants can be employed.

Issues with existing digital tools

For Antwerp participants, a major issue was the **language** used on a website or an application. When users cannot understand the language, the app or website will not be consulted. Participants did not only refer to a lack of different language options, but also to the **wording** used, which might not be adapted to the target group, such as the use of professional jargon. An app is not used or downloaded if it is **not trustworthy**. For instance, a housing-app where users stumbled upon fraud advertisements was replaced by another, more reliable app. In relation to that, participants mention that **insufficient or inadequate information, as well as**

unintelligible or unclear information, are barriers for using an app or a website. Often, this is related to the **fragmented offer of information**, which was also mentioned by participants in Madrid using generic apps for information about neighbourhood events. In relation to this fragmentation, local stakeholders in Antwerp mentioned the oversupply of different websites and systems as an issue.

In Hamburg, participants experienced the **unpredictability of chances** using housing apps as an issue: a lot of effort is asked to visit possible places to live, while the chances of getting negative replies, in the end, remain high. A second issue raised, was related to German language-learning support apps, which are often **not adapted to starters, but already require a certain level of German language skills**.

More specific practical disadvantages mentioned were related to the design of the specific app itself; e.g. no copy-paste function in the app, no English menu, etc.

In sum, participants prefer applications that are comprehensible in language and wording, easy-to-use and that generate adequate outcomes for their situation such as the provision of up-to-date information or accurate housing or job results.

2.2.3. Stakeholders' digital tools usage

Antwerp

Many digital tools were mentioned to be consulted during the interviews and the stakeholders' workshop. However, these were mostly websites, rather than apps. Below is a list of all websites and applications mentioned.

- **Welkom in Antwerpen (App):** *app developed by Atlas, supported by the city of Antwerp, directed at newcomers in Antwerp to easily find organizations according to different themes and basic information such as emergency numbers. Only available in Dutch.*

While not all stakeholders use the app, all of them knew of its existence and evaluated it as a useful app that reaches its goal. Some of the stakeholders use the app during their work with migrants, to guide and inform them about the app itself. Remarkable is that some stakeholders use the app for themselves, to look for other organizations, as a general overview of all actors in Antwerp and their field of work is lacking. Some limitations were mentioned: language – the app is only available in Dutch - no interactive functions (for instance, the possibility to make an appointment with a general practitioner through the app), the lack of a copy-paste function, some icons which are not self-explanatory (e.g. the icon of a scale used for law & justice).

- <https://vakantieaanbod.antwerpen.be/>: *website that collects all information, camps and childcare offers in Antwerp during the holidays.*

The website is mentioned as an example of an overview-website collecting different organizational offers that facilitates parents' search for childcare during school holidays. However, a limitation of the website is that, once an offer is found, the user is still directed to the original website of the organization and its specific subscription-method.

- <http://www.nederlandsoefenen.be/antwerpen/>: a site that lists activities where people can participate to practice their knowledge of Dutch

Stakeholders referred to this website as being very user-friendly and facilitating their work, as before, they always had to search for and list these activities themselves.

- **Ask Antwerp (App)**: a chatbot app, through Facebook Messenger App, directed to visitors of Antwerp, where people can ask different questions which are answered by selected locals. E.g. 'where to eat the best spaghetti in the city?'
- **Gup.zone**: <https://www.gup.zone/> a website to facilitate student jobs by bringing employers in contact with students through a mentor.
- **VDAB digital tools**: VDAB is the agency responsible for employment in Flanders. They have a website with an online profiling part 'Mijn Loopbaan', where users can insert their cv and personalize the offer of vacancies they wish to receive etc.

VDAB was mentioned by the stakeholders as providing already a merely digitalized offer of their services, and the practical application was found to be positive. The agency once developed an app directed to migrants as well, but the implementation of this app was not successful, however reasons for this are not clear.

- <https://www.steffie.nl/>: a site from the Netherlands, where an avatar called "Steffie" explains basic procedures of different themes (e.g. how to visit a general practitioner) through a speech function. Only in Dutch.

The website was mentioned as being very easy and user-friendly, where the user can practice basic things such as registering in the city administration, without giving personal data, because the fictive data of Steffie is used during the exercises. A drawback is the fact that it is only in Dutch.

- Furthermore, an app that is under development in another European project, to facilitate distance learning of integration courses for newcomers was mentioned and considered to be of interest in connection with the MICADO-development.
- Also websites or newsletters which stakeholders use for their own knowledge expansion were mentioned, such as websites from neighbouring countries such as kis.nl from The Netherlands, a knowledge platform on integration and society, directed to policy makers.

Bologna

In the Bolognese context, there are currently **no specific APPs to facilitate the integration of migrants**. The interviews have shown, however, that they have existed and there are still experiments on this subject. In general, three types of experiments have emerged, some of which have failed and one which is still in the process of being defined. One of the cooperatives interviewed had started to create an application due to their need to work with large numbers of migrants in 2014. It was an application that worked mainly on the language since those working in the field of reception are faced with several problems because of the number of languages present. More than 170 mother tongues have been used since the beginning of the "migration emergency" in Italy in 2012. However, the application had the limit of not being able to deal with all this linguistic variety, because it could only be an opportunity for those who

spoke certain languages. Paradoxically, it risked becoming an exclusionary tool, since often the most vulnerable cases were those with rare languages.

The same cooperative has also worked on the digital certification of skills through the "**Compass**" application. There is work in progress on the creation of a digital portfolio of formal and informal skills and the training sector of the Emilia-Romagna Region is also working on it. The certification of skills is a central and fundamental issue for migrants who want to integrate, since for migrants from third countries, the recognition of qualifications is impossible.

Another example of an application designed but never realized is that created by the association "**Avvocati di strada**" of Bologna, which was to be called HI HERE. This application was conceived as an application that traced the journey made by the migrant (at the choice of the migrant), then there was an information part on international protection, then it gave information on the "where to go for", then Italian schools, employment centres, canteens, clinics, listening centres. Unfortunately, the application has never been made for economic reasons.

An interview also referred to another application that the Italian language centres are planning, and which aims to facilitate the learning of the Italian language. The topic, in fact, is not secondary to the issue of integration of migrants, because learning the language is the first step to be able to communicate with Italians and get the necessary information.

Hamburg

Respondents in the interviews said they use online resources for their own information and to offer more specific support during their counselling of refugees and migrants. However, mostly they used **websites** and only two apps were named. This could be either due to a lack of available resources or due to the technical infrastructure of the public sector in Hamburg, as not all public authorities issue smartphones as working tools to their employees.

Officials from the Authority for School and Vocational Education (BSB) mentioned **We.Inform** (Welcome Information for Refugees and Immigrants, we-inform.de) to access fast and more superficial information on a variety of topics. Besides knowledge on education, the platform offers information on legal issues, language acquisition, finances, housing, health and work, as well as offers practical knowledge and a map-based overview of specific offers. The website is available in 8 languages (German, English, Arabic, Dari/Farsi, Kurdish, Tigrinya, Russian, Kurmanji). We.Inform was also known by other interviewees.

Websites mentioned by the Ombudsman's Office were those of the authorities and partners with whom the office collaborates: **BAMF**, **Fördern & Wohnen**, **Dialogforum of BASFI**, and more general resources such as the public transit website **HVV** to research accessibility of services and locations. The office is using an online **video interpreter service** (SAVD) for their counselling. The website offers access to translators of all common languages via a videoconference tool. The user places a request and is guaranteed a response from a translator within 5 minutes. The service costs 35 Euro per call plus an amount per minute.

Resources within the domain housing are the Wilhelmsburg based association **Die Insel hilft** with their **handbook on housing questions** (<http://die-insel-hilft.de/wohnungssuche/>). The information is available in six languages (German, English, Arabic, Farsi, Kurdish and Tigrinya).

For questions related to the labour market and work permits, the **Hamburg Welcome Portal** (<https://welcome.hamburg.de/>) was mentioned as a resource for questions and forms often needed. It is run by public authority and hosted on the city's official website and the layout is in the City of Hamburg's Corporate Identity. It thus has a very particular tonality and layout that might have barriers to some users.

In the domain of health, two apps were mentioned. The **STIKO-app** (https://www.rki.de/DE/Content/Kommissionen/STIKO/App/STIKO-App_node.html) is targeted at medicals offering vaccination. It provides official information on vaccination and a news feed and helps in practice by allowing to insert a person's profile to check for vaccination needs. **ExplainTB** (<https://www.explaintb.org/>) was mentioned as a digital resource with knowledge on tuberculosis that is targeted at medical professionals and service providers to help in their counselling and educational work.

Generally speaking, there is an abundance of services, and oftentimes the path to the required information is confusing. The offers of **Dialogforum** (<https://www.hamburg.de/dialogforen/>) are a good example of how to provide support. These fora are a special Hamburg initiative, bringing together stakeholders from initiatives as well as public authorities to collaborate, and offering online resources that pool information according to several core themes. The **Lagebild** is another important repository displaying relevant information on refugees in the city state of Hamburg (more information in section 7.1).

Madrid

The website of the social services of the Community of Madrid for migrant population (<http://www.comunidad.madrid/servicios/asuntos-sociales/inmigracion>) is well structured by themes but its search engine is not optimized, particularly for technicians. Another downside of the website concerning migrant access is that it is only available in Spanish.

The area in which digitalization has the strongest prevalence is **employment** services. Currently, a nationwide integrated employment system website exists which has a regional branch in Madrid. The website offers a virtual office for job seekers and employers. The platform also serves as a database for technicians working in job counselling. All CVs are accessible, and data can be drawn using oracle and SQL driven platforms following a CRM software-like structure to produce internal reports and reports for funding entities both at the national level and the European one. This experience has led to the simplification of some previously established procedures, like the mandatory use of digital certificates to carry out any kind of online administrative task. Although this application is not specifically conceived for migrants it is still a relevant tool used by job counsellors working with migrants.

With regard to the CARs (Refugee Reception Centres), two main applications are used: SIRIA and i3L.

SIRIA was designed by the Ministry of Home Affairs and it is the main information system on refugee programs, immigrants and asylum seekers available for public authorities and competent accredited bodies in the field of international protection and immigration.

It is a very demanding application in terms of data nourishment, as it requires technicians to perform the following tasks:

- Informing and obtaining the consent of the recipients for the collection of their personal data and its incorporation into the corresponding files.
- Registering and unsubscribing the technicians as users of the App to carry out procedures or queries in support of the asylum seekers.
- Keeping the files and records updated.
- Performing checks of all requests made through the application. Establishing two levels of review, ensuring that the procedures were followed and that all necessary documentation is in place.

i3L was designed by The Ministry of Labour, Migration, and Social Security and it is used as a database registering all the actions carried out with beneficiaries within an itinerary of social and labour inclusion, as well as the financial aid that is managed within the framework of the employment action.

The OAR (Office of Asylum and Refuge) also has access to **SIRIA** but it uses an application called **ASILO** similar to the software Access which is said to be outdated and serves as a repository of all the files and documents provided by asylum seekers when soliciting international protection. This database is only accessible to technicians working in the OAR and must be constantly updated.

3. User personas

ANTWERP

Based on the data and the changing needs and statuses of the migrants (e.g., from recently arrived to job searching, or from undocumented to recognized legal status), we propose that the categorization and profiling of migrants at the beginning of the MICADO tool would work as a hindrance and limit the information people have access to. Migrants could profit from more guidance during the navigation of the MICADO tool and actively be involved to the extent they want to limit the information they receive. During the navigation on the MICADO tool, visitors could then actively click on or select some of the relevant criteria to filter out information. Some relevant topics resulted from the workshops that could work inspiring for the development of the MICADO tool. These were the following:

- **Legal situation**
- **Current occupation** (e.g., work status, student, etc.)
- **Language knowledge and proficiency** (e.g., languages familiar with, knowledge and proficiency of Dutch)

These relevant factors could play a role when reading information or accessing particular themes in the developed MICADO tool. Their relevance may vary for the visitor according to the theme discussed. Important to note is that gender did not necessarily need to be distinguished. Rather, practical criteria seem to be relevant. For instance, if you don't have particular papers yet, you will not be able to enrol in the official system of health care. Thus, this information would then be relevant to provide per theme, if selected by the visitor. If not, a broader package of information could be given and then the visitor would have to read for themselves whether or not this applies to his or her situation. It is then important to keep a large role for the visitor in the decision making of whether or not he or she can get access to all information or not.

Based on particular options visitors of the MICADO tool have to select (if preferred), there could be some kind of 'sorting mechanism' that favours some themes above others depending on their current situation. This could be for instance when someone just arrived in Antwerp, he or she will be very likely to have to search for accommodation first, before searching for dental health care. These sorting mechanisms could be also based on the behaviour of visitors to the site.

MADRID

Avatar/User personas	Description	Legal situation	Digital literacy	Issues/Problematic	
1	<i>"Dubliners"</i>	Migrants or refugees who have been returned by authorities of another country to the first country they entered.	Asylum seeker	Proficient/ Limited knowledge and usage	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Emergency housing • Legal information on asylum for returned migrants or refugees
2	<i>Skilled Refugee</i>	He/she has a high educational and professional level. Mostly from Latin America. Spanish speakers. Many used the services provided by NGO's and they have help to be integrated into the society.	Refugee	Proficient	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Job seeking • Counselling • Degree homologation • Adaptation to local job market • Knowledge about the educational system (especially if with children) • Knowledge about the administrative procedures after the refugee period
3	<i>Unskilled Refugee</i>	He/she has no knowledge of the language, low educational or professional level.	Refugee recognized status	Limited knowledge and usage	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Job seeking • Language courses • Counselling
4	<i>Unskilled migrant</i>	Migrants with low educational levels	Resident permit	Medium knowledge and usage	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Job seeking • Counselling • Housing (renting a room or a flat in the city) • Accurate information about rights • Accurate information on the administrative procedures, especially regarding the residence permit • Formation to develop new skills • Information about Spanish nationality
5	<i>Skilled migrant</i>	Skilled migrants who live or/and study in the city	Resident card or student card	Very proficient	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Job seeking • Counselling • Housing (renting a flat or a room in the city) • Accurate information about rights • Accurate information on the administrative procedures, especially regarding the residence permit • Information on the access to health services • Homologation of the degrees • Information on how to acquire the Spanish nationality • Information about Spanish language courses for non-Latin migrants

HAMBURG

Avatar/User personas	Description	Legal situation	Digital literacy	Issues/Problematic
1 <i>Skilled Refugee</i>	He/she already has recognized the refugee status. Has a knowledge of the language, high educational or professional level.	Refugee	Very proficient	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Job seeking • Housing outside of the public housing facilities • Contact to locals after leaving arrival centres • Language classes beyond B1 • Funding for university degree • Advanced training
2 <i>Unskilled Refugee</i>	He/she already has recognized the refugee status. Has no knowledge of the language, low educational or professional level.	Refugee	Limited knowledge and usage	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Language courses • Job seeking • Vocational training
3 <i>Unskilled migrant</i>	He/she has obtained the toleration status and renewed it over years. Has spent many years in European countries and Germany, has proficient knowledge of German and other European languages. Low educational or professional level.	Toleration	Limited knowledge, possibly illiterate	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Information on Vocational training & orientation • Language courses • Special housing offers/mediators guaranteeing for them • Schooling for grown-ups
5 <i>Freelancers/artists</i>	He/she has a high educational or professional level. Oftentimes works in the creative or cultural industry where freelancing work arrangement are more prevalent.	Refugee	Very proficient	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Health insurance for freelancers • Bails/proof of financial security before landlords • Orientation on creative labour market • Knowledge on volunteer work possibilities (Bundesfreiwilligendienst)
6 <i>Unskilled undocumented</i>	He/she did not pass the application procedure and is residing without residence permit and thus work permit.	Undocumented	(unknown)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Health offers without insurance coverage • Housing outside of regular market • Informal work arrangements
7 <i>Migrant student</i>	He/she has a high educational background and educational motivation. Has high knowledge of the language.	Refugee	Very proficient	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Needs help finding funding for education • Need orientation on job market/volunteer work • Needs assistance on housing market as

					Jobcenter doesn't apply/info on student housing + bail for security deposit <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • higher language classes
8	<i>Migrant parent</i>	He/she has childcare responsibilities that might hinder them visiting doctor's offices or language classes without childcare support. Might want to support children with school success but missing topical/language knowledge might hinder. Difficult communication with teachers.	Refugee/ Toleration	Varying	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • multilingual school events • knowledge on offers outside of school • childcare offers in language classes

BOLOGNA

	Avatar/User personas	Description	Legal situation	Digital literacy	Issues/Problematic
1	<i>Men asylum seekers</i> (sometimes also Dubliners)	He waits for the recognition of the refugee status in a reception centre. Sometimes he has been returned by authorities of another country to Italy as the first country he entered.	Asylum seeker	Limited knowledge and usage	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Job seeking • Language courses • Stay in reception centres (mandatory) • Uncertainty about their future • Legal information on asylum • Psychological traumas • Social isolation and distrust
2	<i>Women asylum seekers</i> (sometimes also Dubliners)	She waits for the recognition of the refugee status in a reception centre. Very limited knowledge of the language, low educational or professional level; illiteracy.	Asylum seeker	Limited knowledge and usage	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Mono-parental • Job seeking • Language courses • Stay in reception centres (mandatory) • Uncertainty about their future and child's one • Legal information on asylum • Psychological traumas • Social isolation and distrust • Highly illiterate
3	<i>Women/Men asylum seekers outside of the reception centres</i>	He/she waits for the recognition of the refugee status outside of the reception	Asylum seeker or	Limited knowledge and usage	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Irregular legal status • Emergency housing • No contract jobs • Hyper-exploitation

	(sometimes “Dubliners”)	system. Better knowledge of the language; low educational or professional level; illiteracy.	Irregular migrant		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • No regular housing • Fear of the institutions • Limited access to public services
4	<i>Long term Migrants with temporary resident permit</i>	Legal migrant status with long term residence permit; good knowledge of the language, and an acceptable educational or professional level. They normally have strong social network.	Migrants with resident permit for work	Limited knowledge and better usage than the asylum seekers	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Housing problem, in particular after family reunification • Difficult to find an apartment to rent • Diplomas and skills not recognized • Subject to a strong discrimination in Italy • Uncertainty about future due to the resident permit procedure • Exploited at work, less pay than the Italian (even if the law declared the contrary) • Access to a limited range of job
5	<i>Migrants with family reunification</i>	Normally women who arrived in Bologna through the family reunification procedure. No knowledge of the language, low educational level, no professional skills.	Migrants with family reunification permit	Limited knowledge and usage	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Social isolation and fear • Highly illiterate • No knowledge of the country of arrival • Work at home
6	<i>Second generation migrants (over 18 years old)</i>	Young men and women arrived in Bologna when they were child or born in Bologna from a migrant family	Until 18 years old, with parent’s resident permit, then with their own permit (to study or to work)	High knowledge and usage. Strong digital literacy	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Subject to migration laws even if they born in Italy or they arrived very young. • risk of being repatriated to a country of origin never seen before • embedded between two cultures, that of origin and that of Italy, forced to act in the name of tradition or repudiated by families

4. User stories

HAMBURG

EDUCATION (Migrant Perspective)	Goal: Funding for higher education	Goal: Finding appropriate language class	Goal: school success	Goal: diploma recognition
Main actors	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Migrant students 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Migrants 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Migrant parents • migrant children • teacher • co-students 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Migrant professionals • ZAA Hamburg (general) • ZAB Bonn (vocational degrees) • Uni Access Berlin (university degrees) • BSB (school degrees)
Goal as perceived by participants	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Find a funding to finance studies 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Finding a class matching the requirements in terms of language level, location, setting (childcare) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • School success of children 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Having my diplomas recognized quickly to be able to enter the labour market
Level of organisation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Individual level • National level 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Individual • municipal • national 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Individual • school • municipal • national 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • municipal
Stakeholders involved	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • BmBF (Federal Ministry of Education and Research) • State funding like DAAD • Stiftungen • UH hilft • HAW • universities 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Jobcenter • employer • volunteer organizations • language schools • BSB 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • BSB • LIS (Landesinstitut zur Lehrerbildung) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Translator • Berufsverbände • IHK • HWK
Actions undertaken	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Researching funding options online • Getting the necessary documents • Applying • (Passing test) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Knowledge about system • being granted formal access • finding appropriate language class (also online search) • being/ succeeding in class 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Enrol child in school • support child with schoolwork • attend parent meetings • learn about educational system 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Organize all necessary documents • have documents translated and pay for that • have documents certified and paid for • get recognition

Preconditions for success	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Meeting the technical requirements (age, no prior degree) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Legal status • new laws since 8/2019 • free/ alternative offers supplementing formal language class system • within recognition process eligible to C1 • children help with language acquisition • in arrival centre more contact to people 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Educating parents about school system and events such as Klassenfahrt, Klassenkasse, Elternabend • assist parents at parent meetings (multilingual) • volunteer offers, activities outside of school • intercultural competence of teaching staff 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • School degrees are easier recognized
Potential hindrances jeopardizing success	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Due to their specific situation migrants/refugees don't meet these requirements • Availability of scholarships more for technical/economical degrees 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Duldung • expensive alternative offers • nontransparent system • nontransparent criteria of PA to grant higher classes • methodology not suitable for different learning types • high distance to available language class • age restriction • no contact to locals = no practice 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Expensive tutoring classes • location of school far away from residential area • discrimination within school class based on cultural diversity • status • school changes due to insecure status 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Process takes very long (up to 3 years) and is very costly, especially university degrees • different levels of school quality depending on country • nontransparent rules for recognition

EDUCATION (PA Perspective)	Goal: Integration into regular education system
Main actors	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • migrants • teachers of additional supporting measures • teachers of regular classes
Goal as perceived by participants	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Fast and sustainable integration into regular system
Level of organisation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • individual, • school • municipal
Stakeholders involved	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • BSB as a provider of supporting measures • migrants' parents • psychologists
Actions undertaken	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • learning groups • international preparation classes • literacy classes • dual program for teens to prepare for vocational training
Preconditions for success	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • equal opportunities

Potential hindrances jeopardizing success	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • traumatized children • a lack of qualified psychologists on trauma • lack of ongoing support in regular schools • overstrained / not trained teachers
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HEALTH (Migrant Perspective)	Goal: getting an appointment	Goal: receiving the required health care service during the doctor's visit	Goal: understanding the German health care system
Main actors	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Migrant patient • Doctor's practices 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Migrant patient 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Migrant patient • Migrant parents
Goal as perceived by participants	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Getting an appointment as quick as possible when in an emergency (like tooth ache) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Receiving the needed health care service • Receiving advice on how to treat a condition 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Knowing what has to be paid oneself, what is paid by insurance • What are the different places to visit (Notfallart, Night Pharmacies, Hausarzt, Specialists, Emergency Room)
Level of organisation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Individual/patient level • Individual/doctor's offices level 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Individual migrant patient • Special institutions on district level 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Individual patient • City institutions
Stakeholders involved	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Doctor's offices • Hospital's emergency rooms • Pharmacies 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Marienkrankenhaus • Poliklinik & Medibüro • Night Pharmacies 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Jobcenter • Marienkrankenhaus • Poliklinik & Medibüro • Consumer Assistance office (Verbraucherzentrale) • Doctors doing primary checkup of arrivers in the accomodations • Triaphon • Mi4Mi • Hanseatic Help • Women Health Team • IPSO E care
Actions undertaken	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Conducting google search • Calling several practices • Asking in the pharmacy • Going to hospital ER instead • OR going to doctor's practice early in the morning and waiting long to slide into an empty slot 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Conducting research online • Asking for advice in (night) pharmacies or migrant health counselling (like Poliklinik and Marienkrankenhaus) • Organizing an appointment (see Goal 1) • Organizing a translator • Paying the translation themselves 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Receiving primary check-up in accommodation (for asylum applicants) • Receiving initial information at Jobcenter (insufficient) • Researching within own networks • Visiting counselling offices, NGOs etc
Preconditions for success	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Having a "Hausarzt" (a regular general practitioner referring to specialists), and knowing about the referral system • Digital literacy for google search 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Having insurance (all but undocumented and freelancers) • Translation DURING the doctor's visit • List of Arabic speaking doctors (not known to many) • Language mediators 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Sensitive doctors understanding the migrant's difficult situation and not re-traumatizing • Language mediators • Having access to available information (like list of Arabic speaking doctors, language mediators and special institutions)
Potential hindrances	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Pain • No time to wait in ER/doctor's practice 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Long distances from residential area to health care location 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Different rules in the 16 countries

jeopardizing success	due to childcare responsibilities • Poor covering of doctors/not enough available appointments in metropolitan areas	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • High extra costs for special medication, for daily expense at hospital, for dentist treatment, for additives like Vitamin D • Language proficiency • Extra costs for translation not paid by insurance • Complicated Specialist's language/medical vocabulary • Doctor's gender • Complicated issues/psychological issues • Long waiting • Quality of doctors 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Changing rules after 15 months of presence in Germany
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HEALTH (PA Perspective)	Goal: Increase Health Care for Refugees		
Main actors	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • District Authority of Altona, Department of Health 		
Goal as perceived by participants	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Ensure health care 		
Level of organisation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Municipal • District 		
Stakeholders involved	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Medical Teams in initial accommodation facilities • Social Management in initial accommodation facilities 		
Actions undertaken	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Establish electronic health card for refugees • Establish medical consulting hours in all initial accommodation facilities • Educating newcomers about the system 		
Preconditions for success	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • provide basic medical care on-site, transfer patients to specialists in regular health care system • having interpreters 		
Potential hindrances jeopardizing success	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • lack of knowledge from migrants about system / lack of understanding from system about migrants • uneven distribution of doctors in Hamburg • lack of language proficiency 		

WORK (Migrant Perspective)	Goal: finding a low-skilled job	Goal: finding a vocational training	Goal: finding a high-skilled job
Main actors	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Individuals • Employer • Jobcenter 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Individual • Vocational School • Employer 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Individuals • Employers • Jobcenter
Goal as perceived by participants	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Finding a job that sustains me financially 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Finding a vocational training that prepares me for a professional career in that field • Being able to finish the training and obtain a degree 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Finding a job that matches my abilities and competences

Level of organisation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Individual 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Individual • Municipal • national 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • individual • municipal • national
Stakeholders involved	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Café Nova • Romani Kafava • Migrant economies 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • IHK • BSB • Employers • Colleagues • Jobcenter 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Verikom • Tor zur Welt
Actions undertaken	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Ask friends and networks • Going into employer's places and ask for job 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • (1) Understanding the system and own abilities; converging abilities and work fields • (2) Receiving formal access/legal working permit • (3) Application procedure • (4) Job preparation through internships, part-time jobs and preparational classes • (5) Vocational training in the company and school 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Look for job online • Receive job offers via agent at Jobcenter • Organizing necessary documents for the application • Applying for job • Receiving invitation for interview • Going to interview • Being offered a job
Preconditions for success	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Migrant economies: less discrimination • People from countries with large Diaspora have it easier since many people speak their language 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • (2) Since "Migrationspaket" (set of new migration laws issued 8/2019) the legal permit is not as important anymore • (3) employers' organizations like IHK are interested/motivated to employ migrants • (4) preparational offers such as internships, part time jobs, preparational classes • (5) special models of 4-year vocational training (instead of 3) can be agreed upon by company and school 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Translators can help get access to internships • Internship, but only when you already know the language • Work experience from home country • Knowing about salaries and tax system as well as working rights and obligations • Bundesfreiwilligendienst and other volunteer works as entry • Knowledge can be transferred from one country's system to the other, only the language is oftentimes in the way, and knowledge of specific standards
Potential hindrances jeopardizing success	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Migrant economies rather employ countrymen • High competition • Negative experiences at Jobcenter • Toleration status (only valid for 3 months, has to be renewed, unclear perspective) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • (2) toleration status. Not many employers know about the new law permitting work • (3) motivation of company to employ migrant • (3) language proficiency: oftentimes B2 is needed • (4) premature picking of training to secure residence permit > high number of dropouts b/c of mismatch • (5) lacking professional vocabulary creates problems, even though employees are good at what they do • (5) discrimination & mobbing on the job through co-workers 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Jobcenter pushes for quick entry in labour market through lower qualified jobs • High language requirements for entering job • Fear of having to speak German • Discrimination, "new guest worker" • exclusion due to hijab • no recognition/appreciation of degrees • recognition process is time and cost-intensive • unnecessary detours (like too early internships) • toleration status • Being creative/freelancer • Different formats and styles of application

WORK (PA Perspective)	Goal: Address qualified migrants	Goal: Integrate Migrants in Labour Market	Goal: recognizing certificates, skills and experiences
Main actors	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Hamburg Welcome Centre 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> W.I.R. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Hamburg Zentrale Anlaufstelle Anerkennung – ZAA
Goal as perceived by participants	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Providing newcomers with information needed Facilitate processes in residence and registration matters 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Facilitate bringing migrants into the labour market on a long-term basis 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Establish equivalence of professions
Level of organisation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Municipal 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Municipal 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Municipal
Stakeholders involved	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Foreign (refugee) students Qualified migrants Companies 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Youth Employment Advisory Service Agency of Employment Jobcenter team.arbeit.hamburg Authority for Labour, Social Affairs, Family and Integration 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Netzwerk – IQ W.I.R. Jobcenter Agency for Employment Youth Employment Advisory Service Companies Support system
Actions undertaken	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Inform newcomers about school system, housing market, language courses Register migrant's place of residence Extending visa Apply for certificate of good conduct 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Offering point of contact for refugees Support and advise employers who are willing to offer internship/vocational training/job to refugees Provide consultation hours for refugees Advise both groups on labour rights 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> new law passed in 2012 (Anerkennungsgesetz) Check if recognition process makes sense (sometimes a vocational training of 3 years makes more sense) Scan existing skills and documents Check the German referencing profession Have documents translated and certified (by migrant) Hand out certificate / need to perform qualification and or compensatory measures
Preconditions for success	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Hamburg is popular as a city to migrate to for specialists (expected to have high living standards) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> combining forces and knowledge of crucial stakeholders in the field 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Passing law to standardize and fasten-up the process ValiKom Project
Potential hindrances jeopardizing success		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> companies can be biased against migrant workers migrants might prefer to work with short contracts on "helper market" than to finish a vocational training and be integrated into the labour market more sustainably because of their precarious financial situation 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Time and cost intensive High level of resilience needed Difficulty to find company that conducts the qualification / compensatory measures with migrant especially for niche professions

HOUSING (Migrant Perspective)	Goal: permission to live outside public housing	Goal: finding a flat	Goal: renting a flat and feeling well in neighbourhood
Main actors	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Individuals • Only refugees • Foreigners Registration Agency • Public welfare housing Fördern & wohnen 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Individual migrant • Social worker • Saga, Hansa and other (social) housing cooperatives • Private landlords • Housing Agency • Jobcenter 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Individual migrant • Landlord
Goal as perceived by participants	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Receiving a permission to move out of public housing 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Living in an affordable flat with sufficient space in a self-chosen location 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Feeling well in the neighbourhood
Level of organisation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Municipal/National 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Individual • Municipal 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Individual • Owner/landlord • Neighbourhood level
Stakeholders involved	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Agency for Housing • Jobcenter (paying for flat) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Café Nova • Immanuel Kirche Veddel • Exilcafé • Fluchtpunkt • Poliklinik • Romani Kafava • Sozialhelfer • Saga • Fördern & wohnen • Brot & Rosen • Arabic brokers • Municipal help/Sozialhilfe • Starthilfe (Berliner Tor) • Counselling services at Baugemeinschaften • NGO Diakonie 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Neighbours • District social management • Social workers • associations
Actions undertaken	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Apply for refugee status, and going to the very long process 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Ask friends and networks • Ask helpers • Research online on real estate pages, Ebay Kleinanzeigen, in Facebook groups and email lists like Linke Liste, Buttclub • Get on the waiting list of social housing (Saga) and housing cooperatives • Send application/call landlords • Receive answer • Go to house visit • Receive rental contract 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Talk to neighbours • Write complaint to landlord • Hide personal items (as shoes and bikes) in the apartment
Preconditions for success	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • refugee status (and relative planning security for 3 years) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Refugee status (3 years residence permit) • Dringlichkeitsschein ("roter Brief") • Dringlichkeitsbescheinigung • Wohnberechtigungsschein • Case of hardship • Jobcenter paying the rent, providing "income" vis-à-vis landlord • Friends and networks • Arabic brokers 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Safe common spaces • Built solutions like Bike racks, safe mailboxes • Neighbourhood community

		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Taking flat in fringe areas or ethnic neighbourhoods • Once you have a flat (e.g. In Saga) it's easier to swap flats • Having all documents: financial security, income (pay slips), other work documents (contract) positive Schufa report • Having a Bail from friends/acquaintances 	
Potential hindrances jeopardizing success	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • toleration status (only valid for 3 months, has to be renewed, unclear perspective) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Landlords prefer tenants with steady jobs and incomes • High competition • Few housing available/tight market • Discrimination • Administrations sending out documents via post instead of direct handing over > problem for people without address 	

HOUSING (PA Perspective)	Goal: Find solution of conflicts related to Housing		
Main actors	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Ombudsman's Office • refugees 		
Goal as perceived by participants	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Improve Housing Situation of Refugee 		
Level of organisation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Municipal 		
Stakeholders involved	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Initial Accommodation Facilities • Fördern & Wohnen as main operator • Social Management of facility • All other relevant municipal stakeholders 		
Actions undertaken	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Reach out to Stakeholders such as f&w • Mediate between stakeholders • Find common agreement • Improve existing structures/implement new processes 		
Preconditions for success	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Having Agreement of all stakeholders • Having formed a network including all important actors • Having neutral mediator 		
Potential hindrances jeopardizing success	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Standards of public accommodation facilities → can't be changed easily 		

PARTICIPATION	Goal: Build Social Networks		
Main actors	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Migrants • NGOs • Neighbours 		
Goal as perceived by participants	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Meeting people from the majority population 		

Level of organisation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • All levels
Stakeholders involved	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • NGOs • Communities • (International) Cafés • Sport clubs • Cultural centres
Actions undertaken	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Go to event • Mingle with locals
Preconditions for success	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Productive events that enable encounter • Donation base • Special fares for migrants/refugees • Contact younger people via social media, elderly differently • Mouth to mouth communication
Potential hindrances jeopardizing success	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • High entry/membership fee • No participants from host community • Not being able to reach the respective communities

MADRID

EDUCATION	Goal: Homologate Degree	Goal: Enrolment procedure	Goal: Improve skills
Main actors	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Skilled Refugees or Migrants • Public Administration: Ministry of Education or Education DG of Community of Madrid. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Migrant parents • Schools • Region of Madrid 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Migrants and refugees • State Employment Services
Goal as perceived by participants	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Provide all documentation in order to get the homologation. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Enrol son/daughter in a primary school 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Improve professional skills by attending (free) courses
Level of organisation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • National level • Regional level 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Regional level • School level 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • National level • Regional level
Stakeholders involved	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Ministry of Education / Ministry of Science • Education DG of Community of Madrid • Migrants or refugees 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Migrant parents and children • Education DG of Community of Madrid 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Employment DG of Community of Madrid • State Employment Services
Actions undertaken	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Requesting information about the necessary documentation and procedures • Submission of the documentation • Search for additional information • Waiting for confirmation (long) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Questions asked to Public Administration • Application for a place in school (needed documentation and deadlines) • Final resolution and notification from school. • Enrolment 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Questions asked to Public Administration. • Procedure and requirements to apply for a free course • Attendance the course • Get the final certification.
Preconditions for success	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Digital literacy • Acquiring accurate information on the procedures • Compilation of all the necessary documents 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Digital literacy • Contact with educational system • Knowledge about the educational system 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Digital literacy • Contact with the Employment DG and State Employment Services • Counselling for choosing the right courses
Potential hindrances jeopardizing success	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Lack of information • Lack of knowledge of the language 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Lack of guidance • Lack of information (especially regarding deadlines for the administrative procedure) • Digital illiteracy • Lack of knowledge of the language 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Lack of information • Digital illiteracy • Lack of knowledge of the language

HEALTH	Goal: Getting the health card	Goal: Getting emergency/ordinary health consultation	Goal: Understanding the regional health system and rights
Main actors	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Municipality • Local Primary Care Centre • Migrants or refugees 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Migrants or refugees • Local Primary Care Centre • Local Hospital • General Practitioner 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Local Primary Care Centre • Migrants or refugees

Goal as perceived by participants	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Getting the documentation to apply for the health card 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● What to do in case of health emergency/ordinary consultation? 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Where can migrants and refugees get information regarding their health rights?
Level of organisation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Municipality Level ● Regional Level 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Municipality Level ● Regional Level 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Municipality Level ● Regional Level
Stakeholders involved	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Migrants and refugees ● Local Primary Care Centres ● Municipality (census) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Migrants and refugees ● Local Primary Care Centres ● Local Hospital ● General Practitioner 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Migrants and refugees ● Local Primary Care Centres ● Local Hospital ● NGO's
Actions undertaken	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Gathering necessary documentation for the census certificate ● Registering in the census ● Submitting all documentation at the Primary Care Centre 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Search of facilities for ordinary consultation / in case of emergency ● Going to emergency clinic at the hospital ● Waiting to be attended ● Redirection to the Primary Care Centre ● Booking an appointment with the General Practitioner ● Getting consultation/treatment 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Consultation about the health rights ● Information regarding the migrant and refugees' rights ● Getting consultation
Preconditions for success	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Proof of residence in the municipality (housing) ● Knowledge about the administrative procedure 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Health card ● Knowledge on the health system ● Language proficiency 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Language proficiency ● Knowledge on the health system
Potential hindrances jeopardizing success	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Lack of proof of residence in the municipality (housing) ● Lack of knowledge of the language ● Lack of information 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Lack of knowledge of the language ● Lack of information 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Lack of information ● Lack of knowledge of the language

WORK	Goal: Getting a job	Goal: Improving the quality of the job	
Main actors	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Migrants/Refugees ● Employers ● Intermediaries 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Migrants/Refugees ● Employers ● Intermediaries 	
Goal as perceived by participants	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Look for a job (personal networks mainly and apps) and get one. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Look for a new job in another area (Personal networks, apps and employers) 	
Level of organisation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Local level ● Regional level 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Local level ● Regional level 	
Stakeholders involved	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Migrants ● Employers 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Migrant ● Employers 	
Actions undertaken	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Accurate CV ● Looking for a job through the personal network or/and using apps ● Signing a contract 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Accurate CV ● Looking for a job through the personal network or/and using apps and formal nets ● Signing a contract 	

Preconditions for success	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Digital literacy ● Proper training ● Strong personal network ● Language proficiency 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Digital literacy ● Proper training ● Strong personal network ● Language proficiency 	
Potential hindrances jeopardizing success	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Digital illiteracy ● Lack of education / professional training ● Lack of knowledge of the language ● Lack of information 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Digital literacy ● Proper training ● Strong personal network ● Language proficiency 	

HOUSING	Goal: Get housing (flat or room)	Goal: Improve the quality of the housing	Goal:
Main actors	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Migrants or refugees ● Landlords (Normally migrants do not use real-estate services) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Migrants or refugees ● Landlords (Normally migrants do not use real-estate services) 	
Goal as perceived by participants	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Get the “best” place to live 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Get the best place to live according to the personal situation migrants and refugees 	
Level of organisation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Local level 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Local level 	
Stakeholders involved	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Migrants or refugees ● Landlords 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Migrants or refugees ● Landlords ● NGO’s services 	
Actions undertaken	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Looking for a housing solution (room or a flat) through the personal network or apps ● Choosing the right housing ● Signing the contract 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Looking for a housing solution according to personal situation. ● Choosing the right housing ● Signing the contract 	
Preconditions for success	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Employment contract ● Digital literacy ● Sufficient funds ● Strong personal network 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Employment contract ● Digital literacy ● Sufficient funds ● Personal network ● Knowledge of the law 	
Potential hindrances jeopardizing success	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Digital illiteracy ● Precarity of employment ● Lack of knowledge of the language ● Lack of information 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Precarity of employment ● Lack of knowledge ● Lack of information 	

PARTICIPATION	Goal: Grow a personal network	Goal: Be involve in the social life	Goal:
Main actors	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Migrants and refugees ● NGOs 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Migrants and refugees ● NGOs (social and cultural life) 	
Goal as perceived by participants	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Get to know peers from my home country 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Meet more natives 	
Level of organisation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Local level 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Local level 	

Stakeholders involved	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● NGOs ● Local cultural centres ● Social networks 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● NGOs ● Local cultural centres ● Social networks 	
Actions undertaken	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Search for peers online ● Search for peers through NGOs ● Participation in local cultural / leisure activities 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Search for enlarging the personal networks with Spanish people. ● Participation in local cultural / leisure activities 	
Preconditions for success	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Digital literacy ● Proactive attitude 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Digital literacy ● Proactive attitude 	
Potential hindrances jeopardizing success	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Social exclusion ● Lack of time ● Lack of information 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Lack of time ● Lack of information ● Lack of resources to participate 	

BOLOGNA

EDUCATION	Goal: Enrolment procedure (for long term migrants)	Goal: Enrolment procedure (for Asylum seekers)	Goal: Find a professional Training (For asylum seekers)	Goal: Find a professional Training (For long term migrants)
Main actors	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Migrant parents • Schools • Bologna municipality 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Asylum seekers parents • Schools • host structure (cooperative) • ASP (manager of services) • Bologna municipality 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Asylum seekers • host structure (cooperative) • ASP (manager of services) • Bologna municipality 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Migrants • Bologna municipality • Emilia Romagna region • Associations / third sector
Goal as perceived by participants	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Enrol son/daughter in 'best' primary school 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Enrol son/daughter in 'best' primary school 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Find training that ensure career opportunities 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Find training that ensure career opportunities
Level of organisation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Municipality level • School level 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Regional Level • Municipality level • School level 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Regional Level • Municipality level 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Municipality Level • Regional Level
Stakeholders involved	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • CD/LEI (public organization to obtain information about schools for migrants) • Migrant parents and children 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Host structure (Cooperatives) • ASP (manager of services) • Asylum seekers parents and their children 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • host structure (cooperatives) • Associations • Private companies for professional training • University of Bologna 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Private companies for professional training • Associations • University of Bologna
Actions undertaken	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Wait for the letter of the public authority (for mandatory level of instruction) • ask to social services • ask to the school • Direct Enrolment • (Also for migrants without regular documents) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Wait for the letter of the public authority (for mandatory level of instruction) • ask to social services • ask to the schools • Direct Enrolment • (Also for migrants without regular documents) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • To define with the host cooperative (SPRAR) the interests of the asylum seeker • To match the interest with the opportunities available • ask to the cooperative's educator to register the asylum seeker for professional training 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Search on internet for professional training opportunities • ask to the community of reference (Example: Senegalese community) • Contact the agencies for temporary works • Search for financial support or pay the training
Preconditions for success	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Digital literacy • Contact with educational system (through other school actors) • Knowledge of other persons in the same situation 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Knowledge of the language • Knowledge of other persons in the same situation • Relations with the social services • Knowledge of the educational system and of the educational laws 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Knowledge of the language • Personal Motivations 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Knowledge of the language • Personal Motivations • real compatibility between training and available job offers

Potential hindrances jeopardizing success	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Lack of guidance • Lack of interest by the parents • Digital Illiteracy • Language proficiency 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Language proficiency • Lack of interest by the parents • Social Isolation/ discriminatory environment • Digital Illiteracy • Lack of guidance by the host structure 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Language proficiency • Social Isolation • Digital Illiteracy • Homogenization of the professional training (to many migrants trained in the same sector) • Lack of guidance by the host structure 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Language proficiency • Social Isolation • Digital Illiteracy • Lack of training opportunities • Lack of traineeship during the professional training courses
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HEALTH	Goal: Obtain a health card (tessera sanitaria)	Goal: Procedure for recognition of total exemption in the health system	Goal: Find a linguistic mediator
Main actors	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Migrants • Bologna Health services (Sportello Unico del Distretto dell'Azienda Usl di Bologna) • Questura of Bologna • Bologna Municipality 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Migrants • Bologna Health services (Sportello Unico del Distretto dell'Azienda Usl di Bologna) • associations for social promotion (ACLI, CAF) • Union (CGIL, CISL, UIL etc.) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Migrants • Bologna Health system • Social services and social workers
Goal as perceived by participants	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • To have a health card as soon as possible 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • access to health services free of charge 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • To have a linguistic translation of their specific language
Level of organisation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Municipality level • National Level (Questura) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Municipality level • Health services level 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Municipality level • Health services level • Social services level
Stakeholders involved	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Associations for migrants' health • Family counselling and space for immigrant women and their children 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • associations for social promotion (ACLI, CAF) • Union (CGIL, CISL, UIL etc.) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Private service of linguistic mediation • Public Relations Office and Relations with Voluntary Associations (Public) • Social workers • Family members (or friends) Italian speakers
Actions undertaken	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Ask to family counselling or health associations for migrants the procedure to follow • Go and ask to the "Sportello Unico" • Ask to an association about the temporary health card (same duration of resident permit and for the irregular migrant only 6 months) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • go to the social promotion associations of Bologna or to the trade unions to produce the certificate of their economic condition (ISEE) • Go to the "Sportello Unico" and ask the total exemption 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Ask for a linguistic translation to the social workers (if they have it one) • ask to the Bologna Health services (Public Relations Office and Relations with Voluntary Associations) when the migrant booked the health service (the translation can be scheduled in advance, on an urgent call, and always

			available in a fixed location) • Going to the health structure with a family member for the translation
Preconditions for success	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Knowledge of the language • Digital Literacy • Have a regular job and a valid residential permit in the city of Bologna (Questura level) • Knowledge of other persons in the same situation • Relations with the social services • Knowledge of the health system and of the educational laws 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • knowledge of the procedure • knowledge of the services that help to implement the practices Knowledge of the language • Digital Literacy • Knowledge of other persons in the same situation 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • correspondence between spoken language or dialect and linguistic mediation • quality of the translation • relationship between migrant and translator
Potential hindrances jeopardizing success	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Language proficiency • Social Isolation • Digital Illiteracy • Lack of knowledge of health system organization in the hosting country • Fear of being reported if irregularly staying on the territory 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Language proficiency • Social Isolation or social problems • Lack of knowledge of health system organization in the hosting country • Lack of guidance 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • low level of linguistic mediation • absence of linguistic mediators for rare languages • Lack of guidance

WORK	Goal: Find a Job	Goal: Improve the language for a better chance of finding a job or do the mandatory Italian language test (B1 level)	Goal: Obtain legal advice in case of problems at work	Goal: Renewing the residence permit for work purposes
Main actors	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Migrants • Public Employment office of Bologna • Temporary job agencies • Migrants' Social networks • Questura of Bologna • Bologna Municipality 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Migrants • Bologna Municipality • Linguistic training centers • Private foundation 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Migrants • Legal services • Questura of Bologna 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Migrants • Questura of Bologna • Bologna Municipality
Goal as perceived by participants	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • To find a good job with a good salary that it is compatible with the migrant's aspirations, skills and competences 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • acquire a level of knowledge of Italian that can facilitate access to more qualified jobs 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • be protected in situations of abuse, discrimination or exploitation by employers 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • obtain the renewal of the residence permit as quickly as possible in order to be able to find work or not to risk losing it.
Level of organisation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Municipality Level • Individual level 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Municipality level • Individual level 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Municipality level • Individual level 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Municipality level • National Level

Stakeholders involved	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Work agencies • Social cooperatives with a “work” area of intervention • Migrants social networks in Bologna • Private companies 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Public linguistic centres • Private schools for foreigners (Ex: The University of Foreigners) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Legal services for migrants • Unions’ legal services • Associations / third sectors specialized in legal services for migrants (or vulnerable persons) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Sometimes Associations / third sectors specialized in legal services for migrants (or vulnerable persons. Ex: Avvocati di strada / International protection legal services - ASP)
Actions undertaken	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Define a plan with the social cooperatives specialized on “work” • registration with the employment office. • registration with the temp work agencies. • Random Distribution of CV • sharing with their own friendly networks • Follow a professional training with a period of internship in the company 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • ask the educator for information about the available courses • Go to community associations to ask where to do them • search the internet for available information 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Ask family members or friends for legal assistance • Request for legal advice from associations specializing in legal support (Example: Street lawyers, Al Sirat) • Requesting assistance from the International Protection Legal Service (ASP) • Requesting legal assistance to the Union legal services 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Go to the Questura office • Go to CUPA service online to get an appointment for the permit’s renewal • contact the free legal services for information and help
Preconditions for success	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Knowledge of the language • Digital Literacy • Strong social relation • successful completion of the internship in a company • reduced labour force pool (example: depopulating contexts) • offering jobs that are compatible with the person’s skills and abilities 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Strong Individual Motivation • Availability of free/cheap courses • Digital Literacy 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Strong Individual Motivation • Legal knowledge of labour laws (and abuses) • Strong social relation that help to find legal support (for free or cheap) • Presence of a legal support • Ability to prove the facts (exploitation, discrimination, abuse, etc.) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Digital Literacy • To have a regular job • Respect the procedure • to live in a housing whose dimensions are not inferior to the minimums of law • not having committed any crime or illegal activity
Potential hindrances jeopardizing success	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Language proficiency • Social Isolation • Digital Illiteracy • be a lone parent without assistance in the management of children • presence of great traumas or physical and mental pathologies 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Social Isolation • Digital Illiteracy • High cost of the courses • Gender segregation legitimate by the tradition of the country of origin • Low individual motivation • presence of great traumas or physical and 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Language proficiency • Social Isolation • lack of knowledge of labour rights • Digital Illiteracy 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Housing dimension • job loss • precarious employment contracts • Lack of knowledge of the procedure • Lack of guidance

		mental pathologies		
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HOUSING	Goal: Search an apartment to rent	Goal: Application for social housing	Goal: procedures for emergency housing
Main actors	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Migrants • Rent app agencies • Online platform 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Migrants • ACER (Social housing institution in Bologna region) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Migrants • Social services • ASP (Housing transition)
Goal as perceived by participants	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Find the best housing solution available 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Get access to the social housing paying a cheap rent 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • find a temporary solution in the shortest possible time that can mitigate the housing emergency
Level of organisation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Municipality level • Digital level 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Metropolitan level • housing institution level 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Metropolitan Level (metropolitan city of Bologna) • Municipality level
Stakeholders involved	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Migrant social network • Local community • Association/third sector 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • ASP • Social workers • Association (Ex: Sunia) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Social workers
Actions undertaken	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Search online platform • Ask to some friends • Ask to the employers • Move to the apartment of a friend/family member 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Go to the ACER office • go to local associations working on the issue of housing to get help • Ask to the social worker • Apply online 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Talk to their social workers to fill in the request form for emergency housing • Ask to the health services (when the current apartment is not compatible with the health condition of the migrant and when the apartment conditions are really dangerous for the life of someone)
Preconditions for success	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Knowledge of the rent system in Bologna • Strong relational network • have good digital skills • alternative housing projects carried out by associations (Example: Vesta Project) • Willingness to live with people in need of care and who in return donate a portion of their rental accommodation at low prices or free of charge 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • have the necessary requirements to enter the list • reside or work in the municipality • have good digital skills • understand the functioning of the online accommodation application • know the different elements that can jeopardize the demand for social housing • have constant support in the practices to be carried out 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • be willing to undertake a family educational path to get out of the emergency housing situation • be willing to work even if you are a woman who has never worked before • be prepared to contribute financially while in emergency accommodation
Potential hindrances jeopardizing success	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • job loss • Digital Illiteracy • Social isolation • Specific gender condition (Mother alone with children) • Racial Discrimination 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Digital Illiteracy • Lack of guidance • Language proficiency 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • presence of serious physical or mental disabilities • poor motivation • the habit of living in emergency situations and precarious living conditions

	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• precarious employment contracts• legal requirements		
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ANTWERP⁵

HEALTH			
As a... [type of user]	I want... [an action]	So that... [a benefit/value]	Pre-conditions
Migrant	1. To have correct, structured and understandable information about the regional/local health system (and legal implications) and in my language	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> I am well informed on how the health system works and use it appropriately. I know how and where to find trustable en competent GPs or specialists. I can follow the necessary steps, and I can best use the offer available. Information on financial aid for first aid, low and medium critical medical situations To know what are the various documents that I need to provide for accessing free services 	In my language In a step-by-step instruction method: E.g.: Legal status? → 2. Subscription Health Insurance → 3. Find a GP that speaks your language →...
Migrant	2. To join a health insurance	I can receive financial healthcare assistance for myself and/or my family	Clear and centralized information on Belgian health system
Migrant	3. to know what are the differences between the different health insurance organisations and terms & conditions / To get information about health insurances	I can make a good choice or chose the one the best past for my needs	
Migrant	4. To have information (in my language) about my rights and the regulations regarding health services depending on my status (refugee, undocumented, etc.)	I can follow the necessary steps, and I can best use the offer available	in my language
Migrant	5. I want access to a fixed GP, that speaks my or a common language/English	<p>I can have a GP who I understand</p> <p>I have a person to help me with healthcare problems.</p> <p>I can explain my health problem/situation clearly</p>	<p>Awareness of Belgian system (for example GP iso. emergency unit)</p> <p>GP that speaks my language</p> <p>GP in my neighbourhood, with</p>

⁵ The format and content of User Stories is slightly different in the case of Antwerp. See p.81 for an explanation.

HEALTH			
As a... <i>[type of user]</i>	I want... <i>[an action]</i>	So that... <i>[a benefit/value]</i>	Pre-conditions
			view on opening hours
Migrant	6. To know what the normal fees are for consultations and health services	I pay the normal/right price	
Public Authority	7. To cooperate with other organisations	We can give tailor-made assistance to newcomers and to support and train staff	
Public Authority	8. To have updated information about the regulations (national, regional, local) regarding health services depending on migrant's status	we can provide correct information and refer clients to the most suitable service	
Public Authority	9. Inform migrants about the possibility for getting translations/interpretation support (buddies, volunteers, professionals) during medical consultations		
Public Authority	10. To know if a client has already a GP, insurances, etc.	We can warn him/her in case something is missing	
Public Authority	11. To have an overview/list of existing support for mental health issues	we can refer clients to those org.	

HOUSING			
As a... <i>[type of user]</i>	I want... <i>[an action]</i>	So that... <i>[a benefit/value]</i>	Pre-conditions
Migrant	1. To get information on my rights and duties as a tenant	I'm aware of these rules to facilitate and maintain a good housing situation	
Migrant	2. to find a suitable home according to my needs and resources	I have a home base to start my life in my new country.	
Migrant	3. to get in touch with the right organisations/people who can provide me with a house	I can meet my housing needs.	
Migrant	4. to receive reliable information about my rights and obligations when looking for housing	I can take the right steps in finding a proper dwelling	
Migrant	5. to know what rights and obligations I have	I have the right expectations & can take appropriate steps.	

	towards the landlord and vice versa		
Migrant	6. to be able to contact the utility companies	I can have the basic/needed services: heat my house, wash myself, etc.	
Migrant	7. to have a central point of contact with regard to my housing needs /	I can quickly get clear information/	
Migrant	8. To have access to clear, up-to-date and accessible information about housing (e.g. social housing requirements, official support organisations, etc)	I find my way how to subscribe myself for social housing, to get support in searching for a house...	
Migrant	9. To get transparent information from landlords what type of tenants they are looking for	I do not loose time applying for an apartment/house I will not get anyway,	
Migrant	10. To get a 'credit score' so I can show my future landlord that I'm a good tenant / to show proof of my (financial and non-financial) reliability,	Increase my chances to find a house so that landlords are more inclined to rent me a place.	As a migrant I don't want to disclose large amounts of information, especially if it's not housing related and feels like an invasion of my privacy.
Migrant	11. To have visibility on rental prices and availability,	so that I can move to a region that has affordable housing.	
Migrant	12. visibility on existing rules to qualify for rental subsidies	so that I can avoid renting a place that is not eligible for subsidies.	
Public Authority	13. To be able to refer migrants to a central information point about housing and provide 'tips & tricks'	Migrants can get correct and trustworthy information about housing	
Public Authority	14. to inform new residents quickly and correctly about rights and obligations with regard to housing	they can take appropriate action during their search for a home.	
Public Authority	15. to encourage & inform my residents about energy saving measures	they can live in an energy-efficient manner.	
Public Authority	16. have an overview of which target group lives where (age, origin, family composition, etc.)	I can communicate in a way that is tailored to the needs of, for example, a neighbourhood.	
Public Authority	17. have an overview of which target group owns or rent a house	They get tailored information about their rights and obligations	
Public Authority	18. have an overview of initiatives, projects, organisations providing help and assistance to migrants with housing issues	So that I can refer clients to or work together with those organisations	
Public Authority	19. to be able to inform migrants correctly about the expectations of public	they can search appropriately.	

	authorities regarding housing		
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EDUCATION			
As a... [type of user]	I want... [an action]	So that... [a benefit/value]	Pre-conditions
Migrant	1. To enrol my child in a primary school	My child can get education	
Migrant	2. Information about and access to homework- or other school-related support for my children	My child can get support that I cannot provide (due to language barriers or schooling level)	
Migrant	3. To be able to have a translator during parent-teacher meetings	I can understand what is being said and how my child is doing at school	
Migrant	4. Information about professional trainings	I can choose and subscribe a training that is within my interests and will help me find a job easier/faster	
Migrant	5. To have clear, structured information about the education system (primary, secondary and higher education)	I, or my children, make the right choices regarding education	
Migrant	6. As a migrant I want to be able learn Dutch by myself,	as it opens a lot of doors regarding housing, healthcare and employment.	
Migrant	7. Easy/clear Information about professional trainings provided by, amongst others, the respective public employment services	I can increase my competences and therefore my chances to find a job	
Migrant	8. To know what kind of studies or training I can follow depending on my status		Offer according to migrants status
Migrant	9. Higher education: to have clear information about legal status and/or residence or nationality conditions	So that I can apply to local (i.e. lower) tuition fees or to qualify for partial or full scholarships	
Migrant	10. To know the criteria on how to access to free or affordable language classes		
Migrant	11. To have an overview of online applications for self-study (for different groups low schooling level, or advanced..)		
Migrant	12. To know what to do in the case of a change of school		
Migrant	13. To know important deadlines about the school/education system, as well as information about happenings that		

EDUCATION			
As a... <i>[type of user]</i>	I want... <i>[an action]</i>	So that... <i>[a benefit/value]</i>	Pre-conditions
	are an important part of school-life.		
Migrant	14. To know what kind of studies or training I can follow depending on my status		
	15. Higher education: to have clear information about legal status and/or residence or nationality conditions	So that I can apply to local (i.e. lower) tuition fees or to qualify for partial or full scholarships	
Migrant	16. (international students/ parents with older children) → Information about courses taught in English	I know which courses (my child) is able to follow	
Public Authority	17. Digital support provided to the migrants in order to learn and practise their Dutch	Migrants can learn and practise Dutch on their own rhythm and initiative	
Public Authority	18. Digital tool for migrants to get them into contact with local volunteers that want to help them with language education	Migrants can find support in practising their language skills	
Public Authority	19. Make out-of-school organisations (on homework support and leisure activities) more known	Migrants and their children can get more support in their schooling and leisure activities	
Public Authority	20. Easy/clear Information about professional trainings provided by, amongst others, the respective public employment services	I can increase my competences and therefore my chances to find a job	

EMPLOYMENT			
As a... <i>[type of user]</i>	I want... <i>[an action]</i>	So that... <i>[a benefit/value]</i>	Pre-conditions
Migrant	1. To have access to clear, up-to-date and centralized information about employment-related matters and supporting organisations	I know if and where I can look for a job and if it is not clear, which organisation can support me	
Migrant	2. To have support in learning Dutch on the job (rather than only following a language course which is then a prerequisite to be able to work)	I can practise Dutch and learn the job-specific language / , so that I can apply to a larger, more appropriate, pool of job vacancies.	

EMPLOYMENT			
As a... <i>[type of user]</i>	I want... <i>[an action]</i>	So that... <i>[a benefit/value]</i>	Pre-conditions
Migrant	3. To know how to start my own business		
Migrant	4. access to the labour market	I have an income to live the life I want.	
Migrant	5. a job that matches my level of education, competences, experience & skills	I feel recognised (financially, mentally & socially).	
Migrant	6. have a central point of contact with regard to my professional needs	I can quickly get clear information and advice	
Migrant	7. to get in touch with the right organisations/people who can provide me with a job	I can proactively contact them for finding a job'	
Migrant	8. Clear information about the requirements and procedure for obtaining a work permit	I can prepare the needed documentation and follow the right steps	
Migrant	9. a clear overview of the procedures for renewing my work permit	I can keep my job without any problems.	
Migrant	10. to know where I can go for a professional training	I can increase my chances for finding a job/ I can find a job.	
Migrant	11. to know what I have to do to qualify for a professional education	I can start it without any problems.	
Migrant	12. a job that offers space to learn the language as well	I can move forward in different areas at the same time.	
Migrant	13. specialised language courses with a focus on professional language use	I can immediately apply my newly acquired knowledge in a professional context.	
Migrant	14. I want to know what rights and obligations I have towards the employer and vice versa	I have the right expectations & can take appropriate steps.	
Migrant	15. To know where I can get advice or feedback about a work contract or conditions proposed by the employer	I know that I am signing a contract that is correct and suitable	
Migrant	16. to fill in my yearly tax form	so that I comply with local tax legislation and optimize my income	
Migrant	17. visibility on the real language expectations of the employer,	so that I can make my search more efficient.	
Public Authority	18. To follow-up clients who got referred for a job	we know if the referral succeeded	
Public Authority	19. to inform new residents quickly and correctly about possibilities, rights and obligations with regard to employment	they can take appropriate action during their search for a job/professional education.	

EMPLOYMENT			
As a... <i>[type of user]</i>	I want... <i>[an action]</i>	So that... <i>[a benefit/value]</i>	Pre-conditions
Public Authority	20. to encourage & inform my residents/clients quickly and correctly to participate professionally	people can function independently within this society.	
Public Authority	21. To have a good and updated overview of bottleneck professions	I can give this information to clients looking for a job or wishing to reorient their career	
Public Authority	22. An overview of other initiatives/projects providing assistance to migrants for finding a job	I can transfer clients or work together	
Public Authority	23. to have an insight into the competencies of my residents/clients	I can make a match between job supply, training supply and the demand for jobs & training.	

TRANSVERSAL			
As a... <i>[type of user]</i>	I want... <i>[an action]</i>	So that... <i>[a benefit/value]</i>	Pre-conditions
Migrant	1. Checklists of needed steps → step by step instructions on what to put in order (when arriving in Belgium; looking for a house, a job, etc.)	so that I can make use of existing support in its broadest sense	
Migrant	2. Access or built-up a (social) network, Have contact with local people	so that they can help me with finding housing, healthcare, employment and education. I can practise my language skills and establish social networks	
Migrant	3. To know what to do in the case of a change (or loss) of house/ school/ GP/ job		Stappenplan
Migrant	4. In case of change of status (e.g. refugee → recognised refugee?), to receive notifications/reminders about documents that that I need to update or about the most urgent actions		Via stappenplan module
Public authority	5. to make organisations more sensitive to issues		

TRANSVERSAL			
As a... <i>[type of user]</i>	I want... <i>[an action]</i>	So that... <i>[a benefit/value]</i>	Pre-conditions
	of diversity and existing power dynamics.		
Public authority	6. To know about discrimination and racism incidents which are often catalysed by language, legal or cultural differences	I can make decisions and work on measures for removing /dismissing such barriers	
Public authority	7. To know when or for what situations the help of an interpreter is a must	I can give the right information to migrants and to help to look for an interpreter	
Public authority	8. To know the availability of interpreters (individuals and/or organisations) for consultations, facilities and the procedures for requesting them	I can facilitate access to services	

5. Frequently Asked Questions (FAQs)

HAMBURG

HEALTH

FAQs	Local/National Answers
Where do I get information on Health counselling?	https://www.fluechtlingsrat-hamburg.de/content/Beratungsstellen_Gesundheit_2018_final.pdf
Where do I get information on the system and different rules in the countries?	https://www.verbraucherzentrale.de/wissen/gesundheit-pflege/aerzte-und-kliniken/medizinische-versorgung-von-asylbewerbern-12312 , oder unterschiedliche Regelungen in den Bundesländern, Infos siehe hier: http://gesundheit-gefuechtete.info/regelung-in-den-bundeslaendern/
Where do I get information on German health care system?	brochure produced by Department of Health on health care system in Germany translated in 9 different languages (https://www.hamburg.de/forum-fluechtlingshilfe/11841536/broschuere-gesundheit-migrant/)
Whom to address in case I have the impression children in my class are traumatized / (psychologically) disabled?	Kinder- und Jugendpsychiatrischer Dienst der BA Altona (https://www.hamburg.de/altona/jugendpsychiatrischer-dienst/)
Whom to address if I am / a family member is disabled and need/s support?	Consultation office for refugees with a disability (connected to Fördern & Wohnen) https://www.foerdernundwohnen.de/begleitung/beratung/beratung-fuer-gefuechtete-mit-behinderung/
I am still living in an accommodation facility. Whom can I contact in case of a medical emergency?	The medical teams in the facilities.

HOUSING

FAQs	Local/National Answers
How and where do I apply for a Dringlichkeitsschein ("roter Brief")?	https://www.hamburg.de/behoerdenfinder/hamburg/11268748/ oder https://www.promietrecht.de/Wohnberechtigung/Wohnberechtigungsschein-mit-Dringlichkeit-bekommen-E2534.htm)
Where do I get information and counselling in housing questions?	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - https://www.hamburg.de/contentblob/7686886/5733cd3f60396b559772c6bc56c185c9/data/faq-df-wohnen-final.pdf - Flüchtlingsrat HH has a list of counselling offers for housing: https://www.fluechtlingsrat-hamburg.de/content/Beratungsstellen_Wohnen_2018_final.pdf
Where do I get help when I want to visit a free apartment?	Hanseatic Help offers support: - https://www.hanseatic-help.org/

I am still living in a secondary accommodation facility. Where can I find help searching for an apartment?	You should visit the social management of your facility.
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EDUCATION

FAQs	Local/National Answers
Why is Bafoeg only paid until 35?	
Where do I get counselling for questions for University access and funding?	https://www.uni-hamburg.de/uhhhilft.html - <u>Participants mentioned that they cannot really help there</u>
Where do I find Advanced Training for professionals? (“Weiterbildung”)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Youth Employment Advisory Service - Agency of Employment - Jobcenter team.arbeit.hamburg - Authority for Labour, Social Affairs, Family and Integration - W.I.R.
Are there free language classes I can attend?	Bücherhallen Hamburg: https://www.buecherhallen.de/international-learning-german.html
Where do I get information on the education system in Germany? (recognition of foreign certificates, how to take a German school leaving certificate, ...)	SIZ (Schulinformationszentrum) https://www.hamburg.de/bsb/siz/

EMPLOYMENT

FAQs	Local/National Answers
Do I have permission to work?	http://www.bamf.de/DE/Infothek/FragenAntworten/ZugangArbeitFluechtlinge/zugang-arbeit-fluechtlinge-node.html
Where do I find information if I want to volunteer?	https://freiwilligennetzwerk-harburg.de/ , Hamburger Freiwilligenagenturen https://www.freiwillig.hamburg/angebot-finden.html , Diakonie Hamburg https://www.diakonie-hamburg.de/freiwillig/freiwillig-engagiert/ , Bücherhallen Hamburg https://www.buecherhallen.de/ehrenamt.html https://hamburgasyl.de/mitmachen/landkarte/
Counselling on topic labour?	https://www.fluechtlingsrat-hamburg.de/content/Beratungsstellen%20Arbeit_2018_final.pdf
Counselling on topic labour for people with toleration status?	https://www.hamburg.de/contentblob/6770728/4b70c448dd2e7a1c5c045becb46380d7/data/df-arbeit-faq.pdf W.I.R.: https://www.hamburg.de/wir/
Where do I find help with legal issues?	Hanseatic Help offers counselling with a lawyer every Thursday
How do I best get an “Ausbildungsplatz”?	Best way to get an <i>Ausbildungsplatz</i> (recommended by NGOs): <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Internship 2. part-time job 3. Vorbereitungsklassen 4. Ausbildungsplatz

Who helps me if I want to get my professional qualification recognized?	<p>ZAA/Zentrale Anlaufstelle Anerkennung</p> <p>Großer Burstah 25 20457 Hamburg 040/ 30 62 03 96</p> <p>www.diakonie-hamburg.de/web/visitenkarte/zaa/</p> <p>zaa@diakonie-hamburg.de</p> <p>Beratung zur Anerkennung von Schul-und Berufsabschlüssen aus den Herkunftsländern von MigrantInnen</p>
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PARTICIPATION

FAQs	Local/National Answers
How to build solid and effective networks?	Go into active and productive spaces of encounter. Local actors in Hamburg are, among many others, Bergedorfer für Völkerverständigung e. V., Embassy of Hope, New Hamburg and Café Nova, GWA St Pauli, Hackerschool, Die Insel hilft e.V., Landungsbrücken - Patenschaften in Hamburg stärken, leetHub St.Pauli e.V., Schaltzentrale
How do I get to know Germans?	Online resources are Couchsurfing and New in Hamburg (Facebook Group), but there are also volunteer groups and associations organizing mentoring. Those are, among others: Hamburg volunteer agency (Hamburger Freiwilligenagenturen), Die Insel hilft e.V., Hamburger mit Herz e.V., Human Hamburg, INCI e.V., KAROLA – Internationaler Treffpunkt für Frauen und Mädchen (insb. Roma), LÄLE Interkulturelle Begegnungsstätte e.V. in St. Pauli, Menschen stärken Menschen Patenschaften in der Hansestadt, c/o PARITÄTISCHES Kompetenzzentrum Migration, Migrantenhilfe Hamburg e.V., Welcome Dinner e.V.
How to reach migrants best?	Flüchtlingsmagazin, New in Hamburg (Facebook Group)
Is there a community meet-up where migrants can help each other?	New Hamburg/Café Nova offers community meetups. <i>There must be many but we have not systematically researched these yet.</i>

MADRID**HEALTH**

FAQs	Local/National Answers
What are the formal requirements for obtaining the health card?	<p>Being registered in the census and having a valid identification. If the immigrant is not in a regular situation, it is necessary to ask for the DAR (Foreigner not insured) or the TIR (Passer-by without resident permit).</p> <p>https://www.madrid.es/portales/munimadrid/es/Inicio/Servicios-sociales-y-salud/Salud/Direcciones-y-telefonos/Servicio-Madrid-libre-de-exclusion-sanitaria?vgnextfmt=default&vgnextoid=82d3a62607872510VgnVCM2000000c205a0aRCRD&vgnnextchannel=cee88fb9458fe410VgnVCM1000000b205a0aRCRD</p>
Can I have the health card without a job contract?	<p>Yes, having a job contract is not necessary. The only requirements are: to be registered in the census and to have a Social Insurance Number.</p> <p>https://gestionesytramites.madrid.org/cs/Satellite?c=CM_ConvocaPrestac_FA&cid=1142635685817&noMostrarML=true&pageid=1142687560411&pagename=ServiciosAE/CM_ConvocaPrestac_FA/PSAE_fichaConvocaPrestac</p>
How to obtain the health card? Do I need to make an appointment? Where? How? What documents should I provide?	<p>You can do it in person at your local Health Centre. You can search for it here: http://www.comunidad.madrid/servicios/salud/buscador-centros-sanitarios</p> <p>More information on the documents you will need to provide and on the procedure: http://www.comunidad.madrid/servicios/salud/tarjeta-sanitaria</p> <p>You can also do it online or in person at any of the Offices of the Registry Assistance (List: http://www.madrid.org/cs/Satellite?cid=1331802501745&pagename=PortalCiudadano/Page/PCIU_contenidoAgrupadoBuscador).</p> <p>You will need to fill the following document: https://gestionesytramites.madrid.org/cs/Satellite?c=CM_ConvocaPrestac_FA&cid=1142635685817&language=es&nombreVb=impresos&op=PSAE_&pagename=CMFramework%2FComunes%2FLogica%2FICM_WrapperGetion&tipoGestion=GFORM</p> <p>Then submit it with other documents required (census registry document and Social Insurance Number). No appointment needed although each office has its own opening hours.</p>
Where should I apply for the National Insurance Number?	<p>To do so you need to go to your nearest General Social Security Treasury Office.</p> <p>List of the Madrid Offices: http://www1.seg-social.es/ActivaInternet/groups/public/documents/rev_anexo/rev_035062.pdf</p> <p>The documents needed are:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> -An official document of identification. -Model TA1 filled. <p>Model TA1: http://www.seg-social.es/wps/portal/wss/internet/Trabajadores/Afiliacion/10817/31190/572</p>
How long does the administrative process of obtaining the National Insurance Number take? And the health card?	<p>Usually it is given immediately. But it could take up to 45 days. http://www.seg-social.es/wps/portal/wss/internet/InformacionUtil/44539/44084</p> <p>The Health card will be sent to the same Health Centre where you requested it in about 3-4 weeks.</p> <p>https://gestionesytramites.madrid.org/cs/Satellite?c=CM_ConvocaPrestac_FA&cid=1142635685817&noMostrarML=true&pageid=1142687560411&pagename=ServiciosAE/CM_ConvocaPrestac_FA/PSAE_fichaConvocaPrestac</p>

What services do I have access to with the health card?	You will have access to all public health benefits in Madrid. http://www.comunidad.madrid/servicios/salud/tarjeta-sanitaria
What health services do I have access if I don't have a health card yet?	You will still have access to the following benefits: -Assignment of medicine and nursing consultation -Referral to consultation with a specialist -Recipes To be able to access health care without the card you will need: -to be registered in the census. -an official identification document https://www.madrid.es/portales/munimadrid/es/Inicio/Servicios-sociales-y-salud/Salud/Direcciones-y-telefonos/Servicio-Madrid-libre-de-exclusion-sanitaria?vgnextfmt=default&vgnextoid=82d3a62607872510VgnVCM2000000c205a0aRCRD&vgnnextchannel=cee88fb9458fe410VgnVCM1000000b205a0aRCRD

HOUSING

FAQs	Local/National Answers
Where can I find a model of rental contract?	http://www.madrid.org/cs/Satellite?blobcol=urldata&blobheader=application%2Fpdf&blobkey=id&blobtable=MungoBlobs&blobwhere=1202749322629&ssbinary=true
What is a deposit?	It is a certain amount of money (usually one month of rental payment) you have to hand to the landlord. It serves as a guarantee and once the contract is finished the money should be returned. http://www.comunidad.madrid/servicios/vivienda/fianzas-arrendamiento
What number of monthly payments should I contribute in a deposit?	Usually it is one month of rental payment. http://www.comunidad.madrid/servicios/vivienda/fianzas-arrendamiento
What are the most common requirements to rent a home?	You will need an official document of identification (in Spain for foreigners it is the NIE [Número de Indentidad de Extranjero]). Also, you will be asked to prove your economic solvency (usually in form of an employment contract). Additionally, you will need to pay the deposit. http://www.madrid.org/cs/Satellite?c=FRAME_Contentido_FA&childpagename=PortalConsumidor%2FFrame_Contentido_FA%2FFPTCS_contenidoReportajes&cid=1354675156195&p=1343064181510&pagename=PTCS_wrapper http://www.comunidad.madrid/servicios/vivienda/proceso-alquiler-vivienda
What are the most common requirements to rent a room?	There are several forms of renting a room. The most official way is to sign a renting contract with the landlord with similar requirements to renting a house. In reality, many rooms are offered for renting by the tenants with a simple verbal agreement.
Where can I get information about my rights as a tenant for free?	Here you can find more information about tenant rights. http://www.comunidad.madrid/servicios/consumo/alquilar-vivienda-derechos-garantias The Community of Madrid offers counselling and intermediation services with „Plan Alquila“ http://www.comunidad.madrid/servicios/vivienda/plan-alquila
How can I identify abusive clauses?	At the following links you can find more information about identifying abusive clauses. http://www.madrid.org/cs/Satellite?c=Page&childpagename=PortalConsumidor%2FFPage%2FFPTCS_contenido&cid=1343064074075&pagename=PTCS_wrapper http://www.comunidad.madrid/servicios/consumo/clausulas-abusivas-lo-no-debe-firmar

Where should I go in case of problems with the landlord?	You can make a claim to the renting appeals board: http://www.madrid.org/cs/Satellite?c=FRAME_Contentido_FA&childpagename=PortalConsumidor%2FFrame_Contentido_FA%2FPTCS_contenidoGenerico&cid=1343066039973&p=1343064071745&pagename=PTCS_wrapper
Should they give me a monthly rent receipt?	Yes. http://www.madrid.org/cs/Satellite?c=FRAME_Contentido_FA&childpagename=PortalConsumidor%2FFrame_Contentido_FA%2FPTCS_contenidoFaq&cid=1343065715219&p=1343064074075&pagename=PTCS_wrapperCR

EDUCATION

FAQs	Local/National Answers
How does the Spanish education system work?	<p>Education in Spain is obligatory for all those between 3 and 16 years old. Public schools are free, but you can also chose paid private schools (some of them are partially subsidised from state budget). You can then voluntarily choose either vocational studies (FP) or continue with high school studies (Bachillerato), after which you can enter University education or graduate vocational studies.</p> <p>http://www.educacionyfp.gob.es/contenidos/estudiantes/portada.html</p> <p>Here you can find an organization chart on how the Spanish education system works:</p> <p>http://www.educacionyfp.gob.es/bulgaria/dam/jcr:2a124588-bad9-45d9-8ee2-073bf31408e2/sistema-educativo-lomce-pdf.pdf</p>
When should I apply for a place in school for my children? What are the key deadlines?	<p>In Madrid the deadlines are: 24 April - 10 May. This applies to all the stages of free public education.</p> <p>http://www.comunidad.madrid/servicios/educacion/solicita-tu-admision-educacion-infantil-obligatoria-bachillerato</p>
Where should I complete the procedure for requesting a school place?	<p>You can complete it by submitting it online or in person at the centre you have chosen as your first preferred option.</p> <p>http://www.comunidad.madrid/servicios/educacion/solicita-tu-admision-educacion-infantil-obligatoria-bachillerato</p> <p>There are various school support offices, where you can ask for more information:</p> <p>http://www.comunidad.madrid/servicios/educacion/solicita-tu-admision-educacion-infantil-obligatoria-bachillerato</p>
Can I apply for a scholarship? How should I do it?	<p>In Madrid you can request a series of scholarships that goes from nursery scholarships to school canteen or support for buying text books.</p> <p>You can search for scholarship offers here:</p> <p>http://www.comunidad.madrid/servicios/educacion/becas-ayudas-premios-actividades-culturales-artisticas</p>
What are the formal requirements for a scholarship?	<p>Each programme has its own requirements. You can consult them here:</p> <p>http://www.comunidad.madrid/servicios/educacion/becas-ayudas-premios-actividades-culturales-artisticas</p>
How can I homologate my academic degree? Where should I do it? What documents do I need? How long does it take?	<p>For non-University degrees, you can either do it online or in person at the offices of Ministry of Education in Madrid, at the Government Delegations in other cities or in one of the Registry Offices in Madrid. Here is the link to all the information you need:</p> <p>http://www.educacionyfp.gob.es/servicios-al-ciudadano/catalogo/gestion-titulos/estudios-no-universitarios/titulos-extranjeros/homologacion-convalidacion-no-universitarios.html</p> <p>The documents needed depend on the degree to homologate but there are some documents needed for every request. You can check them at the following link:</p> <p>http://www.educacionyfp.gob.es/servicios-al-ciudadano/catalogo/gestion-titulos/estudios-no-universitarios/titulos-extranjeros/homologacion-convalidacion-no-universitarios.html</p> <p>It could take up to 3 months to resolve the homologation.</p>

	<p>Here you can find all the information related to homologation of University degrees:</p> <p>http://www.ciencia.gob.es/portal/site/MICINN/menuitem.26172fcf4eb029fa6ec7da6901432ea0/?vgnextoid=47e9656691165610VgnVCM1000001d04140aRCRD</p> <p>This kind of homologation could take longer.</p>
Where can I take free courses to improve my CV?	<p>Here is a list of free courses given by the Employment Agency of the City of Madrid that will help you to improve your CV.</p> <p>https://www.madrid.es/portales/munimadrid/es/Inicio/Educacion-y-empleo/Empleo/Agencia-para-el-Empleo-de-Madrid/?vgnextfmt=default&vgnextoid=c65815fa10294110VgnVCM1000000b205a0aRCRD&vgnextchannel=3f50c5dee78fe410VgnVCM1000000b205a0aRCRD&idCapitulo=10860120</p>

EMPLOYMENT

FAQs	Local/National Answers
Where can I find a model of Spanish CV?	<p>At the Public Service of State Employment web, you can find all the information on CV needed:</p> <p>https://www.sepe.es/HomeSepe/Personas/encontrar-trabajo/ayudamos-buscar-empleo/elaboracion-tipos-curriculum.html</p>
What are the formal requirements to work based on my legal situation?	<p>The requirements for work permit will depend on your legal status, the employment type and duration of your stay in Spain:</p> <p>http://extranjeros.mitramiss.gob.es/es/informacioninteres/informacionprocedimientos/Ciudadanosnocomunitarios/residirtrabajar.html</p> <p>http://extranjeros.mitramiss.gob.es/es/InformacionInteres/FolletosInformativos/arc_hivos/triptico_trabajadores_extranjeros.pdf</p>
Can I work with a EU resident / student / refugee status card?	<p>Here are some links with useful information on the Spanish Immigration Portal.</p> <p>Yes, you can work with a EU resident card:</p> <p>http://extranjeros.mitramiss.gob.es/es/InformacionInteres/InformacionProcedimientos/CiudadanosComunitarios/hoja103/index.html</p> <p>There are certain limitations to work permits while studying in Spain. Check the requirements here:</p> <p>http://extranjeros.mitramiss.gob.es/es/InformacionInteres/InformacionProcedimientos/Ciudadanosnocomunitarios/hoja003/index.html#requicajena</p> <p>Yes, you are allowed to work with a refugee status card:</p> <p>http://extranjeros.mitramiss.gob.es/es/InformacionInteres/InformacionProcedimientos/Ciudadanosnocomunitarios/hoja038/index.html</p>
How can I renew my resident card? Do I need to make an appointment? Where? How?	<p>It depends on what card you want to renew.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - For temporary residence card: <p>http://extranjeros.mitramiss.gob.es/es/InformacionInteres/InformacionProcedimientos/Ciudadanosnocomunitarios/hoja018/index.html</p> <p>It is recommended to request the renewal at least 60 days before the expiration date of the card.</p> <p>Here are the addresses, contact and opening hours of the offices to request it. Appointment will be needed depending on the office:</p> <p>http://www.seap.minhap.gob.es/web/servicios/extranjeria/extranjeria_ddgg.html</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Check here for information on the long term residence card: <p>https://sede.policia.gob.es/portalCiudadano/extranjeria/pr_tar_res_larga.html</p> <p>http://extranjeros.mitramiss.gob.es/es/InformacionInteres/InformacionProcedimientos/Ciudadanosnocomunitarios/hoja046/index.html</p>

	<p>You can hand in the documents either at a Police station or at the Government's Delegation in Madrid.</p> <p>https://www.mptfp.gob.es/portal/delegaciones_gobierno/delegaciones/madrid/extranjeria.html</p> <p>For more information about the type of card renewal check this link from the Immigration Portal:</p> <p>http://extranjeros.mtramiss.gob.es/es/InformacionInteres/InformacionProcedimientos/Ciudadanosnocomunitarios/renovaaautorizaciones.html</p>
What are the formal requirements?	<p>At the following links you can find all the information:</p> <p>http://extranjeros.mtramiss.gob.es/es/InformacionInteres/InformacionProcedimientos/Ciudadanosnocomunitarios/hoja018/index.html</p> <p>https://sede.policia.gob.es/portalCiudadano/extranjeria/pr_tar_res_larga.html</p>
Where can I renew my residence card? What documents should I provide? How long does the administrative process take?	<p>You will need to renew the long term residence card after each 5 years in the Government's Delegation offices.</p> <p>http://extranjeros.mtramiss.gob.es/es/InformacionInteres/InformacionProcedimientos/Ciudadanosnocomunitarios/hoja046/index.html</p> <p>For temporary residence after each 2 years:</p> <p>http://extranjeros.mtramiss.gob.es/es/InformacionInteres/InformacionProcedimientos/Ciudadanosnocomunitarios/hoja018/index.html</p> <p>It is recommended to request the renewal at least 60 days before the expiration date of the card in both cases.</p>
What are my rights in case of vacation or sick leave?	<p>Here is a Labour Guide with all the necessary information:</p> <p>http://www.mtramiss.gob.es/es/Guia/texto/index.htm</p> <p>As a foreign worker in Spain you will be subject to the same laws as national workers. In this sense, all the employees are entitled to 30 days of vacation per year worked. In case of sickness, temporary absence will be possible as long as the doctor confirms it.</p> <p>More information can be found in the Workers' Statute:</p> <p>https://www.boe.es/buscar/act.php?id=BOE-A-2015-11430</p>
Where should I go in case of problems with my employer?	<p>Here is some useful information on how to proceed in case of problems from the Ministry of Labor and Immigration :</p> <p>http://www.mtramiss.gob.es/itss/web/Utilidades/FAQs/RL/rl.html</p> <p>http://www.mtramiss.gob.es/itss/web/Utilidades/FAQs/IYP/iyp.html</p> <p>http://www.mtramiss.gob.es/es/Guia/texto/guia_12/contenidos/guia_12_25_4.htm</p> <p>You can also contact with trade unions in Spain:</p> <p>http://www.madrid.ccoo.es/cms.php?cd cms_pag=12994</p> <p>http://www.ugt.es/ugt-edita-materiales-de-apoyo-la-insercion-sociolaboral-de-trabajadores-y-trabajadoras-extranjeros</p> <p>Additionally, you can find advice here:</p> <p>https://www.madrid.es/UnidadesDescentralizadas/Inmigracion/ContenidosBasicos/Tramites/AsesoriaJuridica/Diptico%20Laboral.pdf</p>
Where can I get free legal advice in case of problems at my job?	<p>Madrid City Town Hall offers help in integration of immigrants and some of its offices provide free legal advice:</p> <p>https://www.madrid.es/portales/munimadrid/es/Inicio/Inmigrantes/Servicio-Municipal-de-Orientacion-Juridica-en-materia-de-Extranjeria-y-para-supuestos-de-Racismo-Xenofobia-Homofobia-y-Transfobia-/?vgnextfmt=default&vgnextoid=1968a34376ec8210VgnVCM1000000b205a0aRCRD&vgnnextchannel=de40b7dd3f7fe410VgnVCM1000000b205a0aRCRD</p> <p>https://www.madrid.es/portales/munimadrid/es/Inicio/Inmigrantes/Oficina-Municipal-de-Informacion-y-Orientacion-para-la-Integracion-de-Poblacion-Inmigrante-Calle-Juan-</p>

BOLOGNA**HEALTH**

FAQs	Local/National Answers
What happens if my health card expires?	<p>If your health card expires, you can still use it as a certification of your social security number (<i>ndr.</i> Codice fiscale) and for buying medicine in pharmacy. If you have a residence permit (<i>ndr.</i> permesso di soggiorno), your health card expires with it.</p> <p>https://sistemats1.sanita.finanze.it/portale/tessera-sanitaria/faq-sulla-tessera-sanitaria</p> <p>https://www.money.it/rinnovo-tessera-sanitaria-scaduta</p>
How can I renew their health card?	<p>If your health card expires, you will receive at your home a new one. All the information about the renewal your health card can be found in the following link</p> <p>https://www.ausl.bologna.it/iap_dati/view_prest_site?id_site=14814&id_prest=52672</p> <p>https://www.money.it/rinnovo-tessera-sanitaria-scaduta</p>
What is the use of having a general doctor if I can go to the emergency room?	<p>The general doctor's main role is to provide medical prescription for illnesses and diseases. Anyway, further information about the benefits and the usefulness of having a general doctor can be found at the following link</p> <p>https://www.sanitainformazione.it/pazienti/medico-base-un-ruolo-chiave/</p> <p>Emergency room could be used only for serious and sudden health problems.</p>
What are the vaccines for and what happens if I don't do them?	<p>„Vaccines are products that protect people against serious and potentially deadly diseases. Unlike most medicines that treat or cure diseases, vaccines prevent them“.</p> <p>For children and teenagers, some vaccines are compulsory to attend school. In the following links you can find useful information about vaccines in Bologna:</p> <p>https://www.ausl.bologna.it/iap_dati/view_prest?id=50942</p> <p>https://ambo.ausl.bologna.it/temi/vaccini/i-vaccini-bambini-e-adolescenti/risorse</p>

HOUSING

FAQs	Local/National Answers
What are the most important tips and steps to find a home in Bologna?	<p>If you are both a foreign student or a private citizen you can find some tips, useful information, and websites links in the field of housing here</p> <p>http://flashgiovani.it/cercare-casa.</p>
What should I know about the type of house if I ask for family reunification?	<p>At the following link you can find all the information you need about family reunification, including housing issues</p> <p>http://www.prefettura.it/bologna/contenuti/Ricongiungimento_familiare-6402904.htm</p>
What do I have to do to have a social house?	<p>You can find information and contacts about bureaucratic procedures for social houses and ASP Città di Bologna's housing transition service at the following links:</p> <p>http://www.acerbologna.it/site/home/documento8494.html</p> <p>http://www.aspbologna.it/servizio-transizione-abitativa/guida-agli-uffici/servizio-transazione-abitativa</p> <p>http://informa.comune.bologna.it/iperbole/salute/pagine_indice/12:3371/</p>
What I can do if I have lost my house?	<p>ASP Città di Bologna provides a service called „prompt hospitality“. You can find information about it at the following link:</p>

	http://www.aspbologna.it/servizio-transizione-abitativa/guida-agli-uffici/servizio-transazione-abitativa
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EDUCATION

FAQs	Local/National Answers
What would be the migration path to ensure better integration of our children in Bologna?	At the following link you can find an exhaustive list of local Organizations and Associations of migrants in Bologna. They organize activities and initiatives for both foreign adults and children. Beside the organizations' names you can find also their contacts and a short description of their activities and scopes. https://www.cittametropolitana.bo.it/sanitasociale/Engine/RAServeFile.php/f/immigrazione/ElencoAssociazioni.pdf
How can I obtain recognition of my qualifications and skills in Bologna?	Useful information about the bureaucratic procedure for the recognition of both professional and educational qualifications can be found at the following links: https://www.mise.gov.it/index.php/it/mercato-e-consumatori/titoli-professionali-esteri/documentazione-per-il-riconoscimento http://bo.istruzioneer.gov.it/wp-content/uploads/sites/3/2018/07/Equipollenza-Vademecum-per-gli-utenti.pdf

EMPLOYMENT

FAQs	Local/National Answers
What are my rights and duties in the workplace? Are they the same as for Italians?	Yes, rights and duties in the workplace are the same for both Italian and foreigner worker in possession of a regular residence permit. At the following link you can find further information about it. http://www.integrazionemigranti.gov.it/normativa/procedureitalia/Pagine/Lavoroold.aspx https://www.inps.it/nuovoportaleinps/default.aspx?itemdir=45831
What can I do if someone exploited me and/or does not pay me if I worked?	If you think you need legal assistance for exploitation or for not being paid at work, you can refer to the organizations and associations at the following links: http://informa.comune.bologna.it/iperbole/sportellosociale/servizi/4352/2686/ https://www.cgilbo.it/le-nostre-strutture-servizio/centro-lavoratori-stranieri/ http://www.cislmetropolitana.bo.it/associazioni/anolf.html
How can I find work more easily?	At the following link you can find a video showing some useful tips and advices to find a job. http://www.bolognatoday.it/cronaca/CERCARE-LAVORO-STRANIERI-RICHIEDENTI-ASILO.html Clearly, a good and well-written curriculum vitae, a sufficient knowledge of Italian language and pro-activity are the most important requirements.
Who can help me to find a job and a profession training?	You can take contact with ASP Città di Bologna or other organizations specialized in assisting incoming foreigner workers in the field of professional training and job searching. In the following link you can find a short description of the activities carried on by these organizations and all their contacts details. http://informa.comune.bologna.it/iperbole/sportellosociale/servizi/2072/51374/ http://informa.comune.bologna.it/iperbole/sportellosociale/servizi/2072/2686/

OTHER

FAQs	Local/National Answers
How can I renew their residence permit?	All the information you need about the request and renewal of your residence permit can be found in the website of Questura di Bologna.

	https://questure.poliziadistato.it/it/Bologna/articolo/5730dcf70812b112400403
What happens and what risks do I face if you stay in Bologna without a valid residence permit?	<p>If you do not have a personal residence permit or if you do not renew it, you are considered an irregular migrant. You could be charged with illegal/ clandestine immigration. In this case, a fine from 5.000 to 10.000€ and expulsion from Italian territories are foreseen, with respect for your fundamental rights.</p> <p>At this link you can find a lot of detailed information about the consequences of not having a valid residence permit in Italy.</p> <p>https://www.meltingpot.org/Note-sintetiche-sulla-situazione-del-cittadino-straniero.html</p>
What do I have to do to obtain citizenship?	<p>All the information you need to obtain citizenship can be found at the following link: https://www.inps.it/nuovoportaleinps/default.aspx?itemdir=51985</p> <p>http://www.prefettura.it/bologna/contenuti/Cittadinanza-15090.htm</p>
Who should I contact if I do not understand the content of the institutional communications I receive? Who can I contact if I am not able to speak on the phone about the institutional issues that concern me?	<p>The Municipality of Bologna, in collaboration with ASP Città di Bologna, has established a Centralised Service of Cultural Mediation. You can find more information at the following link</p> <p>http://informa.comune.bologna.it/iperbole/sportellosociale/servizi/2072/2649/</p>
Who can I contact if I suffer domestic violence?	<p>If you suffer domestic violence, you are encouraged to take contact with Casa delle Donne per non subire Violenza onlus. Useful and precious information can be found at the following link https://www.casadonne.it/</p> <p>Another useful Association is Associazione Senza Violenza, specialised in assisting women victim of violence but also violent men.</p> <p>http://www.senzaviolenza.it/</p>
Who can I contact if my family wants to oblige me to respect traditions that I do not share?	<p>The Centre for Families of ASP Città di Bologna, as well as the International Protection Service, could be useful places that you can try to contact for the mediation of family conflicts, also for cultural and traditional reasons.</p> <p>http://www.aspbologna.it/centro-per-le-famiglie/guida-agli-uffici/centro-per-le-famiglie</p> <p>http://informa.comune.bologna.it/iperbole/sportellosociale/servizi/4352/51374/</p>

ANTWERP

Resulting from the co-creative workshops, we could not retrieve the answers for many of the **FAQs** or could develop specific user stories. This is because both require very **specialised knowledge** and are in most cases, **most migrants are not aware of these answers nor the correct/conventional pathways to follow**. The data gathered during the co-creative workshops offer an overview of the topics that are frequently mentioned by participants of the workshops as difficult topics. However, FAQs and user stories need to be developed and answered by experts. The interviews and workshop with the local stakeholders and authorities were oriented at frequent difficulties for them and migrants and towards the ways in which the new MICADO tool could assist them in the support of recently arrived migrants in the city they work in. Since four themes and much more transversal themes needed to be covered during a limited amount of time, **more in-depth and specialised questions need to be developed** based on the data gathered until now, to ask the experts and to be able to construct both FAQs and user stories

Nonetheless, the overview of collected data gave already some clues on the information migrants are missing. These insights need to be transformed into real questions, with respective answers, in order to be valuable for the development of the MICADO tool. Since most migrants were not sufficiently aware of all customs and opportunities in Antwerp/Flanders/Belgium, it was hard to depart from the data collected through the workshops to further develop actual FAQs and user stories. Additionally, the difficulty of setting up these FAQs and user stories also varied across themes discussed in MICADO. What follows are some general remarks/examples with regard to the construction of FAQs.

Most newcomers do find information. However, this **information is often too fragmented, complex** (e.g., written in a legal language or complex Dutch), or relates to ‘official explanations’. This type of scattered information often does not help them to make any ‘choices’ or ‘decisions’, nor understand the overall institutional context. This is, for instance, the case when it comes to the choice of obliged (something many respondents are often not aware of) **mutuality/health care insurance** in Flanders. Although they are many providers of health care insurance, choosing one of them depends on the ‘pillars’ they belong to (e.g., Christian, socialist, liberal, neutral, independent, etc.) and the additional offers they provide (e.g., dental care, glasses, gifts after childbirth, leisure activities etc.) and enrolment fees. Hence, comparative websites of the enrolment fees, will not provide a full picture in which the actual benefits and costs of a particular health care insurance for a particular person/family are included. This means that everyone needs to make informed choices on which health care insurance suits his or her personal situation best. Providing some rules of thumb that may facilitate new members of society and health care insurance companies to make these choices could be very rewarding and helpful for the migrants to fully integrate and benefit from the existing social services.

Another example in which informal practices need to be specified more in detail relates to the knowledge most migrants have of the **Flemish secondary educational system**, which is also pillarized but state-subsidized. This system is subject to a general enrolment registration in Antwerp, for which you need to register in time and have already acquired knowledge on the existing schools and tracks that are available within this region. Related to school choice, and very influential for youngsters’ future educational and professional careers, is the track choice

at the beginning and throughout students' secondary school career. Although official sites and discourses will equally value all tracks (which is certainly true), it is important for newcomers to be aware of the distinct skills they actually provide for particular future jobs. Tracks are related to different social statuses, which is also important when estimating the value particular careers have on the labour market. Furthermore, although in theory, all kinds of track changes are possible, they only occur in particular ways, following a cascade-like structure (i.e., going from higher status tracks to lower status tracks). This cascade-like trend is partially due to the different curricula and dependence of feasibility to catch up in particular courses, but also very much embedded in the local school cultures and their subjective 'valuation' of tracks. The latter means that although it would also be hard to catch up on for instance courses like Car Mechanics, it is only conceived as a problem by teachers when it relates to Latin as this is valued as requiring a higher intelligence of pupils. Finally, although teachers give advice at the end of primary education on these track choices, these pieces of advice are socially and ethnically biased and not binding. Furthermore, there seems to be a trend that migrants' parents are more likely to follow these sometimes biased track recommendations, while others do not necessarily do so. Thus, to conclude, as shown by these examples of the health care and educational system, the FAQs we could include in the MICADO app could be very revealing when they help to explain 'the system' and the **informal practices related to the institutional context** in which people find themselves.

Apart from the need for more guidance in the institutional Antwerp/Flemish/federal context, and the scattered information provided now on official websites or even in the 'Welkom in Antwerpen' app, there is also some variation with regard to the themes included in the MICADO project. **While the structure of the health care and educational system is far more organised by governmental structures and led by governmental organisations, the opposite is true for housing and employment.** Although some issues relate to the governmental agencies and policies (e.g., unemployment allowances, agency for work, social housing), the government does not have to provide job offers or housing but its policies can have impact on the local labour and housing markets. For both housing and labour market issues, FAQs are far harder to be resolved and are often very context dependent. While many migrants have mentioned the structural barriers, such as discrimination based on ethnicity, race, social class or language proficiency, the finding of a job or accommodation is not necessarily provided by the government. Individual players, such as house tenants, employers in particular fields, have space for individual choice and strategies/policies. This often means that the most vulnerable groups are left out or encounter hard times in these markets.

6. Difficulties

During the process of developing this Logbook several difficulties to tackle in the process of development of the MICADO solution were identified. One of the main challenges ahead of MICADO is **data integration and updating**. Among others, the most important ones include the following: **data and privacy regulations; profiling/filtering the information; user involvement in interactive tools for community building**.

Additionally, this section offers some final thoughts on the **local commonalities and differences among the migrant population and integration services in the four pilot cities, the terminology to be used, the scope and ambition of the MICADO solution, and the remaining gaps in knowledge**. Rather than providing solutions, at this moment our aim was to collect all the issues/inconsistencies that might hinder the future development of the MICADO solution.

6.1. Data integration and updating

In all cities, interviewees warned for **the complexity in databases and the incompatibility of connecting different data systems due to data protection regulations**. Stakeholders in **Antwerp** use different data registering systems, sometimes even multiple systems within one organization, and making these systems communicate with each other or even visible outside the organization might be impossible. In **Bologna**, connecting databases on migrants is only possible when the owners of the data are the local actors, the city of Bologna or its services for migrants. In fact, it is not possible to unify data that is State property. Attempts have been made in the past, but no one seems to have been able to solve the problem effectively. In **Hamburg**, some processes reported during the interviews currently are done in paper form in order to not breach data protection regulations. Interviewees also highlighted different data systems, compatibilities and access rights. Also in **Madrid**, data protection policies might hinder tailoring the MICADO-solution to different users, as well as a lack of resources to respond to the high demands of international protection, which currently leads to saturation of existing systems. In addition, some entities (like CARs) do not consider accessing or visualizing general data on migration and reports on migrant populations relevant, as they mainly work with the internal data flow. Being able to cross data between existing databases, localizations and user profiles is useful at an institutional and strategic level, as it allows evidence-based decision making.

Bologna

The other interviewees, on the other hand, did not refer **to any existing application in the context of Bologna but appointed the set of databases** with which they are confronted in their daily work. The Municipality of Bologna, in fact, has its own social database called **"Garcia"** and used by all workers in the social sectors to record the people who turn to services. The database is owned by the Municipality of Bologna.

In addition to this database, **there are at least four other databases**: those for asylum seekers in SPRAR and CAS facilities, owned by the Ministry of the Interior; a database on

minors (SIM) always owned by the Ministry; a database of the Police Headquarters containing all the data of migrants related to legal status (called CUPA) and offering interactive functions at the service of migrants. The database, in fact, is equipped with an interface that allows you to schedule appointments with the police in order to obtain a residence permit or renewals.

Hamburg

A general overview that helps with internal communication within the authorities is the **Lagebild Flüchtlinge** (<https://www.hamburg.de/zkf-lagebild/>), a data overview provided by the Central Coordinating Unit for Refugees (ZKF). This monthly data report is issued as a pdf-publication online, giving an overview of several indicators and their change over time. MICADO is in contact with the ZKF to discuss whether this data could be integrated into the MICADO solution. This initial idea led to the general decision made by the Hamburg group to convene with several representatives of public authorities to analyse which data is required to improve existing work processes and which data could be used and provided by the MICADO solution.

The Hamburg team carried out two workshops on data requirements. The first workshop started with a presentation of the **Hamburg Urban Data Platform (UDP), a platform that connects and provides cross-sectional data in Hamburg**. HAM-LGV showed the idea of sharing data via standardized APIs, so that other organisations or projects can use existing data and combine them with other data in order to get new information, relevant for their own cases. HCU followed up with an example called CoSi (Cockpit Städtische Infrastrukturen). CoSi is a prototype showing the potential of linked data e.g. what influence does a new housing area with 1000 people have on the occupancy of kindergardens in the neighbourhood. **The potential of connecting data through CoSi** led participants to discussions on what is possible and what they need for their daily work in terms of migration and integration. Which data would be useful to provide standardized and automatized in the scope of MICADO, for example in order to use them for a city cockpit? The discussion has been directed to the questions **“What data can you share? And what data do you need in order to optimize processes?”**

The outcome of the first workshop in Hamburg (FHH) about the questions above can be divided as follows:

Offers/Services		
Data needed	Data already existing	Data needed by
Advanced training and work for refugees	https://ichblickdurch.de/	all
Clubs and volunteering for refugees	https://open-hamburg.de/	FHH, Volunteers
Experience exchange meetings	Internal Information	FHH
Overview of existing actors in the districts	unstructured	all
Offers for parents	Hamburg aktiv	tbc
Language courses	tbc	tbc
Integration of adults in the job market	IQ Netzwerk	tbc

Within the sector of Offers/Services there are at least four datasets that are already existing and need to be shared with other interested parties from the PAs.

Education		
Data needed	Data already existing	Data needed by
Regional Education Atlas	soon in Urban Data Platform	all

An Atlas presenting an overview of all educational institutes (eg. Kindergartens, schools or refugee accommodations) is already existing in Hamburg (<https://www.hamburg.de/bsb/regionaler-bildungsatlas-hamburg/>) and is important for all parties of the PAs. The Regional Education Atlas is migrating to an open source software called Masterportal (<https://www.masterportal.org/>). Within that migration process, the data used will be provided via the Hamburg Urban Data Platform.

The datasets are especially important for the Authority for Schools and Vocational Education.

Europe		
Data needed	Data already existing	Data needed by
Dataset of the number of migrants throughout Europe	https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/home	FHH

The dataset by Eurostat (<https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/home>) about migration in whole Europe is existing but not particularly relevant for the daily work of the LESC target group in Hamburg.

Health		
Data needed	Data already existing	Data needed by
Health data of migrants	tbc	tbc
Statistics infectious diseases	fördern und wohnen, tbc	tbc
Database of doctors working in a foreign language	www.kvhh.net	tbc

The datasets about health infrastructure are not relevant for all participating PAs. However, the topic of health infrastructure and related datasets could become interesting in the future through new cooperation within the MICADO project.

Housing		
Data needed	Data already existing	Data needed by
Occupancy of refugee accommodations	In UDP	FHH
Area-Information System (Flächeninformationssystem)	In UDP	FHH

Statistics protected accommodations	tbc	FHH
Daily occupancy and reporting of available places	fördern und wohnen, tbc	FHH
Number of remaining refugees (in regard of housing)	fördern und wohnen, tbc	tbc

Data about refugee accommodations and an area-information system are those datasets that are existing in Hamburg and need to be shared with all interested PAs.

Case: “Lagebild Flüchtlinge”		
Data needed	Data already existing	Data needed by
Overview of the situation of migrants in Hamburg	Monthly PDF	all

The overview “Lagebild Flüchtlinge”, edited by the ZKF, is relevant for all. Furthermore, it will be used as a use case in MICADO. Therefore, MICADO solutions will get integrated in the visualization of the “Lagebild Flüchtlinge”- data.

Welcome Information		
Data needed	Data already existing	Data needed by
Welcome Dashboard for migrants and refugees	we-inform.de/	all
General information about Asylum, Migration and Refugees	BAMF, tbc	tbc

The existing website we.inform. (<https://we-inform.de/portal/en/>) is a welcome dashboard for migrants and refugees in order to get informed about the most important aspects of their daily routine in Germany. The dataset is mainly important for migrants and refugees itself but also for PAs and NGOs.

The second workshop was planned as a data requirement workshop as well. However, as there have been only two participants from a number of invited PAs, the time has been used to discuss how we can get more PAs involved in the future.

A Mock-up of a dashboard of the well-known “Lagebild Flüchtlinge” was presented in January 2020 to a Steering Group dealing with refugee and migrant issues. By this improvement of the static PDF, that produces workload for almost all participating parties, the MICADO-Hamburg team wants to convince more PAs to join MICADO activities and to give input on content and function on the dashboard.

Madrid

Currently, the Directorate of Social Services and Social Integration of the Community of Madrid has an **internal database** containing social services users’ files from all administrations (local, regional and national), this information concerns subsidies they’ve received and services they have benefited from.

Public administration authorities are considering to implement a database system which would allow accredited social entities like the Red Cross or CEAR to both access and provide relevant information for local authorities to make users files more complete and detailed, the goal is to create an accessible sort of “**social record**” similar to a “medical record”.

The **Observatory of Migration** which is also dependent upon the GD for Social Services, gathers/produces the following data:

- City councils from the whole region who provide the observatory with census data biannually in advance to national statistics institute and this data provides insight on the number of migrants by nationality residing in the area, this data could be used to create the dashboard and to be cross-analysed with existing projects.
- The barometer about immigration (biennial report)
- Regional survey on immigration (biennial study)

Additionally, a regional branch of nationwide integrated employment system website offers a **virtual office for job seekers and employers**. The platform serves also as a database for technicians working in job counselling. All CVs are accessible, and data can be drawn using oracle and SQL driven platforms following a CRM software-like structure to produce internal reports and reports for funding entities both at the national level and the European one.

Participation and Integration Centers (CEPIs): Each month **CEPIs** facilitate their activity scheduling to the Directorate for Social Services and Social Integration as a database comprising information related to the type, objective, and public targeted by each activity as well as the information on the participants in each activity.

- CEPIs could provide information useful for migrants, other CEPIs, and social entities, as well as for the General Directorate of Social Affairs.
- The database provides information that could be used to map existing resources for migrants by geographical location and by themes: for instance, language courses (education), vocational training (employment), legal counselling (legal). Currently this information is only displayed on the CEPI’s website as a **pdf**.

The **General Directorate for Social Services and Social Integration** has a database in which **all the activities it finances are registered. Funds for the vulnerable populations** are managed through Access. **Low-income subsidies** are stored in an excel file.

- This information is useful for Dashboard creation, as the collected data could be imported to a platform in order to be exploited and visualized. For instance, **data on global expenditure, users’ profiles** (gender, nationality, geographical location), etc. It would be useful to map projects geographically to be able to identify which are the predominant intervention areas and which areas seem to receive less attention from public authorities. **The possibility of crossing data on migrant population concentration in certain areas with the number of projects financed by area** would be particularly appreciated.
- Another improvement that the Directorate is considering, is to elicit feedback from city councils concerning the projects which will be or have been financed in their city. This feedback is already in place for the low-income subsidy, but authorities would like it to be also in place for the subsidy on the vulnerable population. For instance, if there is a

project to improve employment of said population in a given city, the city council could, using the available data, give input and recommend to target certain population instead of another or advise to avoid altogether the implementation of a certain type of project given the local context. Thus, **information sharing would improve decision making concerning social intervention at a regional level.**

6.2. Data protection and privacy regulations

Data protection and privacy regulations are of capital importance in MICADO. As stated in the MICADO Grant Agreement (p. 34):

“As MICADO aims to collect and process personal data retrieved from migrants, data protection is a central issue in MICADO. If personal data protection is insufficiently considered, the overall legality of MICADO is threatened. Mitigation: In the project, the EU General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR 2016) will be obeyed to the fullest extent, and respective technical measures implemented. MICADO foresees principles of data protection by design (pseudonymising) and data protection by default. Personal data will be processed only with explicit consent given for the specific purposes. Privacy settings will be at high level from the start and records of processing activities will be maintained. Users have full control and access, and the right to correct their data, retention time for personal data. Information for data controller and data protection officer will be provided (s. art. 39 of AMGA). A Data Protection Impact Assessment according to article 35 of GDPR is considered in WP7 of the project. For specific issues, the consortium has consulted local data protection officers, and will continue doing so during the project lifetime. MICADO also aligns with the systemic standardisation approach to empower smart cities and communities (ESPRESSO), the regulations for spatial data (INSPIRE 2009), and obeys local data policies of the respective partner locations.”

On top of the challenges caused by the privacy regulations to data integration among various partners of the project, data sharing raises other privacy issues to be solved in the development phase of MICADO. First of all, the **privacy issues regarding the use of personal data of migrants that will be shared within the application.** Antwerp interviewees argue that the newcomer should be given agency, as an active owner of his/her own data in the app, being **able to decide which information could be shared with whom.** In addition, sharing personal information **should be ‘rewarding’ for the user,** not merely for the sake of following-up of his/her integration trajectory. On an organizational level, **it might be a difficult task to get ethical clearance** for the development of a system sharing personal data among organizations, as many interviewees in the different cities encountered already many difficulties and data protection issues with previous attempts to simplify data sharing.

It has been pointed out (Deliverable D1.3, p.43) that: “Well-guided procedures of use in this case are key: the user will not only consume information but also provide data to the system. Most importantly, users (migrants especially) shall provide valuable personal data such as biography, education, or professional skills in exchange when registering or using the cockpit. This valuable data input will allow much more profiled integration measures and management.”

A reluctance to share personal data has been identified during the workshops. Especially so for those **migrants of unclear legal situation, who might benefit the most from the existence of MICADO.** Thus, **careful design** is necessary in order to balance the privacy

regulations of data sharing, the necessity of profiling the information, and the ethical aspects of gathering data on a vulnerable population.

6.3. Profiling/filtering information

One of the main demands of the potential users of MICADO is for it to provide information profiled by the legal status of the immigrant/refugee and by proximity (geospatial data). An important aspect highlighted by the interviewees in all cities was the **delimitation of the migrant target group of the tool**. The approach and contents of the app should depend on the target group/specific groups of newcomers the app is directed to. A generic application for migrants should not be considered, because it would be too large to be operationalized, therefore the application should take into account the **differences in legal status, age, gender and migratory phase**.

However, **the categories into which the migrants fall are not fixed but change over time and place**; they not only depend on classic profiling: refugees, asylum seekers, resident or working migrants' permits, reunited families, but also on bilateral agreements that each country of origin has with the host country.

Moreover, given the volatility of the legal status of the migrants, over-profiling might lead to discrimination in access to information. One of the interviewees in Antwerp warned that the app should “use profiling only to a limited extent and for certain themes.” This concern calls for **a creative solution that would allow for profiling without limiting access to other information**.

6.4. User involvement in interactive tools for community building

Another issue of key importance for the development of the MICADO tool raised by the participants was the suggestion to make it an **open-approach interactive community-building tool** (Hamburg). The demands included an enhanced chatbot and interactive FAQs, for users to become involved and help each other in resolving their doubts. This approach is tempting, as it will allow for community building, an important aspect of the integration process. Nevertheless, it also entails the **risk of sharing false or incomplete information**. Also in Bologna, the possibility of creating a chat between migrants was discussed. Although the interviewees consider it an interesting and potentially useful idea, there is a risk that incorrect information will be passed between migrants.

A possible solution to this dilemma would be to create some kind of user involvement, for instance, a bulletin board that collects requests and offers, e.g. support for language classes within specific community languages, without running into the problem of sharing misinformation. Regardless, when it comes to users uploading content to the app, the necessity of involving moderators must be assessed.

6.5. Local commonalities and differences

Many local commonalities were identified during the recollection of the demands and issues raised by the migrants, the local stakeholders and authorities. Although the requests of migrants evidently vary among the cities, mostly due to the differences in the structure of local migrant populations and access to local services, the basic needs of migrants/refugees are similar among the newcomers to the pilot cities.

Nonetheless, important differences were spotted regarding: (i) multilevel governance, (ii) digitalization, (iii) characteristics of the local migrant population.

Concerning **multilevel governance**, a major issue is the complexity due to different levels of government involved in designing and implementing policies of integration of migrants. It is fairly easy to get lost (both for the developers and for the migrants) in the context of multilevel governance. As it has been already described in Deliverable 1.2 (p. 144): “Most of the cities involved in the project belong to a strongly decentralised government system, in which each level of government is responsible and autonomous in its activities. Moreover, even at a regional level, there are several different areas -or even third sector stakeholders- involved in migrant integration policies without a clear coordination board.”

What follows is a short description of these differences from Deliverable 1.2 (p.26):

“The intricacies of competences distribution in multilevel governments in a sensitive issue such as immigration can mislead the interpretation of the results. The four countries included in this report account for four different competencies distribution in this regard and, therefore, four different ways to design, implement and develop migration integration policies. Although that can be considered as a strength to encompass the diverse institutional structure present in the European context and so to be considered for the development of the application, it also presents several complexities when presenting general results. Thus, the city of Hamburg represents the case of a city-state in a federal system such as the German, in which the city holds some prerogatives and can lead by itself specific policies. The city of Antwerp which is also a region has developed different competences and has a strong relationship with third actors or organizations who directly lead most of the migration policies developed in this region. On the other hand, Bologna as a municipality within a region, leads innovative migration integration plans involving third actors in its development. Finally, Madrid as an Autonomous Community in a decentralized country, assumes direct responsibility in some areas, specially health, education and employment, when others like housing, refugees or more broad policies relies on national or local government levels.”

It is crucial to acknowledge these differences in governance networks among the pilot cities from the point of data gathering and integration, but also from the point of view of the end-user, who many times does not know where to find a solution for his problem – whether at the local, regional or national level of governance. Providing a clear distinction between these levels is key for the information to be useful to the newcomers.

Secondly, the level of **digitalization** of local services and data is unequal among the pilot cities. This issue is described in more detail in sections 2.2.3 and 6.1. However, as the divergence goes from, for instance, uploading online information on courses offered by each centre specialized in migrant integration in Madrid, separately in a pdf form, to Hamburg Urban Data Platform that connects and provides cross-sectional data, it is important to bear in mind these differences in the convergence phase of the project.

Third, we identified several differences among the **characteristics of the local migrant populations** in the four cities involved (see Section 2). To name just a few: females dominate in Madrid and in Bologna; the migrant population is on average the oldest in Hamburg; there share of migrants with temporary residence is the lowest in Madrid; low-educated foreign females' employment rate is almost three times higher in Madrid than in Antwerp (59.6% and 22.9%, respectively); and, finally, while the knowledge of the local language is not the main issue in Madrid, it is of key importance for the access to services both in Antwerp and Hamburg. These differences should be taken into account in the design of local solutions after the convergence process.

6.6. Terminology/Stigmatisation

An unsolved question is: what term to use when describing the migrant population? The terms migrant, refugee, asylum seeker, newcomer, foreigner, foreign-born are sometimes used interchangeably, although they describe different groups of people. The necessity to maintain a **critical awareness** with regard to these categories, terms and concepts, was already raised in the Deliverable D1.2 (pp. 35-38), as “they are created and do not simply represent the world, but reconstruct and reinforce it, also through the iterative relation between academia, policy-making and public opinion.” On top of that, what was mentioned by several participants is the danger of **stigmatisation**. The term “migrant” might not fit everyone, or people might not feel addressed by it. Thus, the term “newcomer/arrivals” could be a better alternative. However, it limits the target to those whose arrival is fairly recent (e.g. last two years) and some of the potential users of MICADO tool are to be encountered also among the more settled migrants. This issue needs to be resolved during the convergence sessions.

6.7. Scope and ambition

Interviewees have also emphasized **the importance of the broader context** in which the MICADO-solution will be implemented. **An app or website cannot be seen as a miracle solution-for-all**. It should primarily be seen as a digital support tool during the integration process. Personal contact was mentioned as being of high importance, as it leads to people taking up responsibility and enabling change. A digital tool can facilitate overcoming certain barriers such as information gaps, but true hindrances in integration such as experienced discrimination, financial burdens or the difficulty of establishing social connections won't be solved by the creation of an application. There needs to be more awareness rising towards migration issues in society as a whole and in all public bodies that must include migration as a cross-cutting issue, as political instability and economic crises do not prioritize the adoption of new tools for integration.

It is essential to think bold when developing the MICADO solution. However, **this tool will not outperform other already existing, specialized platforms in various of the MICADO domains such as house renting websites or job-seeking platforms.**

6.8. Gaps in knowledge

After reviewing the deliverables, internal working documents, and country reports on the results of the co-creation, co-design workshops and interviews, the following gaps in knowledge were identified:

- There is limited data gathered on the possible **dead ends** the migrants face due to their status and characteristics and many times due to the incompatibility in time frames of administrative procedures. For instance, in order to sign a work contract, you would need a German bank account to receive the salary. In order to open an account, you need to be registered in Germany. But in order to be registered, you need an address and thus, an apartment. You cannot sign your work contract without the bank account. And the probability to find an apartment is raised in turn by being employed. One possible way of breaking this vicious circle is registering domicile at a friend's place, registering a bank account, and signing the work contract. Identifying more of these dead ends (or vicious circles) related to particular status of the user of MICADO would be useful for the further stages of this project.
- A related issue is that of **tricks** to get something done. Many times, migrants share insider knowledge among them on how to get things done in a more *de facto* than *de iure* way. The access to this kind of information was one of the demands raised during the workshops. How to present info on tricks to get something done without falling into recommending unethical or uncertain behaviour?
- Most of the administrative procedures can be done online. However, to access these features, one most probably will need a digital certificate. Getting one is a complex process, especially for the non-natives. Thus, MICADO tool might also serve of guidance and as an **entry door to the digital administration**.
- Finally, after compiling the workshops' results, it is safe to say that the knowledge on the **local CSOs' demands** is limited at this point, at least compared to the migrants' demands. Hence, it would be advisable to gather more data with regard to the expectations of future MICADO users on the side of local migrant integration entities.

7. Conclusions

The Logbook for Development compiled the results of the co-creative sessions and interviews with local authorities in four partner cities of MICADO for later IT development. To contextualize this knowledge, it first offered a description of local migrant populations to get to know MICADO's target groups better. Subsequently, it systematically gathered the demands of the stakeholders involved in the integration process (migrants, public authorities and CSOs) together with data on the usage of existing apps. Additionally, User Personas, User Stories and FAQs were listed for each city in order to inform and facilitate the development of the MICADO tool accordingly to the local context. Finally, it briefly assessed the difficulties identified while gathering both qualitative and quantitative data in WP1 and WP2 to show the possible hindrances that the project might encounter in the development phase.

This document is complementary to the deliverables D2.1 'Overview of existing solutions incl. data and Demand Analysis for MICADO key services' and D2.2 'Strategic Data Visualization Kit.'

On top of the difficulties described in the previous section related to data integration and updating, data and privacy regulations, profiling/filtering the information, user involvement in interactive tools for community building, heterogeneity of local migrant populations and integration services in the four pilot cities, the terminology, the scope and ambition of the MICADO solution, and the remaining gaps in knowledge, the following and final three limitations should be considered in the convergence and development phase of the project:

- 1) **Legal status** is the single most important discriminating variable during the migrant integration process. National legislations are complex and vary (e.g., the tolerated status in Germany), thus classifying the legal status in each country is the most pressing issue to address during the convergence process. It will have a crucial impact on the development of the MICADO tool (e.g., user personas, user stories, profiling of information, etc.).
- 2) **Available data** on migrant population on the local level is scarce. Data gathered in section 2 of this document offers some insight, as well as data described in section 2 of the Deliverable 2.1. However, there are still some gaps to fill in. For instance, with regard to the share of the foreign population in each city/region, it has been observed that the high number of citizens with foreign nationality in Hamburg might be due to higher restrictions in naturalization processes compared to the other cities. Thus, a better description of local migrant populations, considering the local idiosyncrasies in legal regulations, is one of the challenges for MICADO, given that the digital tool could gather the missing data in order to better inform local policies regarding migrant integration.
- 3) **Collected data** on migrants' and CSOs' demands in many cases did not allow for an "inductive" compilation of User Stories and FAQs. Data gathered through the co-creation workshops and interviews are insufficient to derive the profiles of the possible users and their stories in a comprehensive way. In order not to fall into "cherry-picking" in selecting the information to be included in the FAQs, User Stories, etc., further data should be collected during the piloting phase and the development of the tool adjusted

accordingly. Additionally, experts should be consulted during the process of fine graining user stories and FAQs. Finally, in the upcoming stages of the project, the representativeness of local migrant populations should be considered in the decisions made by the consortium.

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PART II – CONVERGENCE HANDBOOK

Workshop Handbook

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1. Introduction

The idea of the **MICADO Convergence Handbook** originated from the necessity to create a handy tool and a common thread leading the way through the **First Convergence Workshop of MICADO, held in Hamburg in January 2020** in the context of the third Work Package (Concept Convergence). The first project year had seen a thorough sociological research on challenges in migration integration, after which researchers had conducted co-creative workshops with stakeholder and target groups to determine critical demands that a MICADO solution could answer to. The goal of the Convergence Workshop was to **identify those needs that would be part of the Minimal Viable Product (MVP) and pair these with possible technical solutions in order to kick-start the development phase.**

The Handbook was used as a physical workshop tool that displayed all relevant content needed for this converging task in a **graphical, easily accessible manner**. Each page could be torn out so the data presented on it could be used and worked with on flip charts and in group work.

Together, the consortium was to boil down the manifold results of the demand analysis and **end up with a few hand-picked choices to be able to start development tasks**. In order to identify and choose the most important needs that would be part of the MVP, the MICADO consortium had to refresh the knowledge on all demands that had been raised in the four pilot cities Antwerp, Bologna, Hamburg and Madrid by the stakeholder and target groups (migrants, civil society organizations and public administrations) in the first project year. The criteria that would help prioritizing were (1) in how many cities a demand is shared, (2) for how many cities there is data available to address the demand, and (3) the criticality of a demand expressed by each city.

To fulfill these tasks, the Handbook displayed a variety of information that was based on previous work in the project:

- 1) **a summary and categorization of requirements raised by the target groups in the co-creative workshops** (Logbook for Development, Task 2.4). These “need-cards” displayed the requirement itself, the domain and by which stakeholder group it had been raised on the frontside, as well as by how many cities the need had been raised and a provisional categorization of criticality from 1 to 3 on the backside. Thus, each page could be torn out and pinned to a wall;
- 2) **the User Stories and User Personas** developed on the basis of a one-year long research phase containing, among others a Systematic Literature Research, as well as demand analyses with stakeholder interviews, co-creative stakeholder workshops, and stakeholder mappings as part of work package 1 and 2;
- 3) four tables with the **data availabilities** of all pilot cities (not complete);
- 4) possible **technical solutions** laid out by the developers in the project;

- 5) a **glossary** displaying selected definitions to facilitate understanding between disciplines of technical/social science. These were taken from the MICADO Wiki Glossary (<https://github.com/micado-eu/MICADO/wiki/Glossary>).

1.1. Convergence Workshop Dynamics

1.1.1. First Step: Completing Shared Needs

In preparation for the first step, the organization team pinned all need-cards from the first chapter of the Handbook to four walls indicating the number of cities that had formulated the demand. The first wall displayed all needs that had only been raised in one city, the second by two cities, and so forth.

Thereafter, copies of the Handbook were handed out and all participants formed local groups and were given time to familiarize themselves with the manifold needs and requirements of all four pilot cities summarized in chapter 1.

The groups were then tasked to rip out each need-card, discuss it and make sure their city's name was written on the card in case it was raised during their city's demand analysis. Alternatively, they were to identify needs that were formulated in a different manner but described the same need, group these needs, and move that requirement to the next wall as it had now one more city that shared it. The goal of this first step was for all local groups to reassess all need-cards once so that in the end the cards could be sorted on flip charts according to the number of cities in which they were shared.

Only needs that were shared in three or all four pilot cities were carried to the next decision step.

1.1.2. Second Step: Matching Data Availability to most shared needs

In the second step, all local teams were given the task to assign differently coloured stickers to the remaining needs depending on the level of data availability from their city's perspective [option 1 – good data availability - blue, option 2 – medium data availability - yellow, option 3 – bad data availability - red]. Here, the Handbook presented the collected data availabilities in the cities and served as an information repository. Medium data availability meant cases where the data was not available in all of the cities, where the demand existed.

Only those needs with good or medium data availability were carried to the next decision step.

1.1.3. Third Step: Analysing Criticality and Data Availability in the Matrix

On a large chalk-wall, a matrix was drawn with the dimensions' criticality on the x-axis and data availability on the y-axis. In a group effort, all needs were assessed, discussed, and then sorted into the four quadrants. Quadrant 1 indicated: high criticality, good data availability; quadrant 2 showed medium criticality and good data availability, quadrant 3 showed high criticality and medium data, and quadrant 4 showed low criticality and medium data availability.

Those needs in quadrant 1 were deemed as the ones to be included in the Minimum Viable Product. All needs of the quadrants 1, 2 and 3 were considered important enough to be saved and taken to the next step of creating so-called epics. Epics is a term used in agile development to describe a body of work than can be broken down into specific tasks based on the needs of end users⁶.

⁶ Rehkopf, M. Agile epics: definition, examples, and templates. In: Atlassian Agile Coach.

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1.1.4. Fourth Step: Writing the Epics by pairing the most Critical Needs with Technical Feasibility

After having reduced and condensed the many needs of all pilot cities to the most urgent ones with good or at least medium data availability, day two of the Convergence Workshop aimed at first grouping and thereafter enriching the remaining groups with important specifics and details, such as their technical feasibility. The epics that were created through this process, symbolise the transition of rather sociological research results into technical instructions and therefore symbolise the whole convergence process. To create the epics, templates for all 19 remaining need-groups were prepared on flipchart paper and spread over the whole workshop area so that small groups could work on them. The template asked to summarise the main criteria of each need on one paper, namely its criticality, its data availability as well as its technical feasibility. Groups of three to four people from different piloting cities were working on one epic before moving around the room to find each other in a new group to work on the next epic.

1.1.5. Fifth Step: Evaluation and Categorization of Epics

In the last step, all epics were presented to the consortium. Through group discussions, four categories were formed to sort the epics, also in preparation of a possible app structure. Thereafter, each epic was evaluated through a scoring system to be able to prioritise them. At the end of the workshop, all epics were handed over to the development team, formally kicking off the development work.

4 categories

- Guided procedures → guided processes
- Links to external resources → info portal / events
- PA exchange & collaboration → migrant situation monitor, integration task monitor
- Explanations & clarifications → glossary, guided processes

1.1.6. Sixth Step: Conclusion

This description comprises the individual steps that guided the convergence of scientific research results into technical development issues. The four categories lead to the initial architecture of the App that is to be developed. The guided processes, links to external resources and explanations & clarifications are represented in the frameworks that are part of the “Cockpits” within the App, while the PA exchange & collaboration are shown within the “Dashboards”. Additional functionalities have been added, such as a consent manager for the management of personal data.

2. Table of Prioritized Needs

Content:

- 1. Table of Prioritized Needs
- 2. User Stories
- 3. User Personas
- 4. Technical Solutions

DESCRIPTION		
TYPE OF NEED	DEMANDS OF ...	
 priority	Raised by: xxxxxx xxxxx	
		City City
		City City
EXAMPLE ABOVE – Slide at the top is the front – slide in the middle is the backside possibility to pin it against the wall on the right top corner – So when it's on the wall you can flip it to get more detailed infos		

Information should be provided in the simplest possible way. Conceptual and visual maps, avoiding long and excessively "legal" texts		
Transversal	M/R	
 critical	Raised by: Migrants Refugees	
		Madrid Antwerp
		Hamburg Bologna

ABOVE – filled out example
BELOW - Color codes and abbreviations

Labour	Migrants/ Refugees =M/R	
Education	Public Authorities =PA	
Participation	Local Stakeholders =LS	

2.1. Demands of Migrants and Refugees

Demands of:

Refugees & Migrants

Information should be provided in the simplest possible way. Conceptual and visual maps, avoiding long and excessively "legal" texts		
Transversal	M/R	
A glossary for each thematic area (terms/concepts)		
Transversal	M/R	
Data should be constantly updated		
Transversal	M/R	

		Madrid Antwerp Hamburg Bologna	
		Madrid Antwerp	
		Madrid Antwerp Hamburg Bologna	
		Madrid Antwerp	
		Madrid Antwerp Hamburg Bologna	
		Madrid Antwerp Hamburg Bologna	

Important	2	Raised by: Migrants Refugees	Accessibility for (digital) illiterate and blind users	M/R	★
		Madrid			
Important	2	Raised by: Migrants Refugees	The information on the level of government involved should be clearly visible	M/R	★
		Madrid Hamburg			
Important	2	Raised by: Local Stakeholders	Filter information by district (proximity)	M/R	★
		Madrid			
Important	2	Raised by: Migrants Refugees	An interactive map with local services such as doctors, NGOs, language courses, etc. featuring filters by domains	M/R	★
		Antwerp Bologna			
Important	2	Raised by: Migrants Refugees / Local Stakeholders	Include a feature for cultural mediation/translator request	M/R	★
		Madrid Antwerp			
Important	2	Raised by: Migrants Refugees	Online groups/chats by country of origin and interest	M/R	★
		Madrid			

		Madrid	
		Madrid	
		Antwerp	
		Madrid Antwerp Hamburg	
		Madrid Antwerp	
		Madrid Hamburg	

	 Desirable	Raised by: Migrants Refugees
		Antwerp
	 Desirable	Raised by: Migrants Refugees
		Antwerp
	 Desirable	Raised by: Migrants Refugees
		Antwerp

Formal requirements and the procedure to be able to obtain the health card (ES), insurance (DE, BE)		
Health	M/R	

Information about the difference between emergency health facilities and services and ordinary health and prevention facilities and services (when to go where)		
Health	M/R	

Information on NGOs/Official institutions/Medical associations that provide medical (and psychological) support services to immigrants		
Health	M/R	

	 critical	Raised by: Migrants Refugees
		Madrid Antwerp Hamburg

Information on coverage of state-subsidized prescribed medicines for low-income families / information on eligibility for free treatment and about ways to obtain an exemption from payments		
Health	M/R	

	 critical	Raised by: Migrants Refugees / Local Stakeholders
		Madrid Antwerp Bologna

Advise on how to self-insure for self-employed migrants		
Health	M/R	

	 Important	Raised by: Migrants Refugees
		Madrid Hamburg

Information on which treatment or medication is paid for by the insurance and what needs to be paid by oneself		
Health	M/R	

2	Important	Raised by: Migrants Refugees	Antwerp	Information on night pharmacies	Health	M/R	
2	Important	Raised by: Migrants Refugees / Local Stakeholders	Hamburg Antwerp	More knowledge on the history, culture and society of the host community regarding sexuality and health, example: www.zanzu.de/en/	Health	M/R	
3	Desirable	Raised by: Local Stakeholders	Hamburg		Health	M/R	
2	Important	Raised by: Local Stakeholders	Madrid Bologna	Information necessary for choosing an insurance	Health	M/R	
2	Important	Raised by: Migrants Refugees	Hamburg	"Doctor finder": a map-based overview of physicians offering (free) walk-in appointments (sorted by GENDER and LANGUAGE)	Health	M/R	
2	Important	Raised by: Migrants Refugees	Hamburg	Telephone service for translation in hospitals and a list of doctors speaking migrant's languages	Health	M/R	

	3 Desirable	Raised by: Migrants Refugees
		Hamburg
	3 Desirable	Raised by: Migrants Refugees
		Hamburg

Information on rights and obligations as tenants. Sample of a contract with a simple explanation		★ 🏠
Housing	M/R	
Information on alternative housing/ways to find a flat: cooperatives, social housing, student housing, bonds by friends		★ 🏠
Housing	M/R	
Information about the requirements to qualify for e.g. social housing and government benefits such as rental subsidies		★ 🏠
Housing	M/R	

	1 critical	Raised by: Migrants Refugees/ Local Stakeholders
		Madrid Antwerp Hamburg
	2 Important	Raised by: Local Stakeholders
		Hamburg
	2 Important	Raised by: Migrants Refugees
		Antwerp

Information on NGOs accompanying migrants in the process of finding housing		★ 🏠
Housing	M/R	
Provide simple 'tips and tricks' that advice newcomers to e.g. don't pay the deposit in cash, to never pay before having visited the house		★ 🏠
Housing	M/R	
Information on ways in which the social services can provide certificates to facilitate the administrative procedure of census registration		★ 🏠
Housing	M/R	

		Madrid	
		Madrid	
		Madrid	
		Antwerp	
		Hamburg	
		Madrid	

		Madrid		
		Madrid		
		Hamburg		
		Bologna		
		Antwerp		
			Information on free professional training and certificates offered by the Public Employment Services	

		Madrid Hamburg Bologna		
		Madrid		
		Madrid		
		Antwerp Hamburg		
		Madrid		
		Hamburg		

	 Desirable	Raised by: Migrants Refugees
		Hamburg
	 Desirable	Raised by: Local Stakeholders
		Antwerp

Announcement board for users to promote events /Collect requests and offers		
Participation	M/R	
Include a tool that enables migrants to reach each other and engage with the local community		
Participation	M/R	
Access to announcements of volunteer activities		
Participation	M/R	

	 critical	Raised by: Migrants Refugees
		Madrid Hamburg
	 critical	Raised by: Migrants Refugees
		Antwerp Hamburg Bologna
	 Important	Raised by: Migrants Refugees
		Madrid

Information about cultural activities, especially those free of charge		
Participation	M/R	
Information on how to find sport clubs/leisure activities and become member of clubs		
Participation	M/R	
Participation	M/R	

	 Desirable	Raised by: Migrants Refugees
		Madrid
	 Desirable	Raised by: Migrants Refugees
		Antwerp Bologna

2.2. Demands of Public Authorities

Demands of:

Develop a digital databank of all organizations, projects or available data regarding integration. An overview of all existing resources, counselling offers, locations and information, and likewise more general networking of all available actors		
Transversal	PA	
Provide a web-based version of the app, as members of public authorities are not provided with smartphones		
Transversal	PA	
Map the existing resources for migrants/projects by geographical location and by themes (e.g. language courses [education], vocational training [employment], legal counselling [legal]) to identify which are the predominant intervention areas and which areas seem to receive less attention from public authorities		
Transversal	PA	

			Transversal PA	
			PA	
			Transversal PA	
			Transversal PA	
			Transversal PA	
			Transversal PA	

	 Desirable	Hamburg
	 Desirable	Madrid

2.3. Demands of Local Stakeholders

Pooling and overview on all existing resources, counselling offers, locations and information, to provide individual assistance to newcomers and, when necessary, refer them to organisations accordingly		
Transversal	LS	
Data sharing: the possibility to share overlapping and relevant information could be useful both for the organisations as well as for the newcomers who won't be required to constantly provide the same information		
Transversal	LS	
Networking and Collaboration: MICADO-tool should facilitate the exchange and the cooperation of different actors		
Transversal	LS	

			Transversal	
			Transversal	
			Transversal	
			Transversal	
			Transversal	
			Transversal	

	 critical	Antwerp Hamburg
	 Desirable	Hamburg

3. User Stories

Domain	Goal	Goal	Goal	Goal
City				

3.1. Bologna

Education Bologna	Enrolment Procedure (long term migrants)	Enrolment Procedure (asylum seekers)	Professional Training (Asylum seekers)	Professional Training (long term migrants)
Main Actors	Migrant parents Schools Bologna municipality	Asylum seekers parents, Schools host structure (cooperative) ASP (manager of services) Bologna municipality	Asylum seekers host structure (cooperative) ASP (manager of services) Bologna municipality	Migrants Bologna municipality Emilia Romagna region Associations / third sector
Goal as perceived by participants	Enroll son/daughter in 'best' primary school	Enroll son/daughter in 'best' primary school	Find training that ensure career opportunities	Find training that ensure career opportunities
Level of organisation	Municipality level School level	Regional Level Municipality level School level	Regional Level Municipality level	Regional Level Municipality level
Stakeholders involved	CD/LEI (public organization to obtain informations about schools for migrants) Migrant parents and children	Host structure (Cooperatives) ASP (manager of services) Asylum seekers parents and their childrens	Host structure (Cooperatives) Associations Private companies for professional training University of Bologna	Private companies for professional training Associations University of Bologna

Education Bologna	Enrolment Procedure (long term migrants)	Enrolment Procedure (asylum seekers)	Professional Training (Asylum seekers)	Professional Training (long term migrants)
Actions undertaken	Wait for the letter of the public authority (for mandatory level of instruction) ask to social services ask to the school Direct Enrolment (Also for migrants without regular documents)	Wait for the letter of the public authority (for mandatory level of instruction) ask to social services ask to the school Direct Enrolment (Also for migrants without regular documents)	To define with the host cooperative (SPAR) the needs of the asylum seekers To match the interest with the opportunities available ask to the cooperative's educator to register the asylum seeker for professional training	Search on internet for opportunities in training opportunities ask to the community of reference (Example: Senegalese community) Contact the agencies for temporary works Search for financial support or pay the training
Preconditions for success	Digital literacy Contact with educational system (through other school actors) Knowledge of other persons in the same situation	Knowledge of the language Knowledge of other persons in the same situation Relations with the social services Knowledge of the educational system and of the educational laws	Knowledge of the language Personal Motivations	Knowledge of the language Personal Motivations real compatibility between training and available job offers
Potential hindrances jeopardizing success	Lack of guidance Lack of interest by the parents Digital illiteracy Language proficiency	Language proficiency Lack of interest by the parents Social isolation/discriminatory environment Digital illiteracy	Language proficiency Social isolation Digital illiteracy Homogenization of the professional training (so many migrants trained in the same sector) Lack of guidance by the host structure	Language proficiency Social isolation Digital illiteracy Lack of training opportunities Lack of traineeship due to the professional training courses

Health Bologna	Obtain a health card (tessera sanitaria)	Procedure for recognition of total exemption in the health system	Find a linguistic mediator
Main Actors	Migrants Bologna Health services (Spaziello Unico del Distretto dell'Azienda Usi di Bologna) Questura of Bologna Bologna Municipality	Migrants Bologna Health services (Spaziello Unico del Distretto dell'Azienda Usi di Bologna) associations for social promotion (ACLI, CNF Union (CGIL, CISL, UIL etc.)	Migrants Bologna Health system Social services and social workers
Goal as perceived by participants	To have a health card as soon as possible	access to health services free of charge	To have a linguistic translation of their specific language
Level of organisation	Municipality level National Level (Questura)	Municipality level Health services level	Municipality level Health services level Social services level
Stakeholders involved	Associations for migrants health Family counselling and space for immigrant women and their children	associations for social promotion (ACLI, CNF Union (CGIL, CISL, UIL etc.)	Private service of linguistic mediation Public Relations Office and Relations with Voluntary Associations (Public Social workers Family members (or friends) Italian speakers

Health Bologna	Obtain a health card (tessera sanitaria)	Procedure for recognition of total exemption in the health system	Find a linguistic mediator
Actions undertaken	Ask to family counselling or health associations for migrants the procedure to follow Go and ask to the "Spaziello Unico" Ask to an association about the temporary health card (same duration of resident permit and for the irregular migrant only 6 months)	go to the social promotion associations of Bologna or to the trade unions to produce the certificate of their economic condition (ISEE) Go to the "Spaziello Unico" and ask the total exemption	Ask for a linguistic translation to the social workers (if they have it one) ask to the Bologna Health services (Public Relations Office and Relations with Voluntary Associations) when the migrant booked the health service (the translation can be scheduled in advance, on an urgent call, and always available in a fixed location) Going to the health structure with a family member for the translation
Preconditions for success	Associations for migrants health Digital Literacy Have a regular job and a valid residential permit in the city of Bologna (Questura level) Knowledge of other persons in the same situation Relations with the social services Knowledge of the health system and of the educational laws	Knowledge of the procedure Knowledge of the services that help to implement the practices Knowledge of the language Digital Literacy Knowledge of other persons in the same situation	correspondence between spoken language or dialect and linguistic mediation quality of the translation relationship between migrant and translator

Health Bologna	Obtain a health card (tessera sanitaria)	Procedure for recognition of total exemption in the health system	Find a linguistic mediator
Potential hindrances jeopardizing success	Language proficiency Social isolation Digital illiteracy Lack of knowledge of health system organization in the hosting country Fear of being reported if irregularly staying on the territory	Language proficiency Social isolation or social problems Lack of knowledge of health system organization in the hosting country Lack of guidance	low level of linguistic mediation absence of linguistic mediators for rare languages Lack of guidance

Labour Bologna	Potential hindrances jeopardizing success	Language proficiency Social Isolation Digital Illiteracy be a lone parent without assistance in the management of children presence of great traumas or physical and mental pathologies	Social Isolation Digital Illiteracy High cost of the courses Gender segregation legitimate by the tradition of the country of origin Low individual motivation presence of great traumas or physical and mental pathologies	Language proficiency Social Isolation lack of knowledge of labour rights Digital Illiteracy	Housing dimension job loss precarious employment contracts Lack of knowledge of the procedure Lack of guidance
	Find a Job	Renewing the residence permit for work purposes			

Labour Bologna	Main actors	Migrants Public Employment office of Bologna Temporary job agencies Migrants' Social networks Questura of Bologna Bologna Municipality	Migrants Bologna Municipality Linguistic training centers Private foundation	Migrants Legal services Questura of Bologna	Renewing the residence permit for work purposes
	Goal as perceived by participants	To find a good job with a good salary that it is compatible with the migrant's aspirations, skills and competences	acquire a level of knowledge of Italian that can facilitate access to more qualified jobs	be protected in situations of abuse, discrimination or exploitation by employers	obtain the renewal of the residence permit as quickly as possible in order to be able to find work or not to risk losing it.
Level of organisation	Municipality Level Individual level	Municipality Level Individual level	Municipality Level Individual level	Municipality Level Individual level	Municipality Level Individual level
Stakeholders involved	Work agencies Social cooperatives with a "work" area of intervention Migrants social networks in Bologna Private companies	Public linguistic centers Private schools for foreigners (Ex: The University of Foreigners)	Legal services for migrants Unions' legal services Associations / Third sectors specialized in legal services for migrants (or vulnerable persons)	Sometimes Associations / third sectors specialized in legal services for migrants (or vulnerable persons, Ex: Avvocato di strada / International protection legal services - ASP)	Sometimes Associations / third sectors specialized in legal services for migrants (or vulnerable persons, Ex: Avvocato di strada / International protection legal services - ASP)

Labour Bologna	Actions undertaken	Define a plan with the social cooperatives specialized on "work" registration with the employment office. registration with the temp work agencies. Random Distribution of CV sharing with their own friendly networks Follow a professional training with a period of internship in the company	ask the educator for information about the available courses Go to community associations to ask where to do them search the internet for available information	Ask family members or friends for legal assistance Request for legal advice from associations specializing in legal support (Example: Street lawyers, AI Street) Requesting assistance from the International Protection Legal Service (ASP) Requesting legal assistance to the Union legal services	Renewing the residence permit for work purposes
	Find a Job	Improve the language for a better chance of finding a job or do the mandatory Italian language test (B1 level)	Improve the language for a better chance of finding a job or do the mandatory Italian language test (B1 level)	Obtain legal advice in case of problems at work	Obtain legal advice in case of problems at work
Preconditions for success	Knowledge of the language Digital Literacy Strong social relation successful completion of the internship in a company reduced labour force pool (example: dequalifying contexts) offering jobs that are compatible with the person's skills and abilities	Strong individual Motivation Availability of free/cheap courses Digital Literacy	Strong individual Motivation Legal knowledge of labour laws (and abuses) Strong social relation that help to find legal support (for free or cheap) Presence of a legal support	Digital Literacy To have a regular job Respect the procedure to live in a housing whose dimensions are not inferior to the minimums of law not having committed any crime or illegal activity	Digital Literacy To have a regular job Respect the procedure to live in a housing whose dimensions are not inferior to the minimums of law not having committed any crime or illegal activity

Labour Bologna	Find a Job	Improve the language for a better chance of finding a job or do the mandatory Italian language test (B1 level)	Improve the language for a better chance of finding a job or do the mandatory Italian language test (B1 level)	Obtain legal advice in case of problems at work	Obtain legal advice in case of problems at work
	Actions undertaken	Define a plan with the social cooperatives specialized on "work" registration with the employment office. registration with the temp work agencies. Random Distribution of CV sharing with their own friendly networks Follow a professional training with a period of internship in the company	ask the educator for information about the available courses Go to community associations to ask where to do them search the internet for available information	Ask family members or friends for legal assistance Request for legal advice from associations specializing in legal support (Example: Street lawyers, AI Street) Requesting assistance from the International Protection Legal Service (ASP) Requesting legal assistance to the Union legal services	Renewing the residence permit for work purposes
Preconditions for success	Knowledge of the language Digital Literacy Strong social relation successful completion of the internship in a company reduced labour force pool (example: dequalifying contexts) offering jobs that are compatible with the person's skills and abilities	Strong individual Motivation Availability of free/cheap courses Digital Literacy	Strong individual Motivation Legal knowledge of labour laws (and abuses) Strong social relation that help to find legal support (for free or cheap) Presence of a legal support	Digital Literacy To have a regular job Respect the procedure to live in a housing whose dimensions are not inferior to the minimums of law not having committed any crime or illegal activity	Digital Literacy To have a regular job Respect the procedure to live in a housing whose dimensions are not inferior to the minimums of law not having committed any crime or illegal activity

Housing Bologna	Search apartment to rent	To Candidate for a social house	procedures for emergency housing
Main actors	Migrants Rent app agencies Online platform	Migrants ACER (social housing institution in Bologna region)	Migrants Social services ASP (Housing transition)
Goal as perceived by participants	Find the best housing solution available	Get access to the social housing paying a cheap rent	find a temporary solution in the shortest possible time that can mitigate the housing emergency
Level of organisation	Municipality level Digital level	Metropolitan level housing institution level	Metropolitan Level (metropolitan city of Bologna) Municipality level
Stakeholders involved	Migrant social network Local community Association/third sector	ASP Social workers Association (Ex. Sunia)	Social workers

Housing Bologna	Search apartment to rent	To Candidate for a social house	procedures for emergency housing
Actions undertaken	Search online platform Ask to some friends Ask to the employers Move to the apartment of a friend/family member	Go to the ACER office go to local associations working on the issue of housing to get help Ask to the social worker Apply online	Talk to their social workers to fill in the request form for emergency housing Ask to the health services (when the current apartment is not compatible with the health condition of the migrant and when the apartment conditions are really dangerous for the life of someone)
Preconditions for success	Knowledge of the rent system in Bologna Strong relational network have good digital skills alternative housing projects carried out by associations (Example: Vesta Project) Willingness to live with people in need of care and who in return donate a portion of their rental accommodation at low prices or free of charge	have the necessary requirements to enter the list reside or work in the municipality understand the functioning of the online accommodation application know the different elements that can jeopardize the demand for social housing practices to be carried out	be willing to undertake a family educational path to get out of the emergency housing situation be willing to work even if you are a woman who has never worked before be prepared to contribute financially while in emergency accommodation

3.2. Hamburg

User Stories

Hamburg

Education Hamburg	Main Actors	Funding for higher education	Finding appropriate language class	School success	Diploma recognition
Goal as perceived by participants	Migrant parents Find a funding to finance studies	Migrant parents Teachers Co-students	Migrants Finding a class matching the requirements in terms of language level, location, setting (child care)	Migrant parents Migrant children Teachers Co-students	Migrant professionals ZAA Hamburg (General degrees) ZAB Bonn (vocational degrees) Uni Access Berlin (University degrees) BSB (school degrees)
Level of organisation	Individual level National level	Individual Municipal National	Individual Municipal National	School success of children	Having my diplomas recognized quickly to be able to enter the labor market municipal
Stakeholders involved	BMBWF (Federal Ministry of Education and Research) State funding (like DAAD Stifungen UH/Hilt HAW universities	Jobcenter employer Volunteer organizations Language schools BSB	Individual Municipal National school	BSB LIS (Landesinstitut zur Lehrerbildung)	Translator Berufsverbände IHK HWK

Education Hamburg	Actions undertaken	Funding for higher education	Finding appropriate language class	School success	Diploma recognition
	Researching funding options online Getting the necessary documents Applying (Passing test)	Meeting the technical requirements (age, no prior degree)	Knowledge about system being granted formal access finding appropriate language class (also online search) being/ succeeding in class	Enrol child in school support child with school work attend parent meetings learn about educational system	Organize all necessary documents have documents translated and pay for that Have documents certified and paid for Get recognition School degrees are easier recognized
	Preconditions for success		Legal status new laws since 8/2019 free/ alternative offers sublementing formal language class system within recognition process eligible to C1 parent meetings children help with language acquisition in arrival center more contact to people	Educating parents about school system and events such as Klassenfahrt, Klassekasse, Elternabend assist parents at parent meetings (multilingual) volunteer offers, activities outside of school intercultural competence of teaching staff	

Education Hamburg	Potential hindrances jeopardizing success	Funding for higher education	Finding appropriate language class	School success	Diploma recognition
	Due to their specific situation migrants/ refugees don't meet these requirements Availability of scholarships more for technical/economic or degrees	Expensive tutoring classes location of school far away from residential area discrimination within school class based on cultural diversity school changes due to insecure status	Dulding expensive alternative offers Intransparent system PA to grant higher classes methodology not suitable for different learning types high distance to available language class age restriction no contact to locals = no practice	Expensive tutoring classes location of school far away from residential area discrimination within school class based on cultural diversity school changes due to insecure status	Process takes very long (up to 3 years) and is very costly, especially university degrees different levels of school quality depending on country intransparent rules for recognition

Education (PA Perspective)	Goal: integration into regular education system
Main actors	migrants teachers of additional supporting measures teachers of regular classes
Goal as perceived by participants	Fast and sustainable integration into regular system
Level of organisation	individual school municipal
Stakeholders involved	BSB as a provider of supporting measures migrants' parents psychologists

Education (PA Perspective)	Goal: integration into regular education system
Actions undertaken	learning groups international preparation classes literacy classes dual program for teens to prepare for vocational training
Preconditions for success	equal opportunities
Level of organisation	traumatized children a lack of qualified psychologists on trauma lack of ongoing support in regular schools overstrained / not trained teachers

Health (Migrant Perspective)				understanding the German health care system
Main Actors	Migrant patient Doctor's practices	Migrant patient	Migrant patient Migrant parents	
Goal as perceived by participants	Getting an appointment as quick as possible when in an emergency (like tooth ache)	Receiving the needed health care service Receiving advice on how to treat a condition	Knowing what has to be paid oneself, what is paid by insurance Knowing what has to be paid What are the different places to visit (Nozialart, Night Pharmacies, Hausarzt, Specialists, Emergency Room), what is paid by insurance	
Level of organisation	Individual/doctor's offices level Individual/patient level	Individual migrant patient Special institutions on district level	Individual patient City institutions	
Stakeholders involved	Doctor's offices Hospitals emergency rooms Pharmacies	Marienkrankenhaus Poliklinik & Mediburo Night Pharmacies	Marienkrankenhaus, IPSO E care Poliklinik & Mediburo Consumer Assistance office (Verbraucherzentrale) Doctors doing primary checkup of arrivers in the accommodations Hanseatic Help, Women Health Team	

Health (Migrant Perspective)				understanding the German health care system
Actions Undertaken	Conducting google search Calling several practices Asking in the pharmacy Going to hospital ER instead early in the morning and waiting long to slide into an empty slot	Conducting research online Asking for advice in (night) pharmacies or migrant health counseling (like Poliklinik and Marienkrankenhaus) Organizing an appointment Organizing a translator Paying the translation themselves	Receiving primary checkup in accommodation (for asylum applicants) Receiving initial information at Jobcenter (insufficient) Researching within own networks Visiting counselling offices, NGOs etc	
Preconditions for success	Having a "Hausarzt" (a regular general practitioner referring to specialists), and knowing about the referral system Digital literacy for google search	Language mediators List of Arabic speaking doctors (not known to many) Having insurance (all but undocumented and freelancers) Translation DURING the doctor's visit	Sensitive doctors Understanding the migrant's difficult situation and not re-traumatizing Language mediators Having access to available information (like list of Arabic speaking doctors, language mediators and special institutions)	

Health (Migrant Perspective)				understanding the German health care system
Potential hindrances jeopardizing success	Pain No time to wait in ER/doctor's practice due to child care responsibilities Poor covering of doctors/not enough available appointments in metropolitan areas	Long distances from residential area to health care location High extra costs for special medication, for daily expense at hospital, for dentist treatment, for additives like Vitamin D Language proficiency Extra costs for translation not paid by insurance Complicated Specialist's language/medical vocabulary Complicated issues/psychological issues Long waiting Quality of doctors	Different rules in the 16 countries Changing rules after 15 months of presence in Germany	
getting an appointment				

Health (PA Perspective)				Goal: Increase Health Care for Refugees
Main actors	District Authority of Altona, Department of Health			
Goal as perceived by participants	Ensure health care			
Level of organisation	Municipal District municipal			
Stakeholders involved	Medical Teams in initial accommodation facilities Social Management in initial accommodation facilities			
Actions undertaken	Establish electronic health card for refugees Establish medical consulting hours in all initial accommodation facilities Educating arrivers about the system			

 Health <i>(PA Perspective)</i>	Goal: Increase Health Care for Refugees
Preconditions for success	provide basic medical care on-site, transfer patients to specialists in regular health care system having interpreters
Potential hindrances jeopardizing success	lack of knowledge from migrants about system / lack of understanding from system about migrants

 Labour <i>(Migrant perspective)</i>	finding a low-skilled job	finding a vocational training	finding a high-skilled job
Main Actors	Individuals Employer Jobcenter	Individual Employer Vocational	Individuals Employer Jobcenter
Goal as perceived by participants	Finding a job that sustains me financially	Finding a vocational training that prepares me for a professional career in that field Being able to finish the training and obtain a degree	Finding a job that matches my abilities and competences
Level of organisation	Individual National level	Individual Municipal National	Individual Municipal National
Stakeholders involved	Café Nova Romani Kafava Migrant economies	IHK BSB Employers Colleagues Jobcenter	Verikom Tor zur Welt

 Labour <i>(Migrant perspective)</i>	finding a low-skilled job	finding a vocational training	finding a high-skilled job
Actions undertaken	Ask friends and networks Going into employer's places and ask for job	(1) Understanding the system and own abilities, converging abilities and work fields (2) Receiving formal access/legal working permit for the application (3) Application procedure (4) Job preparation through internships, part-time jobs and preparational classes (5) Vocational training in the company and school	Look for job online Receive job offers via agent at Jobcenter Organizing necessary documents for the application Applying for job Receiving invitation for interview Going to interview Being offered a job
Preconditions for success	Migrant economies: less discrimination People from countries with large diaspora have it easier since many people speak their language	(2) Since "Migrationspaket" (set of new migration laws issued 8/2019) the legal permit is not as important anymore (3) employers organizations like IHK are interested/motivated to employ migrants (4) preparational offers such as internships, part-time jobs, preparational classes (5) special models of 4 year vocational training (instead of 3) can be agreed upon by company and school	Translators can help get access to internships Internship, but only when you already know the language Work experience from home country Knowing about salaries and tax system as well as working rights and obligations Bundesfreiwilligenleist and other volunteer work to entry Knowledge can be transferred from one country & system to the other; only the language & oftentimes in the way and knowledge of specific standards

 Labour <i>(Migrant perspective)</i>	finding a low-skilled job	finding a vocational training	finding a high-skilled job
Potential hindrances jeopardizing success	Migrant economies rather employ countrymen High competition Negative experiences at Jobcenter Tolerant status (only valid for 3 months, has to be renewed, unclear perspective)	(2) tolerant status. Not many employers know about the new law permitting work (3) motivation of company to employ migrant (3) language proficiency: oftentimes B2 is needed (4) premature picking of training to secure residence permit > high number of dropouts b/c of mismatch (5) lacking professional vocabulary creates problems, even though employees are good at what they do (5) discrimination & mobbing on the job through coworkers	Jobcenter pushes for quick entry in labor market through lower qualified jobs High language requirements for entering job Fear of having to speak German Discrimination, "new guest worker" exclusion due to hijab No recognition/appreciation of degrees recognition process is time and cost-intensive unnecessary detours (like too early internships) tolerant status Being creative/freelancer Different formats and styles of application

<p>Labour (Migrant perspective)</p> <p>Actions undertaken</p>	<p>finding a low-skilled job</p> <p>Ask friends and networks Going into employer's places and ask for job</p>	<p>finding a vocational training</p> <p>(1) Understanding the system and own abilities, covering abilities and work fields (2) Receiving formal access/legal working permit (3) Application procedure (4) Job preparation through internships, part-time jobs and preparational classes (5) Vocational training in the company and school</p>	<p>finding a high-skilled job</p> <p>Look for job online Receive job offers via agent at Jobcenter Organizing necessary documents for the application Applying for job Receiving invitation for interview Going to interview Being offered a job</p>
<p>Preconditions for success</p>	<p>Migrant economies: less discrimination People from countries with large diaspora have it easier since many people speak their language</p>	<p>(2) Since "Migrationspaßer" (set of new migration laws issued 8/2019) the legal permit is not as important anymore (3) employers organizations like IHK are interested/inclined to employ migrants (4) preparational offers such as internships, part-time jobs, preparational classes (5) special models of 4 year vocational training (instead of 3) can be agreed upon by company and school</p>	<p>Translators can help get access to internships Internship, but only when you already know the language Work experience from home country Knowing about salaries and tax system as well as working rights and obligations Bundesfreiwilligendienst and other volunteer works as entry Knowledge can be transferred from one country's system to the other, only the language is oftentimes in the way, and knowledge of specific standards</p>

<p>Labour (Migrant perspective)</p> <p>Potential hindrances jeopardizing success</p>	<p>finding a low-skilled job</p> <p>Migrant economies rather employ countrymen High competition Negative experiences at Jobcenter Tolerance status (only valid for 3 months, has to be renewed, unclear perspective)</p>	<p>finding a vocational training</p> <p>(2) tolerance status. Not many employers know about the new law permitting work (3) motivation of company to employ migrant (3) language proficiency: oftentimes B2 is needed (4) premature picking of training to secure residence permit > high number of dropouts b/c of mismatch (5) lacking professional vocabulary creates problems, even though employees are good at what they do (5) discrimination & mobbing on the job through coworkers</p>	<p>finding a high-skilled job</p> <p>Jobcenter pushes for quick entry in labor market through lower qualified jobs High language requirements for entering job Fear of having to speak German Discrimination, "new guest worker" exclusion due to hijab No recognition/appreciation of degrees recognition process is time and cost-intensive unnecessary detours (like too early internships) toleration status Being creative/freelancer Different formats and styles of application</p>
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<p>Labour (PA perspective)</p> <p>Preconditions for success</p>	<p>Address qualified migrants</p> <p>Hamburg is popular as a city to migrate to for specialists (expected to have high living standards)</p> <p>xx</p>	<p>Integrate Migrants in Labour Market</p> <p>combining forces and knowledge of crucial stakeholders in the field</p> <p>companies can be biased against migrant workers migrants might prefer to work with short contracts on "helper market" than to finish a vocational training and be integrated into the labour market more sustainably because of their precarious financial situation</p>	<p>recognizing certificates, skills and experiences</p> <p>Passing law to standardize and fasten-up the process Valikom Project</p> <p>Time and cost intensive High level of resilience needed Difficulty to find company that conducts the qualification /compensatory measures with migrant especially for niche professions</p>
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<p>Housing (Migrant perspective)</p> <p>Main Actors</p>	<p>permission to live outside public housing</p> <p>Individuals Only refugees Foreigners Registration Agency Public welfare housing Förderin & wohnen</p>	<p>finding a flat</p> <p>Individual migrant Social worker Saga, Hansa and other (social) housing cooperatives Private landlords Housing Agency Jobcenter</p>	<p>renting a flat and feeling well in neighborhood</p> <p>Individual migrant Landlord</p> <p>Feeling well in the neighborhood</p>
<p>Goal as perceived by participants</p>	<p>Receiving a permission to move out of public housing</p>	<p>Living in an affordable flat with sufficient space in a self-chosen location</p>	<p>Individual Owner/landlord Neighborhood level</p>
<p>Level of organisation</p>	<p>Municipal/National</p>	<p>Individual Municipal</p>	<p>Individual Owner/landlord Neighborhood level</p>

<p>Housing (Migrant perspective)</p> <p>H</p>	<p>permission to live outside public housing</p>	<p>finding a flat</p>	<p>renting a flat and feeling well in neighborhood</p>
<p>Stakeholders involved</p>	<p>Agency for housing Jobcenter (paying for flat)</p>	<p>Café Nova, Immanuel Kirche, Veddell Exilcafé, Fluchtpunkt, Romani Kafava, Sozialhelfer, Saga, Fördern & Wohnen, Brot & Rosen, Arabic brokers, Municipal help/Sozialhilfe, Starthilfe (Berliner Tor), Counseling services at Baugemeinschaften, NGO Diakonie</p>	<p>Neighbors District social management Social workers associations</p>
<p>Actions undertaken</p>	<p>Apply for refugee status and going to the very long process</p>	<p>Ask friends and networks Research online on real estate pages, Ebay Kleinanzeigen, in Facebook groups and email lists like Linke Liste, Buttclub Get on the waiting list of social housing (Saga) and housing cooperatives Send application/call landlords Receive answer - Go to house visit, receive rental contract</p>	<p>Talk to neighbors Write complaint to landlord Hide personal items (as shoes and bikes) in the apartment</p>

<p>Housing (Migrant perspective)</p> <p>H</p>	<p>permission to live outside public housing</p>	<p>finding a flat</p>	<p>renting a flat and feeling well in neighborhood</p>
<p>Preconditions for success</p>	<p>refugee status (and relative planning security for 3 years)</p>	<p>Refugee status (3 years residence permit) Dringlichkeitsschein ("roter Brief") Arabic brokers Taking flat in fringe areas or ethnic neighborhoods Once you have a flat (eg. in Saga) it's easier to swap flats Having all documents: financial security, income (pay slips), other work documents (contract) positive Schufa report</p>	<p>Safe common spaces Built solutions like Bike racks, safe mail boxes Neighborhood community</p>
<p>Potential hindrances jeopardizing success</p>	<p>Dringlichkeitsbescheinigung Wohnberechtigungsschein Case of hardship Jobcenter paying the rent, providing "income" vis-a-vis landlord Friends and networks Having a Bail from friends/acquaintances</p>	<p>Landlords prefer tenants with steady jobs and incomes High competition Few housing available/tight market Administrations sending out documents via post instead of direct handing over > problem for people without address</p>	<p>toleration status (only valid for 3 months, has to be renewed, unclear perspective)</p>

<p>PARTICIPATION</p>	<p>Goal: Build Social Networks</p>
<p>Main actors</p>	<p>Migrants / NGOs / Neighbors /</p>
<p>Goal as perceived by participants</p>	<p>Meeting people from the majority population</p>
<p>Level of organisation</p>	<p>All levels</p>
<p>Stakeholders involved</p>	<p>NGOs / Communities / (International) Cafés / Sport clubs / Cultural centers</p>
<p>Actions undertaken</p>	<p>Go to event Mingle with locals</p>

<p>PARTICIPATION</p>	<p>Goal: Build Social Networks</p>
<p>Preconditions for success</p>	<p>Productive events that enable encounter Donation base Special fares for migrants/refugees Contact younger people via social media, elderly differently Mouth to mouth communication</p>
<p>Potential hindrances jeopardizing success</p>	<p>High entry/membership fee No participants from host community Not being able to reach the respective communities</p>

3.3. Antwerp

User Stories

Health		Antwerp	
As a... [type of user]	I want... [an action]	So that... [a benefit/value]	Pre-conditions
Migrant	To have information (in my language) about my rights and the regulations regarding health services depending on my status (refugee, undocumented, etc.)	I can follow the necessary steps, and I can best use the offer available	in my language
Migrant	I want access to a fixed GP that speaks my or a common language/english	I can have a GP who I understand I have a person to help me with healthcare problems. I can explain my health problem/situation clearly	Awareness of Belgian system (for example GP (so, emergency unit) GP that speaks my language GP in my neighbourhood, with view on opening hours
Migrant	To know what the normal fees are for consultations and health services	I can I pay the normal/right price I can I pay the normal/right price I can I pay the normal/right price I can I pay the normal/right price	

Health		Antwerp	
As a... [type of user]	I want... [an action]	So that... [a benefit/value]	Pre-conditions
Public Authority	To cooperate with other organisations	We can give tailor-made assistance to newcomers and to support and train staff	
Public Authority	To have updated information about the regulations (national, regional, local) regarding health services depending on migrant's status	we can provide correct information and refer clients to the most suitable service	
Public Authority	Inform migrants about the possibility for getting translations/interpretation support (buddies, volunteers, professionals) during medical consultations		
Public Authority	To know if a client has already a GP, insurances, etc.	We can warn him/her in case something is missing	
Public Authority	To have an overview/list of existing support for mental health issues	we can refer clients to those org.	

Health		Antwerp	
As a... [type of user]	I want... [an action]	So that... [a benefit/value]	Pre-conditions
Migrant	To have correct, structured and understandable information about the regional/local health system (and legal implications) and in my language	I am well informed on how the health system works and use it appropriately. I know how and where to find trustworthy competent GPs or specialists. I can follow the necessary steps, and I can best use the offer available. Information on financial aid for first aid, low and medium critical medical situations To know what are the various documents that I need to provide for accessing free services	In my language in a step-by-step instruction method: E.g.: Legal health insurance → 3. Find a GP that speaks your language →...
Migrant	To join a health insurance	I can receive financial healthcare assistance for myself and/or my family	Clear and centralized information on Belgian health system
Migrant	To know what are the differences between the different health insurance organisations and terms & conditions / To get information about health insurances	I can make a good choice or choose the one the best past for my needs	

Housing			Antwerp	
As a... (type of user)	I want... (an action)	So that... (a benefit/value)	Pre-conditions	
Migrant	To get information on my rights and duties as a tenant	I'm aware of these rules to facilitate and maintain a good housing situation		
Migrant	to find a suitable home according to my needs and resources	I have a home base to start my life in my new country.		
Migrant	to get in touch with the right organisations/people who can provide me with a house	I can meet my housing needs.		
Migrant	to receive reliable information about my rights and obligations when looking for housing	I can take the right steps in finding a proper dwelling		
Migrant	to know what rights and obligations I have towards the landlord and vice versa	I have the right expectations, & can take appropriate steps.		
Migrant	to be able to contact the utility companies	I can have the basic/needed services: heat my house, wash myself, etc.		

Housing			Antwerp	
As a... (type of user)	I want... (an action)	So that... (a benefit/value)	Pre-conditions	
Migrant	to have a central point of contact with regard to my housing needs /	I can quickly get clear information /		
Migrant	To have access to clear, up-to-date and accessible information about housing (e.g. social housing requirements, official support organisations, etc)	I find my way how to subscribe myself for social housing, to get support in searching for a house...		
Migrant	To get transparent information from landlords what type of tenants they are looking for.	I do not lose time applying for an apartment/house I will not get anyway,		
Migrant	To get a 'credit score' so I can show my future landlord that I'm a good tenant / to show proof of my (financial and non-financial) reliability.	Increase my chances to find a house so that landlords are more inclined to rent me a place.	As a migrant I don't want to disclose large amounts of information, especially if it's not housing related and feels like an invasion of my privacy.	

Housing			Antwerp	
As a... (type of user)	I want... (an action)	So that... (a benefit/value)	Pre-conditions	
Migrant	To have visibility on rental prices and availability,	so that I can move to a region that has affordable housing.		
Migrant	visibility on existing rules to qualify for rental subsidies	so that I can avoid renting a place that is not eligible for subsidies.		
Migrant	To be able to refer migrants to a central information point about housing and provide 'tips & tricks'	Migrants can get correct and trustworthy information about housing		
Migrant	to inform new residents quickly and correctly about rights and obligations with regard to housing	they can take appropriate action during their search for a home.		
Migrant	to encourage & inform my residents about energy saving measures	they can live in an energy-efficient manner.		

Housing			Antwerp	
As a... (type of user)	I want... (an action)	So that... (a benefit/value)	Pre-conditions	
Migrant	to encourage & inform my residents about energy saving measures	they can live in an energy-efficient manner.		
Migrant	have an overview of which target group lives where (age, origin, family composition, etc.)	I can communicate in a way that is tailored to the needs of, for example, a neighbourhood.		
Migrant	have an overview of which target group owns or rent a house	They get tailored information about their rights and obligations		
Public Authority	have an overview of initiatives, projects, organisations providing help and assistance to migrants with housing issues	So that I can refer clients to those organisations		
Public Authority	to be able to inform migrants correctly about the expectations of public authorities regarding housing	they can search appropriately.		

Education		Antwerp	
As a... (type of user)	I want... (an action)	So that... (a benefit/value)	Pre-conditions
Migrant	To enrol my child in a primary school	My child can get education	
Migrant	Information about and access to homework- or other school-related support for my children	My child can get support that I cannot provide (due to language barriers or schooling level)	
Migrant	To be able to have a translator during parent-teacher meetings	I can understand what is being said and how my child is doing at school	
Migrant	Information about professional trainings	I can choose and subscribe a training that is within my interests and will help me find a job easier/faster	
Migrant	To have clear, structured information about the education system (primary, secondary and higher education)	I, or my children, make the right choices regarding education	

Education		Antwerp	
As a... (type of user)	I want... (an action)	So that... (a benefit/value)	Pre-conditions
Migrant	As a migrant I want to be able learn Dutch by myself,	as it opens a lot of doors regarding housing, healthcare and employment.	
Migrant	Easy/clear information about professional trainings provided by, amongst others, the respective public employment services	I can increase my competences and therefore my chances to find a job	
Migrant	To know what kind of studies or training I can follow depending on my status		Offer according to migrants status
Migrant	Higher education: to have clear information about legal status and/or residence or nationality conditions	So that I can apply to local (i.e. lower) tuition fees or to qualify for partial or full scholarships	
Migrant	To know the criteria on how to access to free or affordable language classes		

Education		Antwerp	
As a... (type of user)	I want... (an action)	So that... (a benefit/value)	Pre-conditions
Migrant	To have an overview of online applications for self-study (for different groups low schooling level, or advanced...)		
Migrant	To know what to do in the case of a change of school		
Migrant	To know important deadlines about the school/education system, as well as information about happenings that are an important part of school-life.		
Migrant	To know what kind of studies or training I can follow depending on my status		
Migrant	Higher education: to have clear information about legal status and/or residence or nationality conditions	So that I can apply to local (i.e. lower) tuition fees or to qualify for partial or full scholarships	

Education		Antwerp	
As a... (type of user)	I want... (an action)	So that... (a benefit/value)	Pre-conditions
Migrant	(international students/parents with older children) → information about courses taught in English	I know which courses (my child) is able to follow	
Public Authority	Digital support provided to the migrants in order to learn and practise their Dutch	Migrants can learn and practise Dutch on their own rhythm and initiative	
Public Authority	Digital tool for migrants to get them into contact with local volunteers that want to help them with language education	Migrants can find support in practising their language skills	
Public Authority	Make out-of-school organisations (on homework support and leisure activities) more known	Migrants and their children can get more support in their schooling and leisure activities	
Public Authority	Easy/clear information about professional trainings provided by, amongst others, the respective public employment services	I can increase my competences and therefore my chances to find a job	

Labour		Antwerp
As a... (type of user)	I want... (an action)	So that... (a benefit/value)
Migrant	To have access to clear, up-to-date and centralised information about employment-related matters and supporting organisations	I know if and where I can look for a job and if it is not clear, which organisation can support me
Migrant	To have support in learning Dutch on the job (rather than only following a language course which is then a prerequisite to be able to work)	I can practise Dutch and learn the job-specific language /, so that I can apply to a larger, more appropriate, pool of job vacancies.
Migrant	To know how to start my own business	I have an income to live the life I want.
Migrant	access to the labour market	I feel recognised (financially, mentally & socially).
Migrant	a job that matches my level of education, competences, experience & skills	

Labour		Antwerp
As a... (type of user)	I want... (an action)	So that... (a benefit/value)
Migrant	have a central point of contact with regard to my professional needs	I can quickly get clear information and advice
Migrant	to get in touch with the right organisations/people who can provide me with a job	I can proactively contact them for finding a job
Migrant	Clear information about the requirements and procedure for obtaining a work permit	I can prepare the needed documentation and follow the right steps
Migrant	a clear overview of the procedures for renewing my work permit	I can keep my job without any problems.
Migrant	to know where I can go for a professional training	I can increase my chances for finding a job. I can find a job.

Labour		Antwerp
As a... (type of user)	I want... (an action)	So that... (a benefit/value)
Migrant	to know what I have to do to qualify for a professional education	I can start it without any problems.
Migrant	a job that offers space to learn the language as well	I can move forward in different areas at the same time.
Migrant	specialised language courses with a focus on professional language use	I can immediately apply my newly acquired knowledge in a professional context.
Migrant	I want to know what rights and obligations I have towards the employer and vice versa	I have the right expectations & can take appropriate steps.
Migrant	To know where I can get advice or feedback about a work contract or conditions proposed by the employer	I know that I am signing a contract that is correct and suitable

Labour		Antwerp
As a... (type of user)	I want... (an action)	So that... (a benefit/value)
Migrant	to fill in my yearly tax form	so that I comply with local tax legislation and optimize my income
Migrant	visibility on the real language expectations of the employer,	so that I can make my search more efficient.
Public Authority	To follow-up clients who got referred for a job	we know if the referral succeeded
Public Authority	to inform new residents quickly and correctly about possibilities, rights and obligations with regard to employment	they can take appropriate action during their search for a job/professional education.
Public Authority	to encourage & inform my residents/clients quickly and correctly to participate professionally	people can function independently within this society.

Transversal			Antwerp
As a... (type of user)	I want... (an action)	So that... (a benefit/value)	Pre-conditions
Public Authority	To know about discrimination and racism incidents which are often catalysed by language, legal or cultural differences	I can make decisions and work on measures for removing/dismissing such barriers	
Public Authority	To know when or for what situations the help of an interpreter is a must	I can give the right information to migrants and to help to look for an interpreter	
Public Authority	To know the availability of interpreters (individuals and/or organisations) for consultations, facilities and the procedures for requesting them	I can facilitate access to services	

Labour			Antwerp
As a... (type of user)	I want... (an action)	So that... (a benefit/value)	Pre-conditions
Public Authority	To have a good and updated overview of bottleneck professions	I can give this information to clients looking for a job or wishing to reorient their career	
Public Authority	An overview of other initiatives/projects providing assistance to migrants for finding a job	I can transfer clients or work together	
Public Authority	to have an insight into the competencies of my residents/clients	I can make a match between job supply, training supply and the demand for jobs & training.	

Transversal			Antwerp
As a... (type of user)	I want... (an action)	So that... (a benefit/value)	Pre-conditions
Migrant	Checklists of needed steps → step by step instructions on what to put in order (when arriving in Belgium; looking for a house, a job, etc.)	so that I can make use of existing support in its broadest sense	
Migrant	Access or built-up a (social) network. Have contact with local people	so that they can help me with finding housing, healthcare, employment and education. I can practise my language skills and establish social networks	
Migrant	To know what to do in the case of a change (or loss) of house/ school/ GP/ job	I can make a match between job supply, training supply and the demand for jobs & training.	
Public Authority	to make organisations more sensitive to issues of diversity and existing power dynamics.	I can make a match between job supply, training supply and the demand for jobs & training.	

3.4. Madrid

User Stories

Health Madrid	Get the health card	Municipality Local Primary Care Center Migrants or refugees		
Main Actors				
Goal as perceived by participants	Get the documentation to apply for the health card			
Level of organisation	Municipality Level Regional Level			
Stakeholders involved	Migrants and refugees, Local Primary Care Center/Municipality (census)			
Actions undertaken	Get the census certification Submit all documentation in the correct Primary care center Wait for the Health Card			

Health Madrid	Get the health card	finding a vocational training	finding a high-skilled job
Preconditions for success	Digital Literacy Knowledge about administrative procedure		
Potential hindrances jeopardizing success	Language proficiency Digital Literacy Lack of information		

Labour Madrid	Get a job		
Main actors	Migrants Employers		
Goal as perceived by participants	Look for a job (personal nets mainly and apps)		
Level of organisation	Local level		
Stakeholders involved	Migrants Employers		
Actions undertaken	Accurate CV Look for a job into the personal nets or/and using apps Enroll on the job		
Preconditions for success	Digital literacy		
Potential hindrances jeopardizing success	Digital literacy		

Housing Madrid	Get housing (flat or room)		
Main actors	Migrants or refugees Leaseholders (Normally migrants do not use real-estate services).		
Goal as perceived by participants	Get the "best" place to live		
Level of organisation	Local level		
Stakeholders involved	Migrants or refugees and leaseholders. Normally migrants do not use real-estate services		
Actions undertaken	Accurate CV Look for a job into the Look for a housing solution (room or a flat) between the personal nets or apps. Choose the housing solution. Sign the contract nets or/and using apps Email on the job		
Preconditions for success	Digital Literacy Knowledge about the procedure.		
Potential hindrances jeopardizing success	Digital Literacy Lack of Information Language proficiency		

PARTICIPATION			
Main actors			
Goal as perceived by participants			
Level of organisation			
Stakeholders involved			
Actions undertaken			

PARTICIPATION		
Preconditions for success		
Potential hindrances jeopardizing success		

4. User Personas

Avatar / User Personas		
 Legal Situation	 Digital literacy	 City
Description		
Issues / Problematic		
<p>EXAMPLE ABOVE – Slide at the top is the front – slide in the middle is the backside</p> <p>possibility to pin it against the wall on the right top corner – So when it's on the wall you can flip it to get more detailed infos</p>		

4.1. Bologna

User Personas

Men asylum seekers (sometimes also Dubliners)		
 Asylum seeker	 Limited knowledge and usage	 Bologna
Women asylum seekers (sometimes also Dubliners)		
 Asylum seeker	 Limited knowledge and usage	 Bologna
Women/Men asylum seekers outside of the reception centers (sometimes "Dubliners")		
 Asylum seeker or Irregular migrant	 Limited knowledge and usage	 Bologna

	He waits for the recognition of the refugee status in a reception center. Sometimes he has been returned by authorities of another country to Italy as the first country he entered.
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Job seeking Stay in reception centers(mandatory) Psychological traumas Uncertainty about their future Legal information on asylum Social isolation and distrust
	She waits for the recognition of the refugee status in a reception center. Very limited knowledge of the language, low educational or professional level; illiteracy.
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Mono-parental Job seeking Language courses Stay in reception centers (mandatory) Highly illiterate Uncertainty about their future and child's one Legal information on asylum Psychological traumas Social isolation and distrust
	He/she waits for the recognition of the refugee status outside of the reception system. Better knowledge of the language; low educational or professional level; illiteracy.
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Irregular legal status Emergency housing No contract jobs Hyper-exploitation Fear of the institutions Limited access to public services

Long term migrants with temporary resident permit		
 Migrants with resident permit for work	 Limited knowledge and better usage than the asylum seekers	 Bologna
Migrants with family reunification		
 Migrants with family reunification permit	 Limited knowledge and usage	 Bologna
Second generation migrants (over 18 years old)		
 Until 18 years old, with parent's resident permit, then with their own permit (to study or work)	 High knowledge and usage. Strong digital literacy	 Bologna

	Legal migrant status with long term residence permit; good knowledge of the language, and an acceptable educational or professional level. They normally have strong social network.
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Access to a limited range of job • Housing problem, in particular after family reunification • Uncertainty about future due to the resident permit procedure • Difficult to find an apartment to rent • Diplomas and skills not recognized • Subject to a strong discrimination in Italy • Exploited at work, less pay than the Italian (even if the law declared the contrary)
	Normally women who arrived in Bologna through the family reunification procedure. No knowledge of the language, low educational level, no professional skills.
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Social isolation and fear • Highly illiterate • No knowledge of the country of arrival • Work at home
	Young men and women arrived in Bologna when they were child or born in Bologna from a migrant family
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Subject to migration laws even if they born in Italy or they arrived very young. • risk of being repatriated to a country of origin never seen before • embedded between two cultures, that of origin and that of Italy, forced to act in the name of tradition or repudiated by families

4.2. Hamburg

User Personas

Skilled Refugee		
 Hamburg		
Unskilled Refugee		
 Hamburg		
Unskilled migrant		
 Hamburg		

	He/she already has recognized the refugee status. Has a knowledge of the language, high educational or professional level.
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Housing outside of the public housing facilities Language classes beyond B1 Contact to locals after leaving arrival centres Job seeking Funding for university degree Advanced training

	He/she already has recognized the refugee status. Has no knowledge of the language, low educational or professional level.
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Language courses Vocational training Counselling

	He/she has obtained the toleration status and renewed it over years. Has spent many years in European countries and Germany, has proficient knowledge of German and other European languages. Low educational or professional level.
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Information on Vocational training & orientation Special housing offers/mediators guaranteeing for them Language courses Schooling for grown-ups

	He/she has a high educational or professional level. Oftentimes works in the creative or cultural industry where freelancing work arrangements are more prevalent.
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Orientation on creative labour market Health insurance for freelancers Bails/proof of financial security before landlords Knowledge on volunteer work possibilities (Bundesfreiwilligendienst)

	He/she did not pass the application procedure and is residing without residence permit and thus work permit.
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Health offers without insurance coverage Housing outside of regular market Informal work arrangements

	He/she has a high educational background and educational motivation. Has high knowledge of the language.
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Needs help finding funding for education Needs assistance on housing market as Jobcenter doesn't apply/info on student housing + bail for security deposit Need orientation on job market/volunteer work higher language classes

Freelancers / artists		
Refugee	Very proficient	Hamburg

Unskilled undocumented		
Undocumented	unknown	Hamburg

Migrant student		
Refugee	Very proficient	Hamburg

Migrant parent		
Refugee / Toleration	Varying	Hamburg

	He/she has childcare responsibilities that might hinder them visiting doctor's offices or language classes without childcare support. Might want to support children with school success but missing topical/language knowledge might hinder. Difficult communication with teachers.
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • multilingual school events • childcare offers in language classes • knowledge on offers outside of school

4.3. Madrid

User Personas

"Dubliners"		
 Madrid		
Skilled Refugee		
 Madrid		
Unskilled Refugee		
 Madrid		

	Migrants or refugees who have been returned by authorities of another country to the first country they entered.
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Emergency housing Legal information on asylum for returned migrants or refugees

	He/she has a high educational and professional level. Mostly from Latin America. Spanish speakers. Many used the services provided by NGO's and they have help to be integrated into the society.
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Knowledge about the administrative procedures after the refugee period Job seeking Degree homologation Adaptation to local job market Knowledge about the educational system (especially if with children) Counselling

	He/she has no knowledge of the language, low educational or professional level.
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Job seeking Language courses Counselling

	Migrants with low educational levels
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Housing (renting a room or a flat in the city) Job seeking Degree homologation Counselling Accurate information about rights Accurate information on the administrative procedures, especially regarding the residence permit Formation to develop new skills Information about Spanish nationality

	Skilled migrants who live or/and study in the city
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Housing (renting a flat or a room in the city) Job seeking Homologation of the degrees Information on how to acquire the Spanish nationality Accurate information about rights Accurate information on the administrative procedures, especially regarding the residence permit Information on the access to health services Information about Spanish language courses for non-Latin migrants

Unskilled migrant		
Resident Permit	Medium knowledge and usage	Madrid

Skilled migrant		
Resident card or student card	Very proficient	Madrid

5. Technical Solutions

Technical Solutions - Frontend			
Feature + description	technical options	technical details	Notes
Text-To-Speech & Speech-To-Text - Allow the application to "talk" to the user or allow the user to "talk" to the application	External tools: Google Cloud Text-To-Speech, IBM Watson	these solution could cost money, means transmitting data to a third part (GDPR issue), creates a lockin. Could introduce a big time. It produce a better quality	the "talk" to the application means that there is a way for the speech of the user to be translated to text in the same language of the user. Speech2Text, this is because text is processed, this is because text is evaluated the content; there are different ways to implement this feature depending on the strategy and the implementation. It is difficult to have Speech2Text for language like "Frans".
	Self-developed services	Since AI is present in this consortium skills, maybe it is possible to deploy such service on the MICADO system?	
Translation: generate AI translated texts	In browser capability	At the moment works only in chrome and Firefox or languages that is independent of other systems and is runtime	Some content could be available only in local language and not in the language of the migranta translation tool. The implementation depends on the availability of proper dictionaries of the target language
	External tools: e.g. Google Cloud Translate	At the moment works only in chrome and with not all languages but is independent of other systems and is runtime	
send notification messages	In browser capability	the MICADO system could send messages to migrants when there are deadlines for presenting documents or other important events	this notification could also be triggered by the PA to send specific information to target group

Technical Solutions		
Feature	MICADO's Technical component	Notes
Present data as point on a map (with possible description associated)	- [vue.js + leaflet + api gateway + backend application + postgresql]	There are 2 options for this implementation: the first is custom development if the visualization is very specific (like showing the opening hours and photo of a doctor); the second is the dashboarding component when we need a standard approach (es. there is population data to place on the map)
	- [vue.js + metabase]	
Present historical data as a diagram	vue.js + metabase	
Present data as a table		
Collect documents of a user in a personal wallet	vue.js + upload document + custom backend + postgresql	
Present a flow on a visual graph		

Technical Solutions - Frontend			
Feature + description	technical options	technical details	Notes
annotate documents or images		adding text that appears over an area of text or image that contain explanation	migrants declared that they have difficulty in understanding the meaning or content of documents they have to produce; annotating them in non bureaucratic way could help them understand how to correctly compile it
Upload big data: allow user to upload files of big size (to allow user to transfer exported data in CSV format that are bigger than 10MB)	tusd		transferring big data using internet is difficult, but we all use things like "wettransfer", this is a similar feature
promote own services	vue.js + backend	placing in MICADO migrant application a link and a description to an external web site of the public administration where the migrant can find other services	MICADO is not able to integrate everything but can help migrant to find things and also other web services of PA or NGO could be useful having a form to fill for each service will help spreading the knowledge and making MICADO an index for these options

Technical Solutions - Frontend			
Feature + description	technical options	technical details	Notes
Web mapping: creating interactive maps in browser, e.g. Present data as point on a map (with possible description associated)	Leaflet / openlayers		custom development if the visualization is very specific (like showing the opening hours and photo of a doctor);
	metabase	wholistic dashboarding tool including map view.	A standard dashboarding component (es. there is population data to place on the map)
Data visualization: visualizing data in charts and graphs, e.g. Presenting a flow on a visual graph	d3.js	Javascript library. Feature-rich data visualization tool	
	metabase	wholistic dashboarding tool including map view.	A standard dashboarding component (es. there is population data to place on the map)
Frontend framework: javascript framework for building and connecting all frontend components	vue.js		

Technical Solutions - Backend			
Feature + description	technical options	technical details	Notes
managing places	all users can manage places under its control, NGO courses locations, PA administrative offices		this operation can be done using the CSV import if the data could be loaded with a common representation
append comment to MICADO entities	There could be some set of data (courses, doctors...) that could get comments by the migrants visible in the system to get feedback		this imply that MICADO is able to structure the information (we need to define the COURSE entity, the DOCTOR entity etc)
append evaluation to MICADO entities	a migrant could give a 1-5 star evaluation on the course or doctor or ...		this imply that MICADO is able to structure the information (we need to define the COURSE entity, the DOCTOR entity etc)
aggregate migrants information	if MICADO ask to the migrant information about himself, than the information of all the users can be used to provide added insight to PA (the only that could have a legitimate interest in treating the data)		
provide initial GDPR information and consent collection	This has to be done, here only as reminder, but also for remember that all the data elaboration that we plan to do have to be described		
annotate documents	document templates for administrative process flow could be annotated by NGO to provide easy to understand explanation for migrants		

Technical Solutions - Backend			
Feature + description	technical options	technical details	Notes
database: keep data stored and retrievable	postgresql		We choose the version with the GIS component added to be able to manage spatial data, but we need to validate if we really have spatial data
API gateway: give to the frontend application a single piece of software to talk with	WSO2 API manager		is important to make things simple so the frontend needs to know as few as possible "addresses" of software backend pieces otherwise every time we change one in the backend we need to change also the frontend; also since we use many different software in the backend and all could have different authentication systems we need to make the things easy for the frontend that will present itself only to the gateway and than it will be the guy that will pass the communication to all the others.
CSV import: transforming data coming in CSV format into data usable to plot diagrams or dashboarding	upload_service + backend + postgresql		many times data is kept in excel spreadsheets or data silos that can export a chunk as Comma Separated Values; MICADO is able to ingest this data a make it converge either to a common schema or to expose it as data in the dashboarding tool

Technical Solutions - Backend			
Feature + description	technical options	technical details	Notes
Sign documents: give the option to digitally sign a document	backend		to some users MICADO could give a digital signature that can be used to mark documents as validated to certify to other users that that document has been checked
show administrative process as diagram	vue.js + backend / GoJS		this is a custom feature to code in MICADO to describe a process and give it a proper representation easy to understand
get information based on a set of requests	vue.js + chatbot		giving the MICADO system the capability to provide answers to KNOWN topics (the same in all cities, but each city needs to provide its own content)
link user experience within the application			when the user is requesting information for which there is a process flow the assistant not only gives the explanation but also provide a link to the other part of the application so the user can go to see the flow
adding own information			each user can add information about himself; the migrant can enrich data about himself; the NGO could keep updated the list of offices, opening hours etc

